

FOREWORD

Investigations of crystalline materials and phase transitions of them have been in the focus of scientists for quite a long time. Those materials fascinate because of their shape, transparency, color, hardness, and many other physical properties.

Especially in the vicinity of phase transitions the dependences of certain material coefficients on temperature and/or pressure are often remarkable, technically useable, and can also be well described by theoretical means.

Such materials - in particular single crystals - are in many cases fairly easy to obtain and can be used to prove theoretical predictions.

The classical tool of choice is the theory named after the famous Russian scientist Landau. This phenomenological approach is stringently based on group-theoretical and symmetry-based considerations, and can be vastly applied to model phase transitions.

I worked on the attached collection of papers since about year 2000, exclusively during my leisure time. Some of the papers have been repeatedly refined or slightly modified over the years, because after a while I always needed "a certain distance" to the topics in order to be able to see the bigger picture again and not to get lost in too many side aspects. Also some calculations were cumbersome. That's why I lost sometimes the passion to continue, but it luckily re-flourished after a while.

One of my focus points was on ferroelastic / ferroelastoelectric transitions, because they are just my favorites. On the other side I wanted to describe step-by-step and very practically how to compile the energy expressions and how to derive from them the temperature dependences of the material coefficients and alike.

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PS: Interested parties shall feel free to make use of the attached considerations, but referencing to this source is highly appreciated.

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Table of Contents

1. The Landau Theory of Symmetry Changes at Phase Transitions
(10 pages)
2. The Landau Theory of Phase Transitions - Case Discussions
(49 pages)
3. Calculation of Material Coefficients at Phase Transitions
(25 pages)
4. The Landau Theory of Ferroelastic Phase Transition of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$
(43 pages), with Annex for Improper Case (22 pages)
5. The Landau Theory of Ferroelastoelectric Phase Transition of
 $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (42 pages)
6. The Landau Theory of successive Phase Transitions of LiKSO_4
(57 pages)

The Landau Theory of Symmetry Changes Phase Transitions

1. Introduction

It is assumed that a crystal undergoes a symmetry change at a critical point of temperature T_C and/or pressure p_C .

The change of symmetry from a high temperature phase to a low temperature phase and vice versa is called Phase Transition (PT).

Typically such PT can be described by the appearance of an Order Parameter (OP) at T_C when entering the low temperature phase.

In particular cases the OP can be spontaneous polarization, magnetization, elastic strain,...

Practically PTs are observed, where either the OP changes continuously in the vicinity of T_C (PT of 2nd kind) or discontinuously (PT of 1st kind).

2. Basic Assumptions

- The basic idea of Landau's theory is to describe PTs of 2nd kind on the level of a phenomenological theory
- Thereby the crystal exhibits the symmetry group G_0 in the high temperature phase and transforms at T_C to symmetry group G_1 by losing certain symmetry elements (g) of G_0 .
- G_1 is to be a subgroup of G_0 and the crystal transforms from one to another thermo-

The Landau Theory of Symmetry Changes Phase Transitions

- dynamic equilibrium state.
- Even at PTs of 2nd kind the symmetry of the crystal itself changes discontinuously at T_C
- Generally the symmetry elements (g) of a group G of a crystal leaves the function $\rho(x)$ (represents the probability density that an atom is located at position x) invariant:

$$(R|t) \rho(x) = \rho ((R|t)^{-1} x) = \rho(x) \text{ with } (R|t)=g \in G \quad (1)$$

- Whereby: R represents the rotational part of space group element g
 t represents the translation part of space group element g

- For the high temperature phase we can write:

$$(R|t) \rho_o(x) = \rho_o ((R|t)^{-1} x) = \rho_o(x) \text{ with } (R|t)=g \in G_o \quad T \geq T_C \quad (2)$$

- And for the low temperature phase:

$$(R|t) \rho_1(x) = \rho_1 ((R|t)^{-1} (x) = \rho_1(x) \text{ with } (R|t)=g \in G_1 \quad T < T_C \quad (3)$$

- Thus the density function in the low temperature phase can be written:

$$\rho_1(x) = \rho_o(x) + \delta\rho(x) \quad (4)$$

The Landau Theory of Symmetry Changes Phase Transitions

- If we assume that $\delta\rho(x)$ is small, we can develop it according to terms of basis functions of the irreducible representations (IRs) of group G_0 :

$$\delta\rho(x) = \sum_{*k} \sum_{\alpha} \sum_l \sum_i c_i^{*k,\alpha,l} \varphi_i^{*k,\alpha,l}(x) \quad (5)$$

- The $\varphi_i^{*k,\alpha,l}$ transform according to the respective IR D_α
- Next step is the introduction of a potential function compatible with symmetry G_0 above, below and at the transition point.
- If we assume that $\delta\rho(x)$ is small - especially in the vicinity of the PT-point - a Taylor expansion looks like:

$$F = F(T, p, \rho_0, \rho_1) = F^{(0)} + F^{(1)} + F^{(2)} + F^{(3)} + F^{(4)} + \dots \quad (6)$$

- Depending on $\delta\rho(x)$ F has to be at minimum both, in the high and low temperature phases
- $F^{(0)}$ stands for the identity representation of G_0 and depends on $\rho_0 = C_0\varphi_0$
 $F^{(0)}$ cannot describe any PT.

The Landau Theory of Symmetry Changes Phase Transitions

- The other terms of eq. (6) have to be invariant under the symmetry operations of G_0 too
- The transformations among the $\varphi_i^{*k,\alpha,l}(x)$ within an IR D_α can be considered to happen among the coefficients $c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}$ instead (i.e. acc. to the same rules) (7)
- Since $c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}(T, \rho) = 0$ must hold for $T \geq T_C$ the $c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}$ are related to the OP (8)
- The 1st order term $F^{(1)}$ depends on $f^{(1)}(c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}) = \sum_{i=1}^{d_\alpha} c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}$ (for fixed $*k, \alpha, l$, and d_α being the dimension of D_α). The respective invariant must be ruled out because:
 - a) such term cannot be related to an ID, but always to a reducible representation (for simple explanation see e.g. /3/)
 - b) if a 1st order term is present, the potential F cannot assume any minimum value, depending on the $c_i^{*k,\alpha,l} \left(i.e. \frac{\partial F}{\partial c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}} \neq 0 \right)$
- The term $f^{(2)}(c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}) = \sum_{i=1}^{d_\alpha} (c_i^{*k,\alpha,l})^2$ for fixed $*k, \alpha, l$ relates to the 2nd order invariant. There can be only one! (9)
- Together with eq. (9) a general expression of the invariant $F^{(2)}$ of eq. (6) is:

The Landau Theory of Symmetry Changes Phase Transitions

$$F^{(2)} = \sum_{*k} \sum_{\alpha} \sum_l A_{*k,\alpha,l}(T, p) f_{*k,\alpha,l}^{(2)}(c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}) \quad (10)$$

- whereby the coefficients $A_{*k,\alpha,l}(T, p)$ are not known. Generally their number equals the number of the IRs.
- Typically only one ID and therefore one set $c_i^{*k,\alpha,l} \equiv c_i$ is active / responsible for a particular phase transition. Thus we put the respective $A_{*k,\alpha,l}(T, p) \equiv A$
- Considering also higher order terms, finally F (ref. to eq. (6)) can be written for the specific PT

$$F = F(T, p, c_i) = F^{(0)}(T, p) + A(T, p) \sum_{i=1}^{d_a} c_i^2 + \sum_v B_v(T, p) f_v^{(3)}(c_i) + \sum_s C_s(T, p) f_s^{(4)}(c_i) + \dots \quad (11)$$

- Looking now at eq. (11) it becomes obvious that all $c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}$ can only be zero (in high temperature phase!) if the $A_{*k,\alpha,l}(T, p)$ are all positive definite
- On the other side (below critical point), the $c_i^{*k,\alpha,l}$ can become unequal zero only if the related $A_{*k,\alpha,l}(T, p)$ is negative definite $\rightarrow A_{*k,\alpha,l}$ has to change its sign at the critical temperature T_c (or pressure p_c)
- Taking into account these requirements, the easiest function can be

$$A = A_0(p)(T - T_c) \quad (12)$$

Note: Generally the energy function F (eq. (11)) must be invariant under all symmetry operations (g) of the high temperature phase G_0 . The Subscripts v and s ensure that the sums stretch over all possible invariants

The Landau Theory of Symmetry Changes Phase Transitions

- 3rd order terms*) in eq. (11) can be on principle allowed provided the symmetrized cube $[D]^3$ of ID D_α contains the identity representation of group G_o . The so called *Landau Condition* stipulates that for PTs of 2nd order, 3rd order invariants must not be allowed in F
- This can be quickly checked by calculating the corresponding reduction coefficient (see e.g. /02/):

$$\frac{1}{|G_o|} \sum_{g \in G_o} \chi([D_\alpha(g)]^3) \begin{matrix} = 0 & \text{no 3rd order invariant possible} \\ \neq 0 & \text{3rd order invariant possible} \end{matrix} \quad (13)$$

- Existence of the 4th order terms*) can be formally checked through inspection of the related reduction coefficient
- Important is to note: if the energy expression shall describe the PT under equilibrium/minimum conditions, then $F^{(4)}$ (see eqs. (6) & (11)) has to be positive definite in total (14)

*) Notes:

- The explicit form of the 3rd and 4th order invariants can be derived manually, which might be cumbersome sometimes
- Existence of a 3rd order invariant always means that the PT must be of 1st order. However, the Landau Theory and its principles are usually applicable, as shown elsewhere (e.g. /03/).
- If a PT is of 1st kind, but no 3rd order invariant is allowed, then the energy expression has to be developed up the 6th degree $F^{(6)}$, and 4th-term coefficient C has to be set negative, 6th order coefficient positive.

The Landau Theory of Symmetry Changes Phase Transitions

- Another important precondition of the Landau Theory is the requirement for spatial homogeneity of the crystal. This is called *Lifshitz Condition*.
- If the related reduction coefficient calculates to be zero then spatial homogeneity is expected.

$$\frac{1}{|G_o|} \sum_{g \in G_o} \chi(\{D_\alpha(g)\}^2) \chi_p^{(\nu)}(g) = 0 \quad (15)$$

- Also then any invariant containing terms like $c_i \frac{\partial c_j}{\partial x_p} - c_j \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial x_p}$ *) cannot appear in eq. (11) (16)
- Generally, Landau stated that the real IDs (or physically IDs, being the sum of a complex ID and its conjugated complex ID: $D_\alpha \oplus D_\alpha^*$) which fulfil the Landau- and Lifshitz-Conditions are named *active or acceptable representations* are able to trigger continuous phase transitions (2nd kind)**) (17)

*) Notes:

- If such gradient term(s) should be allowed by symmetry, the Landau approach can be applied as well. Then the energy expression depends also on spatial changes of the OP, measurement dimensions, and not just on the unit cell.
- The OP(s) can be modulated and described by wave lengths which are not commensurable with the dimensions of the crystal lattice (unit cell). Such phases are called incommensurate phases.

***) Note:

- Since ρ_o and $\delta\rho$ are real values (ref. to eqs. (1)&(4)), the basis functions φ_i and the coefficients c_i are also real.

3. Special Case: Proper Phase Transitions

- PTs, described by the star $\vec{k} = 0$ (Γ -point of the Brillouin zone of the high temperature phase) are called *ferrodistortive* because the number of atoms of the primitive unit cell doesn't change at the transition.
- Also the translational symmetry doesn't change.
- *Proper* PTs mean that specific physical properties like electric polarization, magnetization, elastic strain can play the role of the order parameter itself.
- In case of polarization the related PT is to be ferroelectric and in case of strain ferroelastic, respectively.
- The representations of the physical properties (e.g. polarization: polar vector $D_p^{(\nu)}$, strain: polar tensor of rank 2: $[D_p^{(\nu)}]^2$) exhibit specific values for the characters $(\chi_p^{(\nu)}(g))$ for individual symmetry elements g (see e.g. /2/).
- To check whether a certain active ID D_α can lead to a ferroelectric, ferroelastic or other low temperature phase, the related reduction coefficients need to be looked at (whereby $\chi_\alpha(g)$ represent the character of the ID of the concerned symmetry element g):

$$m_E = \frac{1}{|G_o|} \sum_{g \in G_o} \chi_p^{(\nu)}(g) \chi_\alpha(g) \quad (18)$$

The Landau Theory of Symmetry Changes Phase Transitions

- The next topic is how to define in detail the components of polarization, strain, etc. that they can be utilized to describe the PT under consideration
- As shown elsewhere (e.g. /2/) certain projection operators are capable to generate the searched basis functions of an ID

$$\rho_{ij}^{\alpha} = \frac{d_{\alpha}}{|G_o|} \sum_{g \in G_o} D_{\alpha}^{*}(g)_{ij} T(g) \quad (19)$$

Dimension of D_{α}

Conjugated complex element ij of D_{α}

Operator related to symmetry element g

- Application onto an arbitrary function $f(x)$ (e.g. polarization, strain, ...) yield to a decomposition of the function according to its irreducible parts:

$$\rho_{ij}^{\alpha} f(x) = f_{ij}^{\alpha}(x) \quad (20)$$

4. Literature

- /01/ Landau, L.D, Lifshitz, E.M., Lehrbuch der Theoretischen Physik, Statistische Physik, Akademie-Verlag Berlin, 1984
- /02/ Kocinsky, J., "Theory of Symmetry Changes at Continuous Phase Transitions", Elsevier, Amsterdam-Oxford-New York, 1983
- /03/ Toledano P., Toledano J.-C., "The Landau Theory of Phase Transitions", World Scientific Publishing, 1987
- /04/ Izyumov Yu. A., Syromyatnikov V. N., "Phase Transitions and Crystal Symmetry", Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht / Boston / London, 1990
- /05/ Gufan, Yu. M., "Thermodynamic Theory of Phase Transitions", Publisher: University of Rostov on Don, 1982

Landau Theory – Case Discussions & Phase Diagrams

Table of Contents

1. Case: $Q^2 - Q^4$
2. Case: $Q^2 - Q^3 - Q^4$
3. Case: $Q^2 - Q^4 - Q^6$
4. Case: 2-component Order Parameter w/o cubic term
5. Case: 2-component Order Parameter with cubic term
6. Case: 2 coupled 1-component Order Parameters
7. Literature

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

1. Case: $Q^2 - Q^4$

This case deals with the Free Energy Expansion (FEE) in dependence of the Order Parameter (OP) Q .

$$F = AQ^2 + BQ^4 \quad *) \quad (1)$$

with $A = A_0(T-T_0)$, T_0 - Transition Temperature, A_0 and B being positive constants.**)
(2)

The **equation of state** requires:
(3)

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q} = 2AQ + 4BQ^3 = 0$$

This yields two solutions for Q

$$\text{Solution I:} \quad Q = 0 \quad (\text{describes Paraphase}) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Solution II:} \quad Q^2 = -A/(2B) \quad (\text{describes Ferrophase}) \quad (5)$$

The **stability condition** of Solutions I & II requires:

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q^2} \geq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad 2A + 12BQ^2 \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\text{For Solution I (ref. to eq. 4) follows:} \quad A \geq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{stable for } T > T_0 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{For Solution II (ref. to eq. 5) follows:} \quad A \leq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{stable for } T < T_0 \quad (8)$$

*) Note: In FEE a linear term of Q is not allowed. Otherwise the equation of state (eq. 3) can never be fulfilled.

***) Note: B must be positive to guarantee that FEE stays positive for large values of OP Q .

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Next task is to investigate the *validity of Solutions* I & II.

Solution I: $Q = 0$ \rightarrow no limitations (9)

Solution II: $Q^2 = -A/(2B)$ \rightarrow since $B > 0$ must be $A < 0$ (10)

To construct the Phase Diagram, the *Phase Transition Line (PTL)* has to be calculated acc. to condition that the FEE of Para- and Ferrophase has to be equal.

$$F(Q = 0) = F(Q^2 = -A/(2B)) \quad (11)$$

$$0 = A \quad (12)$$

The Phase Transition Line is characterized by $A = 0$, the two phases don't overlap but coincide and acc. to eq. (5) the OP has no jump at PTL, which mean that the investigated *Phase Transition (PT) is of 2nd kind*. The Phase Diagram looks like:

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

2. Case: $Q^2 - Q^3 - Q^4$

This case deals with the Free Energy Expansion (FEE) in dependence of the Order Parameter (OP) Q .

$$F = AQ^2 + CQ^3 + BQ^4 \quad *) \tag{1}$$

with $A = A_0(T-T_0)$, T_0 - Transition Temperature, A_0 and B being positive constants. The constant C can be positive or negative. (2)

The **equation of state** requires:
$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q} = 2AQ + 3CQ^2 + 4BQ^3 = 0 \tag{3}$$

$$Q \cdot (2A + 3CQ + 4BQ^2) = 0 \quad *) \tag{4}$$

This yields two principal solutions for Q :

Solution I: $Q = 0$ (describes Paraphase) (5)

Solution II: $Q = Q_{\pm} = -\frac{3C}{8B} \pm \sqrt{\frac{9C^2}{64B^2} - \frac{A}{2B}} = -\frac{3C}{8B} \pm \frac{3C}{8B} \sqrt{1 - \frac{32AB}{9C^2}}$ (6)

(describes Ferrophase)

*) Note: In FEE and in the equation of state (term in brackets of eq. (4)) it becomes visible, that the term CQ^3 respectively CQ is invariant if simultaneously the signs of Q and C change. (7)
 $(+C)(+Q) = (-C)(-Q)$ or respectively $(-C)(+Q) = (+C)(-Q)$.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

The **stability condition** of Solutions I & II requires:

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q^2} \geq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad 2A + 6CQ + 12BQ^2 \geq 0 \quad (8)$$

For Solution I (ref. to eqs. 3,5) follows: $A \geq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{stable for } T > T_o \quad (9)$

For the Solutions II follows with eqs. (8) and (4):

$$2A + 6CQ + 12BQ^2 \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

$$2A + 3CQ + 4BQ^2 = 0$$

$$\text{which together results in } 3CQ + 8BQ^2 \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) can be re-written as: $Q \cdot (3C + 8BQ) \geq 0 \quad (12)$

Stability is guaranteed in 2 cases:

$$\text{1st case: } \quad Q \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad 3C + 8BQ \geq 0 \quad (13)$$

and

$$\text{2nd case: } \quad Q \leq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad 3C + 8BQ \leq 0 \quad (14)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Summary of stability constraints after discussion of solution II (see eq. (6)):

	$Q \geq 0$	$3C + 8BQ \geq 0$	$Q \leq 0$	$3C + 8BQ \leq 0$
Q_+	$A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B}$	$A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B}$	$A \geq 0$	<i>not possible</i>
Q_-	<i>not possible</i>	<i>not possible</i>	$A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B}$	$A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B}$

(15)

Summary:

a) Q_+ is stable and positive if $A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B}$ (16)

b) Q_- is stable and negative if $A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B}$ (17)

Another feature of the solutions Q_+ and Q_- as it can be easily shown using eq. (6):

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \text{if } C < 0 \Rightarrow Q_+ > 0 & -Q_+(C < 0) = Q_-(C > 0) \\
 \text{and} & \text{and}
 \end{array}
 \tag{18}$$

$$\text{if } C > 0 \Rightarrow Q_- < 0 \quad -Q_+(C > 0) = Q_-(C < 0)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Next task is to investigate the **validity of Solutions**.

$$\text{Solution I: } Q = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\text{Solution II: } Q_+ = -\frac{3C}{8B} + \frac{3C}{8B} \sqrt{1 - \frac{32AB}{9C^2}} \quad \text{and} \quad Q_- = -\frac{3C}{8B} - \frac{3C}{8B} \sqrt{1 - \frac{32AB}{9C^2}} \quad (20)$$

Both solutions are real and valid if the root radicand stays positive.

This requires:

$$A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B} \quad (21)$$

Simultaneous consideration of eqs. (16), (17), (18), (21) leads finally to:

$$\rightarrow \text{For } Q_+ : C < 0, \quad A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B} \quad (22)$$

$$\rightarrow \text{For } Q_- : C > 0, \quad A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B} \quad (23)$$

To construct the Phase Diagram, the **Phase Transition Line (PTL)** has to be calculated acc. to condition that the FEEs of Para- and Ferrophase have to be equal.

$$F(Q = 0) = F(Q \neq 0) \quad (24)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

From eqs. (1) and (4) we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= AQ^2 + CQ^3 + BQ^4 \\ 0 &= Q^2(A + CQ + BQ^2) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The solution $Q^2=0$ can only occur provided $A \equiv 0$ in Q_+ (ref. to eq. (6)). This is not possible because Q_+ is stable already for bigger values of A :

$$A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B}$$

The solution $(A+CQ+BQ^2)=0$ leads together with eqs. (4), (23) to $A = C^2/(4B)$ (26) which is the equation of PTL.

Since the stability limits of Para- and Ferrophase do overlap (ref. to eqs. (9), (22), (23)) the Phase Transition is of 1st kind.

Also from eqs. (6), (26) we calculate for the jump of OP at the transition line:

$$Q_{PTL} = -\frac{2A}{C} \quad \text{or with eq. (26)} \quad Q_{PTL} = -\frac{C}{2B} \quad (27)$$

The actual phase transition temperature calculates from eq. (2) together with eq. (26) as:

$$T_{PTL} = T_C = T_o + \frac{C^2}{4BA_o} \quad (28)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Since the stability regions of both phases do overlap, the OP exhibits a jump at the PTL and the investigated **Phase Transition (PT) is of 1st kind**.

This is always the case if a 3rd order OP-Term in FEE appears.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

3. Case: $Q^2 - Q^4 - Q^6$

This case deals with the Free Energy Expansion (FEE) in dependence of the Order Parameter (OP) Q .

$$F = AQ^2 + BQ^4 + DQ^6 \quad (1)$$

with $A = A_0(T-T_0)$, T_0 - Transition Temperature, A_0 and D being positive constants. The constant B can be positive or negative. (2)

The **equation of state** requires: $\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q} = 2AQ + 4BQ^3 + 6DQ^5 = 0$ (3)

$$Q \cdot (2A + 4BQ^2 + 6DQ^4) = 0 \quad (4)$$

This yields two solutions for Q :

Solution I: $Q = 0$ (describes Paraphase) (5)

Solution II: $Q^2 = Q_{\pm}^2 = -\frac{B}{3D} \pm \sqrt{\frac{B^2}{9D^2} - \frac{A}{3D}}$

$$Q^2 = Q_{\pm}^2 = -\frac{B}{3D} \pm \frac{B}{3D} \sqrt{1 - \frac{3AD}{B^2}} \quad (describes Ferrophase) \quad (6)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

The **stability condition** of Solutions I & II requires:

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q^2} \geq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad 2A + 12BQ^2 + 30DQ^4 \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

For Solution I (ref. to eq. 5) follows: $A \geq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{stable for } T > T_c \quad (8)$

For the Solutions II eqs. (7) and (4) are valid:

$$2A + 12BQ^2 + 30DQ^4 \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

$$2A + 4BQ^2 + 6DQ^4 = 0 \quad (10)$$

Subtraction: eq. (9) – eq. (10) $\Rightarrow (B + 3DQ^2)Q^2 \geq 0 \quad (11)$

Therefore stability is guaranteed if $(B + 3DQ^2)Q^2 \geq 0$ is valid. (12)

Since $Q^2 \geq 0$ the expression $(B + 3DQ^2)$ has to be positive definite too.

For the Paraphase (Q=0) follows from eq. (9) that $A \geq 0$. (13)

With the solution of eq. (6) certain cases can be discussed and are summarized for the Ferrophase in the following table:

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

	$Q^2 \geq 0$	$B + 3DQ^2 \geq 0$	
$Q_+^2 \geq 0$	$B > 0, A \leq 0$ $B < 0, A \geq 0$	$B > 0, \textit{always ok}$ $B < 0, \textit{not possible}$	(14)
$Q_-^2 \geq 0$	$B > 0, \textit{not possible}$ $B < 0, \textit{always ok}$	$B > 0, \textit{not possible}$ $B < 0, \textit{always ok}$	

Summary:

$$Q_+^2 \text{ is stable if } B > 0, A \leq 0 \tag{15}$$

$$Q_-^2 \text{ is stable if } B < 0 \tag{16}$$

Next task is to investigate the **validity of Solutions**.

Solution I: $Q = 0 \rightarrow$ no limitations (17)

Solution II: Q_+^2 and Q_-^2 (ref. to eq. (6)) are valid if the root radicand remains positive. This calculates:

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

$$1 - \frac{3AD}{B^2} \geq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad A \leq \frac{B^2}{3D} \quad (18)$$

Simultaneous consideration of eqs. (15), (16), (18) leads finally to:

$$\rightarrow \text{For } Q_+^2: B > 0 \text{ and } A \leq 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\rightarrow \text{For } Q_-^2: B < 0 \text{ and } A \leq \frac{B^2}{3D} \quad (20)$$

To construct the Phase Diagram, the **Phase Transition Line (PTL)** has to be calculated acc. to condition that the FEE of Para- and Ferrophase has to be equal.

$$F(Q = 0) = F(Q \neq 0) \quad (21)$$

$$0 = Q^2 \cdot (2A + BQ^2) \quad (22)$$

$$\text{Solution } Q^2 = 0: \quad \text{this requires } A = 0 \text{ and materializes only for } Q_+^2 \quad (23)$$

(ref. to eqs. (6), (19))

\rightarrow describes a Phase Transition of 2nd kind.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Solution $(2A+BQ^2) = 0$: this requires $A = B^2/(4D)$ (equation of PTL) and can be only materialized for Q_-^2 (ref. to limitation for A as stipulated in eqs. (18, 20)).
→ describes a Phase Transition of 1st kind. (24)

Inserting eq. (24) into Q_- (ref. to eq. (6)) yield for the jump of the OP at the PTL:

$$Q^2_{PTL} = -\frac{B}{2D} \quad (25)$$

With eq. (24) this can be re-written to be:

$$Q^2_{PTL} = -\frac{2A}{B} \quad (26)$$

The actual phase transition temperature calculates from eq. (2) together with eq. (24) as:

$$T_{PTL} = T_C = T_o + \frac{B^2}{4DA_o} \quad (27)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

The Phase Diagram for solution Q_+^2 looks like:

It represents a **Phase Transition of 2nd kind**.

The Phase Diagram for solution Q_-^2 looks like:

It represents a **Phase Transition of 1st kind**.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

4. Case: 2-component Order Parameter w/o cubic term

This case deals with the Free Energy Expansion (FEE) in dependence of two Order Parameter (OP) Components Q_1, Q_2 .

$$F = A(Q_1^2 + Q_2^2) + B_1(Q_1^4 + Q_2^4) + B_2Q_1^2Q_2^2 \quad (1)$$

with $A = A_0(T-T_0)$, T_0 - Transition Temperature, A_0 being positive.

The **equations of state** write:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q_1} = 2Q_1 \cdot (A + 2B_1Q_1^2 + B_2Q_2^2) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q_2} = 2Q_2 \cdot (A + 2B_1Q_2^2 + B_2Q_1^2) = 0 \quad (3)$$

This yields to totally 4 possible phases, depending on combinations of (Q_1, Q_2) :

$$\text{Phase 0: } (0, 0) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Paraphase} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Phase 1: } (Q', 0) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Phase 1 *)} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Phase 2: } (Q'', Q'') \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Phase 2} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Phase 3: } (Q_1, Q_2) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Phase 3} \quad (7)$$

*) Note: Another possible Phase $(0, Q')$ is identical to Phase 1. This originates from the symmetry of FEE regarding Q_1, Q_2 .

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Phase 1: $(Q', 0)$

From eqs. (2) & (3) follows

$$\begin{aligned} A + 2B_1 Q'^2 &= 0 \\ Q'^2 &= -\frac{A}{2B_1} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Phase 2: (Q'', Q'')

From eqs. (2) & (3) follows

$$\begin{aligned} A + (2B_1 + B_2) \cdot Q''^2 &= 0 \\ Q''^2 &= -\frac{A}{2B_1 + B_2} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Phase 3: (Q_1, Q_2)

From the difference of eqs. (2) & (3) follows

$$(2B_1 - B_2) \cdot (Q_1^2 - Q_2^2) = 0 \quad (10)$$

Eq. (10) can only be fulfilled if $Q_1^2 = Q_2^2$, which results either in $Q_1 = Q_2 = Q''$ and describing Phase 2 (as above) or in $Q_1 = -Q_2$, $Q_2 = -Q_1$ describing Phase 3. Other values are not permitted.

The calculation of the **stability condition** requires exploitation of 2nd derivatives of FEE:

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1^2} = 2 \cdot (A + 6B_1 Q_1^2 + B_2 Q_2^2) \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_2^2} = 2 \cdot (A + 6B_1 Q_2^2 + B_2 Q_1^2) \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1 \partial Q_2} = 4B_2 Q_1 Q_2 \quad (13)$$

For OPs with 2 components the stability requires:

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1^2} \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1 \partial Q_2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_2 \partial Q_1} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_2^2} \end{vmatrix} \geq 0 \quad (14)$$

Phase 0: (0, 0) Inserting $Q_1=Q_2=0$ into eqs. (11)-(14) leads to the condition $A>0$ for phase 0 (15)

Phase 1: (Q' , 0) Inserting Q' from eq. (8) into eq. (11) leads to $A<0$ (16)

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Inserting Q' from eq. (8) into eq. (14) leads to

$$\frac{(2B_1 - B_2)}{2B_1} \leq 0 \tag{17}$$

Phase 2: (Q'', Q'') Inserting Q'' from eq. (9) into eq. (11) leads to
& also $AB_1 \leq 0$ (18)

Phase 3: $\begin{pmatrix} Q_1 = -Q_2 \\ Q_2 = -Q_1 \end{pmatrix}$ Inserting Q'' from eq. (9) into eq. (14) leads to
 $(2B_1 - B_2) \cdot (2B_1 + B_2) \geq 0$ (19)

Next task is to investigate the **validity of Solutions**.

Phase 0: $(0, 0)$ no restrictions (20)

Phase 1: $(Q', 0)$ From eq. (8) follows that either
 $A < 0$ and $B_1 > 0$ or $A > 0$ and $B_1 < 0$ must hold.
But eq. (16) requires $A < 0$ which results together
with $B_1 > 0$ and eq. (17) that $(2B_1 - B_2) \leq 0$ (21)

Phase 2: (Q'', Q'') From eq. (9) follows
& also $A > 0$ and $2B_1 + B_2 < 0$ or (22)

Phase 3: $\begin{pmatrix} Q_1 = -Q_2 \\ Q_2 = -Q_1 \end{pmatrix}$ $A < 0$ and $2B_1 + B_2 > 0$ (23)

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Eqs. (22, 23) together with eq. (19) yield

$$A > 0 \text{ and } 2B_1 + B_2 < 0 \text{ and } 2B_1 - B_2 < 0 \quad \text{or} \quad (24)$$

$$A < 0 \text{ and } 2B_1 + B_2 > 0 \text{ and } 2B_1 - B_2 > 0 \quad (25)$$

This can be re-written to be

$$A > 0 \text{ and } 2B_1 < -B_2 \text{ and } 2B_1 < B_2 \quad \text{or} \quad (26)$$

$$A < 0 \text{ and } 2B_1 > -B_2 \text{ and } 2B_1 > B_2 \quad (27)$$

Eqs. (26, 27) can be rewritten as:

$$A > 0, 2B_1 < B_2 < -2B_1 \rightarrow \text{not possible since } B_1 > 0 \quad \text{or} \quad (28)$$

$$A < 0, -2B_1 < B_2 < 2B_1 \rightarrow \text{possible since } B_1 > 0 \quad (29)$$

Summary:

$$\text{Phase 0: } (0, 0) \quad A > 0, \text{ no further restrictions} \quad (30)$$

$$\text{Phase 1: } (Q', 0) \quad A < 0, B_1 > 0, \text{ and } 2B_1 < B_2 \quad (31)$$

$$\text{Phase 2: } (Q'', Q'') \quad A < 0, B_1 > 0, \text{ and } -2B_1 < B_2 < 2B_1 \quad (32)$$

$$\text{Phase 3: } \begin{pmatrix} Q_1 = -Q_2 \\ Q_2 = -Q_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad A < 0, B_1 > 0, \text{ and } -2B_1 < B_2 < 2B_1 \quad (33)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

To construct the Phase Diagram, the **Phase Transition Line (PTL)** has to be calculated acc. to condition that the FEE of Para- and Ferrophase has to be equal.

$$\begin{aligned} F(0, 0) &= F(Q', 0) \quad \text{and} \\ F(0, 0) &= F(Q'', Q'') \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Both expressions of eq. (34) are fulfilled if $A=0$, where the stability limits of the adjacent phases coincide. Therefore those **Phase Transitions are of 2nd Kind**.

The transition between Ferrophases 1 and 2 cannot be described within this model since there is no solution of the form $A = A(B_1, B_2)$. To do this, higher order terms of (Q_1, Q_2) would have to be considered in FEE (ref. to eq. (1)).

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

5. Case: 2-component Order Parameter with cubic term

This case deals with the Free Energy Expansion (FEE) in dependence of two Order Parameter (OP) Components Q_1, Q_2 .

$$F = A(Q_1^2 + Q_2^2) + C(Q_1^3 - 3Q_2^2Q_1) + B(Q_1^4 + Q_2^4) \quad (1)$$

with $A = A_0(T - T_0)$, T_0 - Transition Temperature, A_0 being positive, C can be positive or negative, and B must be positive.

The **equations of state** write:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q_1} = 2AQ_1 + 3C(Q_1^2 - Q_2^2) + 4BQ_1(Q_1^2 + Q_2^2) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q_2} = 2AQ_2 - 6CQ_1Q_2 + 4BQ_2(Q_1^2 + Q_2^2) = 0 \quad (3)$$

This yields to totally 6 possible phases, depending on combinations of (Q_1, Q_2) :

$$\text{Phase 0: } (0, 0) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Paraphase} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Phase 1: } (Q', 0) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Ferrophase 1} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Phase 2: } (0, Q'') \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Ferrophase 2} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Phase 3: } (Q''', Q''') \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Ferrophase 3} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Phase 4: } (Q''', -Q''') \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Ferrophase 4} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Phase 5: } (Q_1, Q_2) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Ferrophase 5} \quad (9)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Phase 1: $(Q', 0)$

From eqs. (2) & (3) follows

$$2A + 3CQ' + 4BQ'^2 = 0$$

$$Q' = Q'_\pm = -\frac{3C}{8B} \pm \sqrt{\frac{9C^2}{64B^2} - \frac{A}{2B}} \quad (10)$$

Phase 2: $(0, Q'')$

From eqs. (2) & (3) follows

$$-3CQ''^2 = 0$$

$$2AQ'' + 4BQ''^3 = 0$$

solvable only if $C = 0$ (3rd order term ruled out!)

and yields $Q''^2 = -\frac{A}{2B}$ (11)

Phase 3: (Q''', Q''')

From eqs. (2) & (3) follows

$$A + 4BQ'''^2 = 0$$

$$A - 3CQ''' + 4BQ'''^2 = 0$$

solvable only if $C = 0$ (3rd order term ruled out!)

and yields $Q'''^2 = -\frac{A}{4B}$ (12)

Phase 4: $(Q''', -Q''')$

Same situation as for phase 3.

(13)

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Phase 5: (Q_1, Q_2)

From eqs. (2) & (3) follows $3Q_1^2 - Q_2^2 = 0 \rightarrow 3Q_1^2 = Q_2^2$ (14)

Inserting eq. (14) in eq. (2) yields:

$$A - 3CQ_1 + 8BQ_1^2 = 0 \quad (15)$$

This expression looks similar like the state equation for phase 1 (ref. to eq. (10)). Indeed eq. (15) can be transformed exactly into the state equation by putting

$$Q_1 = -\frac{1}{2}Q' \rightarrow 2A + 3CQ' + 4BQ'^2 = 0 \quad (16)$$

Result: the solutions $(Q', 0)$, and $(\sqrt{3}Q', Q')$ from eq. (14) yield the same results, except some changes in the coefficients.

The related Ferrophases differ only in their arrangements with regard to the Paraphase.

These sets of combinations of the OP-components are summarized as type $\langle Q', 0 \rangle$ which describes phase 1. (17)

Therefore in the following chapters only phase 1 needs to be investigated.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

The calculation of the **stability condition** requires exploitation of 2nd derivatives of FEE:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1^2} &= 2A + 6CQ_1 + 4B \cdot (3Q_1^2 + Q_2^2) \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_2^2} &= 2A - 6CQ_1 + 4B \cdot (Q_1^2 + 3Q_2^2) \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1 \partial Q_2} &= -6CQ_2 + 8BQ_1Q_2\end{aligned}\tag{18}$$

Phase 0: (0, 0) A > 0 (19)

Phase 1: (Q', 0) Mind that only phase 1 needs to be investigated
Inserting (Q₁=Q', Q₂=0) in eq. (18) and making use of
the state equation eqs. (10, 16) yield:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1^2} &= -4A - 3CQ' \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_2^2} &= -9CQ' \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1 \partial Q_2} &= 0\end{aligned}\tag{20}$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Stability requires:

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1^2} \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1 \partial Q_2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_2 \partial Q_1} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_2^2} \end{vmatrix} \geq 0 \quad (21)$$

and results in: $-4A - 3CQ' \geq 0$ and $(-4A - 3CQ') \cdot (-9CQ') \geq 0$ (22a,b)

Eq. (22a) reformed to $4A + 3CQ' < 0$ and multiplied by itself yields:

$$16A^2 + 9C^2Q'^2 + 24ACQ' \geq 0 \quad (23)$$

If the equation of state (eq. (16)) is rearranged to be $16A^2 + 24ACQ' = -32ABQ'^2$ and if this expression is introduced into eq. (23) the 1st stability condition comes out to be:

$$A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B} \quad (24)$$

If eq. (22a) holds then eq. (22b) requires: $-9CQ' \geq 0 \rightarrow CQ' \leq 0$ (25)

Eq. (25) therefore demands that $Q' < 0$ if $C > 0$ and $Q' > 0$ if $C < 0$. (26)

Furthermore, following relations must hold:

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \text{if } C < 0 \Rightarrow Q'_+ > 0 & -Q'_+(C < 0) = Q'_-(C > 0) \\
 \text{and} & \text{and} \\
 \text{if } C > 0 \Rightarrow Q'_- < 0 & -Q'_-(C > 0) = Q'_+(C < 0)
 \end{array} \tag{27}$$

which mean that Q' changes the sign if C changes its sign. This can be easily proven, using eq. (10).

Next task is to investigate the **validity of Solutions**.

Phase 0: $(0, 0)$ no restrictions (28)

Phase 1: $(Q', 0)$ From eq. (10) follows that either the root radicand needs to be positive. The requires:

$$A \leq \frac{9C^2}{32B} \tag{29}$$

and coincides with one stability limit (ref. to eq. (24)).

To construct the Phase Diagram, the **Phase Transition Line (PTL)** has to be calculated acc. to condition that the FEE of Para- and Ferrophase has to be equal.

$$F(Q', 0) = F(0, 0) \tag{30}$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

$$AQ'^2 + CQ'^3 + BQ'^4 = 0 \quad (31)$$

This can be reformed to be $BQ'^2 = -AQ'^2 - CQ'$
Inserted into the state equation (eq. (16)) yields

$$2A + 3CQ' - 4A - 4CQ' = 0 \quad (32)$$

Now the jump of the OP at the PTL calculates:

$$Q'_{PTL} = -\frac{2A}{C} \quad (33)$$

Inserting eq. (33) into eq. (31) yields the expression of the PTL:

$$A = \frac{C^2}{4B} \quad (34)$$

If this is reinserted into eq. (32) another expression for the OP-jump is obtained:

$$Q'_{PTL} = -\frac{C}{2B} \quad (35)$$

The actual phase transition temperature calculates from eq. (2) together with eq. (34) as:

$$T_{PTL} = T_C = T_o + \frac{C^2}{4BA_o} \quad (36)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Since the stability regions of the Para- and Ferrophases do overlap, the OP exhibits a jump at the PTL and the investigated **Phase Transitions (PTs) are of 1st kind**. This is always the case if a 3rd order OP-Term in FEE appears.

A phase transition between the two Ferrophases [$Q'_+ \Leftrightarrow Q'_-$] cannot be described with this model and would require the addition of higher OP-terms in FEE.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

6. Case: 2 coupled 1-component Order Parameters

This case deals with the Free Energy Expansion (FEE) in dependence of two coupled Order Parameters (OPs) – Q and P.

$$F = AQ^2 + BQ^4 + CQ^6 + DP^2 + EP^4 + FQ^2P^2 \quad (1)$$

with $A = A_o(T-T_{oQ})$, T_{oQ} - Transition Temperature regarding Q, A_o , C, E being positive, and B, F can be positive or negative, $D=D_o(T-T_{oP})$, T_{oP} - Transition Temperature regarding P.

The **equations of state** write:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q} = 2AQ + 4BQ^3 + 6CQ^5 + 2FQP^2 = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial P} = 2DP + 4EP^3 + 2FQ^2P = 0 \quad (3)$$

This yields to totally 3 possible phases, depending on combinations of (Q, P) :

$$\text{Phase 0: } (0, 0) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Paraphase} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Phase 1: } (Q', 0) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Ferrophase 1} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Phase 2: } (0, P) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Ferrophase 2} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Phase 3: } (Q'', P) \quad \rightarrow \text{describes Ferrophase 3} \quad (7)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Phase 1: (Q', 0)

From eqs. (2) & (3) follows

$$A + 2BQ'^2 + 3CQ'^4 = 0$$

$$Q'^2 = Q'_{\pm}{}^2 = -\frac{B}{3C} \pm \frac{B}{3C} \sqrt{1 - \frac{3AC}{B^2}} \quad (8)$$

Phase 2: (0, P)

From eqs. (2) & (3) follows

$$D + 2EP^2 = 0$$

$$P^2 = -\frac{D}{2E} \quad (9)$$

Phase 3: (Q''', P)

From eqs. (2) & (3) follows

$$A + 2BQ'''^2 + 3CQ'''^4 + FP^2 = 0$$

$$D + 2EP^2 + FQ'''^2 = 0$$

$$Q'''^2 = Q'''_{\pm}{}^2 = -\frac{\Delta}{12EC} \pm \frac{\Delta}{12EC} \sqrt{1 - \frac{48AE^2C - 24FDEC}{\Delta^2}} \quad (10)$$

$$P^2 = -\frac{D}{2E} - \frac{F}{2E} Q'''^2 \quad \text{with} \quad \Delta = 4BE - F^2 \quad (11,12)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

The calculation of the **stability condition** requires exploitation of 2nd derivatives of FEE:

$$F_{QQ} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q^2} = 2A + 12BQ^2 + 30CQ^4 + 2FP^2 \quad (13)$$

$$F_{PP} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P^2} = 2D + 12EP^2 + 2FQ^2 \quad (14)$$

$$F_{QP} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q\partial P} = 4FQP \quad (15)$$

In particular *):

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q^2} = F_{QQ} \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q^2} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q\partial P} \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P\partial Q} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P^2} \end{vmatrix} \geq 0 \quad (16a,b)$$

Phase 0: (0, 0) From eqs. (13-15) follows $A > 0$ and $D > 0$ for phase 0 (17a,b)

Phase 1: (Q' , 0) From eq. (13, 16a) together with eq. (2) follows $A + BQ'^2 \leq 0$ (ref. also to **case 3** of this paper) and (18)

yield that stability is given for Q'_+ if $A < 0$ and for Q'_- if $A \leq \frac{B^2}{3C}$ (19)

*) Note: As shown in the literature (ref. to Gufan et al.) the inequations are usually evaluated, but in several cases it is appropriate to investigate the expressions as equations, to find the stability limits.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Eq. (16b) as $F_{QQ}F_{PP} - F_{QP}^2 \geq 0$ calculates

$$(A + BQ'^2) \cdot (2D + 2FQ'^2) - 0 \geq 0 \quad (20)$$

Since the 1st factor is negative (ref. to eq. (18))

the expression $(2D + 2FQ'^2)$ also has to be negative or zero, too. (21)

Using eq. (8) this yields the requirement:

$$A = -\frac{3C}{F^2}D^2 + \frac{2B}{F}D \quad (22)$$

From eqs. (18, 21) follows that:

→ if $A > 0$ then $B < 0$ and therefore $\Delta < 0$ (ref. to eq. (12)) (23)

→ if $B > 0$ then $A < 0$ (24)

→ if $D > 0$ then $F < 0$ (25)

→ if $F > 0$ then $D < 0$ (26)

Phase 2: (0, P)

From eq. (13, 16a) together with eq. (3) follows

$$2A + 2FP^2 \geq 0 \quad \text{and requires} \quad A \geq \frac{F}{2E}D \quad (27)$$

Eq. (16b) as $F_{QQ}F_{PP} - F_{QP}^2 \geq 0$ calculates

$$(2A + 2FP^2) \cdot (2D + 12EP^2) - 0 \geq 0 \quad (28)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Since the 1st factor is positive (ref. to eq. (27))
 the expression $(2D + 12EP^2)$ also needs to be positive or zero. Using eq. (9) this yields the requirement: (29)

$$D \leq 0 \quad (30)$$

From eqs. (27, 29) follows that:

$$\rightarrow \text{if } A < 0 \text{ then } F > 0 \quad (31)$$

$$\rightarrow \text{if } F < 0 \text{ then } A > 0 \quad (32)$$

$$\rightarrow \text{if } D < 0 \text{ then } E > 0 \text{ (E is always positive ref. to eq. (1))} \quad (33)$$

Phase 3: (Q''', P)

First step is to investigate F_{QQ} (ref. to eq. (16a)).
 From eq. (13), but easier from eq. (2) via application
 of the chain rule the 2nd derivative F_{QQ} is obtained

$$Q'''^2 \cdot (B + 3CQ'''^2) \geq 0 \quad (34)$$

The 1st factor of eq. (34) requires to be:

$$Q'''^2 \geq 0 \text{ (ref. to validity of solution below – eqs. (48,49))} \quad (35)$$

The 2nd factor of eq. (34) together with eq. (10) yields for:

$$Q_-'''^2 \text{ with } \Delta < 0 \text{ being always stable if root radicand} \\ \text{of eq. (10) is positive} \quad (36a)$$

$Q_-'''^2$ with $\Delta > 0$ being stable if following relation holds

$$A \leq \frac{F}{2E} D - \frac{B^2}{3C} + \frac{B\Delta}{6EC} \quad (36b)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

$Q_+^{m^2}$ with $\Delta > 0$ being always stable if root radicand of eq. (10) is positive (37a)

$Q_+^{m^2}$ with $\Delta < 0$ being stable if following relation holds

$$A \leq \frac{F}{2E} D - \frac{B^2}{3C} + \frac{B\Delta}{6EC} \quad (37b)$$

Moreover from the 2nd factor of eq. (36) follows:

→ if $B < 0$ then $C > 0$ (but C is always positive ref. to eq. (1)) (38)

Next step is the investigation of $F_{QQ}F_{PP} - F_{QP}^2 \geq 0$.

This leads to the expression

$$16Q^{m^2}P^2 \cdot (\Delta + 12CEQ^{m^2}) \geq 0 \quad (39)$$

The 1st factor of eq. (39) to be positive or zero leads to the stability equation (which equals eq. (22)).

$$A = \frac{2B}{F} D - \frac{3C}{F^2} D^2 \quad (40)$$

whereby the 2nd factor of eq. (39) to be also positive or zero yields:

$$A = \frac{F}{2E} D + \frac{\Delta^2}{48CE^2} \quad (41)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Next task is to investigate the *validity of Solutions*.

Phase 0: (0, 0) no restrictions (42)

Phase 1: (Q', 0) From eq. (8) follows that the root radicand needs to be positive for $Q_{\pm}'^2$. This requires: (43)

$$A \leq \frac{B^2}{3C}$$

Moreover the expression for $Q_{\pm}'^2$ has to be positive definite.

→ For $Q_+'^2$: either $B > 0$ and $A < 0$ or $B < 0$ and $A > 0$ (44)

→ For $Q_-'^2$: $B < 0$ is required (45)

Phase 2: (0, P) From eq. (9) follows that $D < 0$ (46)

Phase 3: (Q''', P) From eq. (10) follows that the root radicand of $Q_{\pm}'''^2$ has to be positive: $A \leq \frac{F}{2E} D + \frac{\Delta^2}{48CE^2}$ (47)

Moreover the expression for $Q_{\pm}'''^2$ has to be positive definite.

→ For $Q_+'''^2$: either $\Delta > 0$ and $A \leq \frac{F}{2E} D$ or $\Delta < 0$ and $A \geq \frac{F}{2E} D$ (48)

→ For $Q_-'''^2$: $\Delta < 0$ is required (49)

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Additionally – to ensure that P^2 is also positive definite - from eq. (11) follows that:

$$\rightarrow Q'''^2 \text{ has to be positive definite (ref. to eqs. (48,49))} \quad (50)$$

$$\rightarrow \text{from eq. (11) follows } D+FQ'''^2 < 0, \text{ which yields:} \quad (51)$$

$$\rightarrow D < 0 \text{ and } F < 0 \text{ or} \quad (52)$$

$$\rightarrow D < 0 \text{ and } F > 0 \text{ or} \quad (53)$$

$$\rightarrow D > 0 \text{ and } F < 0 \quad (54)$$

To construct the Phase Diagram, the **Phase Transition Lines (PTLs)** have to be calculated acc. to condition that the FEEs of the adjacent phases have to be equal.

PTL 0-1:

$$\text{- Phase 0 exists if } A \geq 0 \text{ (ref. to eqs. (17a,b,42))} \quad (55)$$

$$\text{- if } \mathbf{B} > \mathbf{0} \text{ than Phase 1 is stable for } A < 0 \text{ (ref. to eq. (24))} \\ \text{and the OP is } Q'_+{}^2 \text{ (ref. to eq. (44)).} \quad (56)$$

$$\rightarrow \text{the stability limits of Phases 0 and 1 coincide at } A=0 \\ \text{and the PT is therefore of 2}^{\text{nd}} \text{ kind.} \quad (57)$$

$$\text{- if } \mathbf{B} < \mathbf{0} \text{ than Phase 1 is stable if } A \leq \frac{B^2}{3C} \text{ (ref. to eq. (19)),} \\ \rightarrow \text{the stability limits overlap and the PT is of 1}^{\text{st}} \text{ kind,} \\ \text{described by OP } Q'_-{}^2 \text{ (ref. to eq. (45)).} \quad (58)$$

- the respective PTL calculates according to

$$F(Q' = 0, P=0) = F(Q', P=0) \quad (59)$$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

and yield $A = B^2/(4C)$ (ref. also to **case 3** of this paper) (60)

PTL 1-2:

From $F(Q', P=0) = F(Q' = 0, P)$ follows after cumbersome calculations for the PTL:

$$2^6 E^4 C^2 A^3 - 2^4 B^2 E^4 C A^2 - 3 \cdot 2^5 C B E^2 A D^2 + 2^4 B^3 E^3 C D^2 + 3^3 D^4 C^2 = 0 \quad (61)$$

This PTL shall go continuously over to the PTL as derived for the PT between Phases 0 and 1 (ref. to eqs. (55-58))

To check this out, D will be set to zero. From eq. (61)

follows: $2^6 E^4 C^2 A^3 - 2^4 B^2 E^4 C A^2 = 0$ (62)

Rewriting eq. (62) results in:

$$A^2 \cdot (4CA - B^2) = 0 \quad (63)$$

and has two different solutions for A:

1. $A=0 \rightarrow$ describes the case where $B>0$ (ref. to eqs. (56,57))

The OP in Phase 1 is Q'_+ (64)

2. $A = B^2/(4C) \rightarrow$ describes case where $B<0$ (ref. to eq. (58))

The OP in Phase 1 is Q'_- (65)

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

PTL 2-3:

From $F(Q''' = 0, P) = F(Q''', P)$ follows after cumbersome calculations for the PTL:

$$A = \frac{F}{2E} D + \frac{\Delta^2}{64CE^2} \quad (66)$$

PTL 1-3:

Since the stability limits of Phases 1 and 3 coincide at $A = \frac{2B}{F} D - \frac{3C}{F^2} D^2$ (ref. to eqs. (22,41))

the PT is therefore of 2nd kind. (67)

PTL 0-3:

From $F(Q=0, P=0) = F(Q'', P)$ follows after intense calculations for the PTL (ref. to Gufan et al.):

$$2^6 E^2 C^2 \tilde{A}^3 + \Delta^2 C \tilde{A}^2 - 2 \cdot 3^2 \Delta C^2 D^2 \tilde{A} - D^2 [\Delta^3 + 3^2 B^2 E^2 D^2] = 0 \quad (68)$$

with $\tilde{A} = A - \frac{FD}{2E}$

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

Summary:

Looking at the stability condition for Phase 3 (ref. to eq. (39)):

$$16Q'''^2 P^2 \cdot (\Delta + 12CEQ'''^2) \geq 0$$

It turns out that in case $\Delta > 0$ the phase transition lines can only be obtained from $Q'''^2 = P^2 = 0$. The accompanied PTs are all of 2nd kind. Remembering that $\Delta = 4BE - F^2$ (ref. to eq. (12)) it requires $B > 0$ and $-2\sqrt{BE} < F < +2\sqrt{BE}$ (“weak coupling”).

The case $\Delta < 0$ (“strong coupling” between OPs Q''' and P) materializes if $B > 0$ and $F > +2\sqrt{BE}$ or respectively if $F < -2\sqrt{|B|E}$ and $B > 0$ or $B < 0$. In this case new PTLs appear.

One word on the symmetry effects on PTs described by two 1-component OPs with a lowest order interaction term like $Q'''^2 \cdot P^2$.

This term is of course compatible with all symmetries. If we assume that Q''' and P belong to different irreducible representations of the high symmetry group of the Paraphase, depending on the magnitude of interaction of the two Order Parameters they can either appear successively or simultaneously (“triggered PT”), when coming from the Paraphase. In the Phase where the two OPs are both present the symmetry is characterized by the intersection of the symmetry elements accompanied by the onsets of Q''' and P .

This means that for triggered PTs the lowering of symmetry is greater than the lowering of symmetry connected with one OP only.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

On the following summary slide an overview is provided about all stability limits and validity constraints for the individual Phases, followed by graphical representations of different cases – with particular focus on the cases with $\Delta < 0$.

Let's look at interesting examples:

1. In all discussed cases the PTL 1-3 describes completely (sometimes partly) a PT of 2nd kind. This is because the stability limits of Phases 1 and 3 coincide there ($A = \frac{2B}{F}D - \frac{3C}{F^2}D^2$). PT of 2nd kind means, that there is no “jump-like” appearance of the OP Q''' at the PTL 1-3 when coming from Phase 1 (decreasing D). Indeed both OPs (Q'_\pm for Phase 1 and Q'''^2 for Phase 3) exactly coincide at PTL 1-3 (same numerical values), and Q'''^2 is going to grow like a typical 2nd order PT OP on top of Q'_\pm - as D further decreases. When Q'''^2 starts to exist in Phase 3 simultaneously OP P becomes present (acc. to eq. (11)).
2. If looking at sequential PTs – e.g. $0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2$ (ref. to slide 41) the 1st transition is of 2nd kind (Q'_+ appears smoothly). If A and D further decrease the subsequent PT $1 \rightarrow 2$ is of 1st kind (provided this transition happens above the Three-Phase Point Q). Exactly at the PTL 1-2 Q'_+ drops to zero (because of lost stability) and P^2 appears with a jump.

Remarkable is the variety of possible PTs in dependence on the coefficients B and F. Even direct PTs between Phases 0 and 3 can be described (“triggered PT”). Assuming that coefficients A and D depend (or not) only on temperature (T) then all relevant PTs lie on the thermodynamic path in the A-D-Plane, described either by $A(T)$ & $B=\text{const.}$ or by $B(T)$ & $A=\text{const.}$ or by $A(T)$ & $B(T)$.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

	Phase	$Q_+^{\prime 2}$	$Q_-^{\prime 2}$	P^2	$Q_+^{m 2}$	$Q_-^{m 2}$
Stability	1	$A \leq 0$	$A \leq \frac{B^2}{3C}$	Not stable	Not stable	Not stable
		$A = \frac{2B}{F}D - \frac{3C}{F^2}D^2$				
	2	Not stable	Not stable	$A \geq \frac{F}{2E}D, D \leq 0$	Not stable	Not stable
3	Not stable	Not stable	Not stable	---	$\Delta > 0$ &no limits	$\Delta < 0$ &no limits
				$\Delta < 0$ & $A \leq \frac{F}{2E}D - \frac{B^2}{3C} + \frac{B\Delta}{6EC}$	$\Delta > 0$ & $A \leq \frac{F}{2E}D - \frac{B^2}{3C} + \frac{B\Delta}{6EC}$	
				Stable if: $A = \frac{2B}{F}D - \frac{3C}{F^2}D^2$ and $A = \frac{F}{2E}D + \frac{\Delta^2}{48CE^2}$		
Validity	1	$A \leq \frac{B^2}{3C}$		---	---	---
		$B > 0$ & $A < 0$ or $B < 0$ & $A > 0$ (means $\Delta < 0$)	$B < 0$ (means $\Delta < 0$)	---	---	---
	2	---	---	$D \leq 0$	---	---
	3	---	---	---	$A = \frac{F}{2E}D + \frac{\Delta^2}{48CE^2}$	
---		---	---	$\Delta > 0$ & $A \leq \frac{F}{2E}D$ or $\Delta < 0$ & $A \geq \frac{F}{2E}D$	$\Delta < 0$	

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

The PTL 2-3 (1st kind) goes over at Point Q to PTL 1-2 (also 1st kind) and then approaches smoothly the PTL 0-1 at A=0. At The Three Phase Point Q PTL 2-3 (ref. to eq. (66)) and PTL 1-3 (2nd kind, ref. to eq. (67)) meet. Also the PTL 1-2 (eq. (61)) goes through Point Q.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

The PTL 2-3 (1st kind) goes over at Point Q to PTL 1-2 (also 1st kind) and then approaches smoothly the PTL 0-1 at $A=B^2/(4C)$. At The Three Phase Point Q PTL 2-3 (ref. to eq. (66)) and PTL 1-3 (2nd kind, ref. to eq. (67)) meet. Also the PTL 1-2 (eq. (61)) goes through Point Q.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

The PTL 1-3 (2nd kind) goes over at the Tricritical Point T to PTL 1-3 (1st kind) and then becomes at Point L the PTL 0-3 (1st kind, "triggered" PT, ref. also to Holakovsky). Further at Point N this PTL becomes the PTL 2-3 (1st kind).

Since $B > 0$ the PT between Phases 0 and 1 is always of 2nd kind (PTL 0-1).

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

The PTL 1-3 (2nd kind) ends at the Tricritical Point T and goes over into the 1st kind stability line of Phase 3 (blue dots). The Point T lies above PTL 0-1 (1st kind, $A = B^2/(4C)$) if $F > -(2|B|E)^{1/2}$ and also above the Three-Phase Point L. This means that in this case the transition between Phases 1 and 3 will be always of 2nd kind (PTL 1-3). The PTL 0-3 (1st kind) is a "triggered" PT (ref. also to Holakovsky). Further at Point N the PTL 2-3 (1st kind) begins.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

With the settings $B > 0, F > 0$ and $\Delta > 0$ all PTs are of 2nd kind. In case $C = 0$ the PTL 1-3 become straight a line.

Landau Theory of Phase Transitions

With the settings $B > 0, F < 0$ and $\Delta > 0$ all PTs are of 2nd kind. In case $C = 0$ the PTL 1-3 become straight a line. This behavior includes the PT-sequence $0 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3$ (path: $A = \text{constant}$ and D decreasing), where all PTs are of 2nd kind (ref. to Holakovsky).

7. Literature

- /01/ Izyumov Yu. A., Syromyatnikov V. N., “Phase Transitions and Crystal Symmetry“, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht / Boston / London, 1990
- /02/ Gufan, Yu. M., “Thermodynamic Theory of Phase Transitions”, Publisher: University of Rostov on Don, 1982
- /03/ Kocinsky, J., “Theory of Symmetry Changes at Continuous Phase Transitions”, Elsevier, Amsterdam-Oxford-New York, 1983
- /04/ Gufan Yu. M, Larin E. S., Sov. Solid State Phys. 22(2), 270(1980)
- /05/ Gufan Yu. M., Torgashev V. I., Sov. Solid State Phys. 22(6), 951(1980)
- /06/ Holakovskiy, J., phys. stat. sol. (b) 56, 615(1973)

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

Table of Contents

1. Theory
2. Elastic Coefficients
3. Dielectric Impermeabilities
4. Piezoelectric Coefficients
5. Clarifying Example Calculation
6. Calculation of Temperature Dependences
7. Summary

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

Issue

**Provided the Thermodynamic Potential function, suitable to describe the Phase Transition under consideration, has been properly derived –
How can the temperature dependences of certain material coefficients be predicted ?**

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

1. Theory

- Basing on standard group theoretical principles the Free Energy Power Expansion has been derived as

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F} (\mathbf{Q}_i, \mathbf{S}_j, \mathbf{P}_k) \quad \text{with} \quad (1)$$

Q_i – Order Parameter (OP) components

S_j – Deformation Tensor components ($j=1\dots6$, Voigt notation)

P_k – Polarization Vector components ($k=1\dots3$)

- For the sake of generality let's assume that external „forces“ are applied to the crystal – according to:

$$\mathbf{T}_j = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}}{\partial \mathbf{S}_j} \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} \text{(External Stress)} \\ \text{(External Electrical Field)} \end{array} \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_k = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}}{\partial \mathbf{P}_k} \quad (3)$$

Note: For a mechanically and electrically „free crystal“ T_j and E_k has to be set = 0!

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

- Solving the equation system (2), (3) we obtain

$$S_j = S_j(Q_i, E_k, T_j) \quad (4)$$

$$P_k = P_k(Q_i, E_k, T_j) \quad (5)$$

- Inserting (4) and (5) into (1) leads to the Free Energy Expression in the form:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{Q}_i, \mathbf{E}_k, T_j) \text{ with } E_k, T_j \text{ being the external „forces“} \quad (6)$$

Note: Q_i are the only internal parameters the Free Energy is depending on.

- That Energy Expression (eq. 6):
 - Is only suitable to determine the equilibrium values of the Order Parameter Components (Q_i), and therefore the possible changes of the crystal symmetry
 - Has no „dynamic“ relevance because the S_j and P_k are not able to follow the fast changes („vibrations“) of the Order Parameter („soft mode“)

$$\frac{\partial S_j}{\partial Q} \approx 0, \quad \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial Q} \approx 0 \quad (7)$$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

2. Elastic Coefficients

- To calculate the elastic coefficients, formulae (1) has to be re-considered:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F} (\mathbf{Q}_i, \mathbf{S}_j, \mathbf{P}_k) \quad (8)$$

taking into account the following conditions:

1. Via certain couplings the Q_i can be dependent on S_j [$Q_i = Q_i (S_j)$]
 2. Via electromechanical couplings P_k can be dependent on S_j
[$P_k = P_k (S_j)$]
- The elastic coefficients shall be calculated under the condition that the Order Parameter (as the „driver“ of the phase transition) can freely move, i.e.

$$\mathbf{K}_i = \partial \mathbf{F} / \partial \mathbf{Q}_i = \mathbf{0} \quad (9)$$

with K_i being the conjugated force with regard to Q_i

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

- Equation (8) has dynamic relevance because the Order Parameter can quasistatically follow the „slow“ changes of the strain S_j

$$\frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial S_j} \neq 0$$

- When putting together the Free Energy Expression according to (1) or (8), the corresponding material coefficients have to be entered under following conditions:
 1. Bare elastic stiffnesses c_{ij}^0 – at $Q_i = 0$ and $P_k = 0$
 2. Bare dielectric impermeabilities β_{ij}^0 - at $Q_i = 0$ and $S_j = 0$
 3. Bare piezoelectric coefficients h_{mn}^0 - at $Q_i = 0$
- Finally the elastic stiffnesses calculate according to:

$$c_{ij} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_i \partial S_j} \quad (10)$$

with c_{ij} being the stiffnesses under the influence of the order parameter's action (ref. to (9) above) when the Order Parameter can freely move.

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

- The mechanical stresses calculate:

$$T_m = \frac{\partial F}{\partial S_m} + \sum_i \frac{\partial F}{\partial Q_i} \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial S_m} \quad (11)$$

 = 0 (ref. to (9))

- Finally the stiffnesses calculate:

$$C_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial S_n} + \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial Q_i} \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial S_n} + \sum_j \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial P_j} \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial S_n} \quad (12)$$

influence of OP's
action

influence of piezoelectric
coupling

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

Goal is now to express: $\frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial S_m} = ?$

From eq. (9) follows that the Order Parameter can freely move: $\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q_j} = K_j = 0$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{d}{dS_n} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q_j} \right) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_j} + \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_j \partial Q_i} \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (13.1)$$

Suggested 'Ansatz': $\Rightarrow \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial S_n} = - \sum_j \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_j} R_{ij}$ (13.2)

Interchange of subscripts $j \leftrightarrow k$ leads to $\Rightarrow \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial S_n} = \left[- \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_k} R_{ik} \right]$ (13.3)

Intersting into eq. (13.1) yield: $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_j} + \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_j \partial Q_i} \cdot \left[- \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_k} R_{ik} \right] = 0$ (13.4)

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

$$\sum_i \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_j \partial Q_i} R_{ik} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_k} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_j} \quad (13.5)$$

Comparison of coefficients results in:

$$\sum_i \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_j \partial Q_i} R_{ik} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & k \neq j \\ 1 & k = j \end{bmatrix} \quad (13.6)$$

and can be compactly re-written as:

$$\sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_j \partial Q_i} R_{ik} = \delta_{kj} \quad (13.7)$$

Note: The term describing the piezoelectric coupling in eq. (12) can be calculated likewise.

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

- Compact, final expression (see e.g. /1, 2/) :

$$C_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial S_n} - \sum_{i,k} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial Q_i} R_{ik} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_k} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial P_k} R_{kv} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial P_v} \quad (14)$$

Note: The stiffnesses are those to be measured at constant electric Field at isothermal conditions

with

$$\delta_{kj} = \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_i \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{ik} \quad \delta_{vj} = \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_k \partial P_j} \cdot R_{kv} \quad (15)$$

being the equations to determine the R-matrix components in (14), $\delta_{xy} = 0$ if $x \neq y$, $\delta_{xy} = 1$ if $x = y$, represents the Kronecker symbol

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

3. Dielectric Impermeabilities

- The calculation of the impermeabilities is analogue to the calculation of the elastic coefficients as shown in Chapter 2.
- The tensor β of the dielectric impermeabilities is related to the tensor of the dielectric susceptibility ε like $(\beta) = (\varepsilon)^{-1}$

$$\beta_{ij} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_i \partial P_j} \quad (16)$$

- The electric fields calculate:

$$E_m = \frac{\partial F}{\partial P_m} + \sum_i \frac{\partial F}{\partial Q_i} \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial P_m} \quad (17)$$

↑
= 0 (rf. to (9))

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

- Finally the impermeabilities calculate:

$$\beta_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial P_n} + \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q_i} \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial P_n} + \sum_j \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_j} \frac{\partial S_j}{\partial P_n} \quad (18)$$

influence of OP's
action

influence of piezoelectric
coupling

- Compact expression after some treatment (see /1, 2/):

$$\beta_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial P_n} - \sum_{i,k} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q_i} R_{ik} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_n \partial Q_k} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_k} R_{kv} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_n \partial S_v} \quad (19)$$

Note: The impermeabilities are those to be measured at const. mech. Stress at isothermal conditions

with

$$\delta_{kj} = \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_i \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{ik} \quad \delta_{vj} = \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_k \partial S_j} \cdot R_{kv} \quad (20)$$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

4. Piezoelectric Modules

- The calculation of the piezomodules is analogue to the calculation of the elastic coefficients and the impermeabilities as shown in chapters 2 and 3.

$$h_{ij} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_i \partial S_j} \quad (21)$$

- The 1st derivatives of the Free Energy Expansion with regard to the polarization components gives the electrical fields (see eq. (17))

$$E_m = \frac{\partial F}{\partial P_m} + \sum_i \frac{\partial F}{\partial Q_i} \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial P_m} \quad (22)$$

= 0 (rf. to (9))

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

- The 2nd derivatives with regard to the strains give the piezoelectric modules:

$$h_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_n} + \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q_i} \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial S_n} \quad (23)$$

influence of OP's
action

$$h_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_n} - \sum_{i,k} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q_i} R_{ik} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_k} \quad (24)$$

with

$$\delta_{kj} = \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_i \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{ik} \quad (25)$$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

5. Clarifying Example Calculation

- Let's assume the phase transition under consideration is driven by a 2-component order parameter Q_i ($i = 1, 2$)
- Exemplarily the matrix components R_{ik} (ref. to (13.7)) are calculated as follows:

$$\delta_{kj} = \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_i \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{ik}$$

1st Case $k \neq j$

$$0 = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1 \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{1k} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_2 \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{2k}$$

using the abbreviations: $F_{11} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1 \partial Q_1}$ *a.s.o.* follows

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

$$0 = F_{11}R_{12} + F_{21}R_{22} \quad (a)$$

$$0 = F_{12}R_{11} + F_{22}R_{21} \quad (b)$$

2nd Case k=j

$$1 = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_1 \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{1j} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_2 \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{2j}$$

$$1 = F_{11}R_{11} + F_{21}R_{21} \quad (c)$$

$$1 = F_{12}R_{12} + F_{22}R_{22} \quad (d)$$

Solution of this system of 4 equations (a)...(d) yields:

$$R_{11} = \frac{F_{22}}{F_{11} \cdot F_{22} - F_{12}^2}$$

$$R_{22} = \frac{F_{11}}{F_{11} \cdot F_{22} - F_{12}^2}$$

$$R_{12} = \frac{F_{12}}{F_{11} \cdot F_{22} - F_{12}^2} = R_{21}$$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

6. Calculation of Temperature Dependences

- Depending on the coupling term between the OP-components (Q_i) and the state parameters (S_i, P_j) in the Free Energy Expansion (1), following typical cases shall be considered (e.g. ref. to /3, 4/):

1. True proper (ferroelastic) phase transition (2nd kind, OP identical to strain component S)

$$F = \frac{1}{2} AS^2 + \frac{1}{4} BS^4 \quad \text{with } A = A_0(T - T_0) \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial S} = 0 \quad \text{leads to} \quad S = 0 \quad \text{for } T > T_0 \quad \text{and} \quad (31)$$

$$S^2 = -\frac{A}{B} \quad \text{for } T < T_0 \quad (32)$$

The stiffness calculate now acc. to eqs. (10) and (14) as:

$$\begin{aligned} c_S &= A = A_0(T - T_0) \quad \text{for } T > T_0 \quad \text{and} \\ c_S &= -2A = -2A_0(T - T_0) \quad \text{for } T < T_0 \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

2. Pseudo-proper (ferroelastic) phase transition (2nd kind)

$$F = \frac{1}{2}AQ^2 + \frac{1}{4}BQ^4 + \frac{1}{2}c_S^o S^2 + DQS \quad \text{with } A = A_o(T - T_o) \quad (34)$$

"free crystal": $\frac{\partial F}{\partial S} = 0 = c_S^o S + DQ \Rightarrow S = -\frac{D}{c_S^o}Q$ (35)

Minimum of F : $\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q} = AQ + BQ^3 + DS$ (36)

Stability: $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q^2} = A + 3BQ^2$ (37)

Next step is the calculation of the free energy F' of the stress free crystal by inserting of eq. (35) into eq. (34). After some calculation yields:

$$F' = \frac{1}{2} \left(A - \frac{D^2}{c_S^o} \right) Q^2 + \frac{1}{4} BQ^4 \quad \text{mit } A' = \left(A - \frac{D^2}{c_S^o} \right) \quad (38)$$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

Reforming the expression for A' results in a change of the transition temperature:

$$A' = A_0(T - T_C) \quad \text{with} \quad T_C = \left(T_0 + \frac{D^2}{c_S^0 A_0} \right) \quad (39)$$

Searching for the minimum of F' (eq. (38)) with respect to Q yield:

$$Q^2 = 0 \quad \text{for} \quad T > T_C \quad (40)$$

$$Q^2 = -\frac{A'}{B} \quad \text{for} \quad T < T_C \quad (41)$$

Now the elastic coefficients are calculated acc. to eq. (14).

$$c_S = c_S^0 - \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S \partial Q} F_{QQ}^{-1} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S \partial Q} = c_S^0 - \frac{D^2}{F_{QQ}} \quad (42)$$

For the Paraphase ($T > T_C$) follows from eq. (42), using $Q=0$ (in eq. (37)) and with reformed eq. (39) with regard to D:

$$c_S = c_S^0 \frac{T - T_C}{(T_C - T_0) + (T - T_C)} \quad (43)$$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

For the Ferrophase ($T < T_C$) follows from eq. (42), using $Q = -A'/B$ (in eq. (37)) and with reformed eq. (39) with regard to D:

$$c_s = c_s^o \frac{\alpha (T_C - T)}{(T_C - T_o) + \alpha (T_C - T)} \quad (44)$$

3. Improper (ferroelastic) phase transition (2nd kind)

It is well known that an improper transition is accompanied by at least two order parameter components (ref. to /5/). For simplicity we confine our calculations here to one order parameter component Q.

$$F = \frac{1}{2} A Q^2 + \frac{1}{4} B Q^4 + \frac{1}{2} c_s^o S^2 + D Q^2 S \quad \text{with } A = A_o (T - T_o) \quad (45)$$

"free crystal": $\frac{\partial F}{\partial S} = 0 = c_s^o S + D Q^2 \Rightarrow S = -\frac{D}{c_s^o} Q^2 \quad (46)$

Minimum of F: $\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q} = A Q + B Q^3 + 2 D S Q \quad (47)$

Stability: $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q^2} = A + 3 B Q^2 + 2 D S \quad (48)$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

Next step is the calculation of the free energy F' of the stress free crystal by inserting of eq. (46) into eq. (45). After some calculation yields:

$$F' = \frac{1}{2} A Q^2 + \frac{1}{4} \left(B - \frac{2D^2}{c_S^o} \right) Q^4 \quad \text{with } B' = \left(B - \frac{2D^2}{c_S^o} \right) \quad (49)$$

As it can be seen the transition temperature is not changed: $T_0 = T_C$

Searching for the minimum of F' (eq. (49)) with respect to Q yield:

$$Q^2 = 0 \quad \text{for } T > T_C \quad (50)$$

$$Q^2 = -\frac{A}{B'} = -\frac{A}{B - \frac{2D^2}{c_S^o}} \quad \text{for } T < T_C \quad (51)$$

For the strain in the phases (ref. to eq. (46)) is valid:

$$S = -\frac{D}{c_S^o} Q^2 \quad (52)$$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

Now the elastic coefficients are calculated acc. to eq. (14).

$$c_s = c_s^o - \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S \partial Q} F_{QQ}^{-1} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S \partial Q} = c_s^o - \frac{4D^2 Q^2}{F_{QQ}} \quad (53)$$

For the Paraphase ($T > T_c$) follows from eq. (53), applying $Q=0$:

$$c_s = c_s^o \quad (54)$$

For the Ferrophase ($T < T_c$) follows from eq. (53), using Q^2 from eq. (51) and with F_{QQ} (see eq. (48)) where the expressions for Q^2 and S (see eqs. (51), (52)) have been inserted:

$$c_s = c_s^o - \frac{2D^2}{B} \quad (55)$$

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

Proper Transition

Pseudo-proper Transition

Improper Transition

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

7. Summary

- The formalism presented firstly by Slonczewski et al. to predict the temperature dependences of isothermal elastic coefficients has been extended with respect to:
 - Dielectric Impermeabilities
 - Piezoelectric Modules

as well as with respect to:

 - Influences of measuring conditions (constant P_j or E_j respectively constant T_k (“free” crystal) or S_k (“clamped” crystal))

- The outlined formalism is fully applicable at phase transitions that are characterized by multi-component order parameters.

Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients at Structural Phase Transitions

Literature

1. Rehwald, W., Adv. In Physics, Vol. 22, 1973, No.6, p. 721 ff.
„The study of structural phase transitions by means of ultrasonic experiments“
2. Slonczewski, J. C. and Thomas, H., Phys. Rev. B1, 3599 (1970),
„Interaction of elastic strain with the structural transition of SrTiO₃“
3. Bulou, A., Rousseau, M., Nouet, J., Key Engineering Materials, Vol. 68, 133-186 (1992)
„Ferroelastic Phase Transitions and Related Phenomena“
4. Carpenter, M. A., Salje, E. K. H., et al. American Mineralogist, Vol 83, 2-22 (1998)
5. Wadhawan, V. K., Phase Transitions, Vol. 3, 3-103 (1982)
„Ferroelasticity and Related Properties of Crystals“

Table of Contents

1. Observations made and models discussed so far
2. Crystal physical Basics
3. Landau Modelling
 - a. Proper Ferroelastic Transition
 - b. Pseudo-Proper Ferroelastic Transition
4. Comparison with experimental results and Summary
5. Literature

Annex: Investigation of an Improper Ferroelastic Transition Model (4mmFmm2)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

1. Observations made and models discussed

$\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$, abbreviated RLHS, was firstly reported to be ferroelastic by Wolejko et al. /01,02/ and by Mroz et al. /03/.

They found that RLHS:

- Is of tetragonal symmetry by habitus (as grown), confirmed by X-ray investigation
- Exhibits a 2nd Order Phase Transition (PT) at 137 K
- Shows twinning in planes perpendicular to the c-axis. Two types of perpendicular domain walls were observed along [010]- and [100]-directions
- Can be transferred to a mono-domain state by application of external stresses along [010]- and [100]-directions, respectively
- Has a polar axis parallel to c-axis above and below the PT-point
- Shows a λ -type specific heat anomaly and almost no anomaly of the dielectric permittivities at the PT-point
- It was concluded that RLHS should undergo a ferroelastic PT according to Aizu's species $4mmFmm2$ /04/.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Other authors as of Hempel et al. /05/, Zúñiga et al. /06/ and later also Mroz et al. /07/ discarded the possibility of Species $4mmFmm2$ and proposed that the symmetry change is correctly described by $4F2$ (Space Groups (SGs): $P4_1=C_4^2$, $P2_1=C_2^2$). The PT is of ferrodistortive (zellengleich, equitranslational) type which means that the number of molecules per unit cell Z ($Z=4$) does not change through the PT /08,09/.

This finding bases on following observations:

- X-ray and neutron diffraction investigations of RLHS
- The crystal exhibits a rotary power (optical activity) of $-0,28^\circ/\text{mm}$ along its c-axis in the paraelastic phase (at $T=293\text{ K}$), which is generally not allowed for a paraphase belonging to Point Group (PG) $4mm$.
- Ferroelastic domain walls (“W’-walls” according to Sapriel’s classification /10/) are present in planes perpendicular to c-axis. They are mutually perpendicular and are rotated around c-axis by 35° (which contradicts to the observations made by Wolejko et al. /01/ because in case $4mmFmm2$ the domain walls would be fix “W-walls”, mutually perpendicular and along either $[100]$ - and $[010]$ - or $[1-10]$ - and $[110]$ - directions).

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

2. Crystal physical Basics

Symmetry elements of PG 4:

$$1, \mathbf{4^1_3}, \mathbf{4^2_3}, \mathbf{4^3_3}$$

\Rightarrow Order of PG 4mm = 4

(symmetry generators are marked red)

Coordinate System (x(1), y(2), z(3)):

$$\vec{a} = a \cdot \vec{e}_x$$

$$\vec{b} = a \cdot \vec{e}_y$$

$$\vec{c} = c \cdot \vec{e}_z$$

(a, c are the lattice parameters, tetragonal $a=b$)

As result of the PT $4 \rightarrow 2$ the fourfold symmetry along z is lost, but c-axis remains the polar axis. Both phases are piezoelectric.

Since the PT is of ferrodistorptive type, the Landau modelling can be done just within the framework of the Point Groups – here PG 4 and PG 2.

All physical quantities and coefficients are related to the coordinate system x, y, z.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Since the ferroelastic phase exhibits symmetry of PG 2 (with two symmetry elements: 1, 4^2_3) the number of possible ferroelastic domains („states“) calculates as:

$$n = \frac{\text{order of PG 4}}{\text{order of PG 2}} = \frac{4}{2} = 2$$

Species 4F2 leads to the spontaneous deformation tensors for the two states /04/:

$$S_1 = \begin{pmatrix} a & b & 0 \\ b & -a & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad S_2 = \begin{pmatrix} -a & -b & 0 \\ -b & a & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with } a = \frac{1}{2}(S_{22} - S_{11}) \text{ and } b = S_{12}$$

According to Sapriel /10/ two mutually perpendicular domain walls are possible:

$$x = p \cdot y \quad x = -y/p \quad \text{with } p = \frac{b + (a^2 + b^2)^{1/2}}{a}$$

Those walls are denominated W'-walls, because their orientation depends on the spontaneous strain components and they again on the temperature.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

3.a Landau Modelling - Proper Ferroelastic Transition

First step to compile the Free Energy Expansion (FEE) for RLHS is to look up the Irreducible Representations (IDs) of PG 4. According to Kovalev /11/:

ID	1	4^1_3	4^2_3	4^3_3
T1	1	1	1	1
T2	1	i	-1	-i
T3	1	-1	1	-1
T4	1	-i	-1	i

IDs T2 and T4 are complex. To get physically meaningful IDs they have to be transformed into real form /08/. Combination (here addition) of complex T2 with its conjugate complex T4 leads to:

ID	1	4^1_3	4^2_3	4^3_3
$A=\Gamma_1$	1	1	1	1
$B=\Gamma_3$	1	-1	1	-1
$E=E_1+E_2$ ($=\Gamma_2+\Gamma_4$)	2	0	-2	0

ID A is the identical representation and not of interest here. Next step is to check which ID can induce PG 2 symmetry.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

As it can be easily shown (e.g. Kocinski /12/) that in case of equitranslational phase transitions only those IDs will lead to a certain low symmetry phase (subgroup of PG 4) where the characters (χ) of the symmetry elements (g) of the subgroup (here PG 2) are either:

$$\begin{aligned} \chi(g) &= 1 && \text{for one-dimensional IDs} \\ &\text{or} \\ \chi(g) &= 0, 2 && \text{for two-dimensional IDs} \end{aligned}$$

→ Only ID B is able to induce the PG 2 Symmetry, consisting of the symmetry elements $1, 4^2_3$.

Next step is the inspection of the reduction coefficients to derive information regarding permitted appearance of ferroelasticity and ferroelectricity. Acc. to /12/, the calculation of

$$m_E = \frac{1}{4} \sum_g \chi_P(g) \cdot \chi_B(g)$$

yields $m_E=2$ regarding ferroelasticity (i.e. allowed!) and $m_E=0$ regarding ferroelectricity (i.e. not allowed!). Of course this is just a formal group-theoretical justification of the obvious behaviour. Meaning, that ferroelasticity is always allowed if the crystal system of the paraphase changes as a result of a PT.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Whether ID B is an active representation can be decided after consideration of the Landau- and Lifshitz-Conditions.

It turns out that the Lifshitz-Condition is always fulfilled if the PT is of ferrodistortive type (characterized by a PT-mode condensing at the Γ -Point of the Brillouin zone and accompanied by a wave-vector $\vec{k} = 0$).

The Landau-Condition is always fulfilled for ferrodistortive PTs if the ID under consideration is one-dimensional and real [12].

Alternatively the following calculation should be done:

$$\frac{1}{|\mathcal{G}_0|} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}_0} [\chi_B]^3(g) \stackrel{?}{=} 0 \quad \text{with}$$

$$[\chi_B]^3(g) = \frac{1}{3} \chi_B(g^3) + \frac{1}{2} \chi_B(g^2) \cdot \chi_B(g) + \frac{1}{6} (\chi_B(g))^3$$

In the present case the result is zero, which confirms that the Landau-Condition isn't violated.

→ The ID B is an active representation and can induce the PT 4→2.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Next step to get Free Energy Expansion (FEE) is to decompose the (ordinary) strain tensor and (ordinary) polarisation vector into their irreducible parts regarding PG 4.

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad S = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{23} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

Utilisation of the projection operator (see e.g. /12/)

$$\rho_{ij}^T f(x) = \frac{d_T}{|G|} \sum_{g_k \in G} T^*(g_k)_{ij} \cdot T(g_k) f(x) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{with } f(x) = P \text{ resp. } S \text{ and} \\ T(g_k) = \text{operator related to} \\ \text{symmetry element } g_k \end{array}$$

yield the following results:

Strain S: $\frac{1}{2}(S_{11}+S_{22}), S_{33}, \frac{1}{2}(S_{11}-S_{22}), S_{23}, S_{13}, S_{12}$ respectively
 $\frac{(S_1 + S_2)}{\sqrt{2}}, S_3, \frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}}, S_4, S_5, S_6$ (in Voigt's Notation /13/ and normalized*)

*) **Note:** $\frac{1}{2}(S_{11}+S_{22})=S_1/2+S_2/2 \rightarrow |S_1/2+S_2/2|=(0,5^2+0,5^2)^{1/2}=1/(2)^{1/2} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}(S_1+S_2)/|S_1/2+S_2/2|=(S_1+S_2)/(2)^{1/2}$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Polarisation P : P_1, P_2, P_3

When decomposing the strain tensor into its symmetry adjusted irreducible parts it turns out that ID B induces two parts of the irreducible strain tensor, namely

$$\left(\frac{S_1 - S_2}{\sqrt{2}}, S_6 \right)$$

In case of a proper ferroelastic transition one part plays the role to the primary OP and couples linearly to the other secondary OP /14/. It is assumed that in both possible cases the coupling between the two OP-parts is weak (i.e. the coefficient l in eq. (2) below is small). Up to now it's not clear which one represents the primary, respectively secondary OP.

Each term of the FEE has to be invariant under the action of all the symmetry elements of PG 4, but it is sufficient to prove this invariance under the action of the “generators” of PG 4 only. These are here just the symmetry operation 4^1_3 .

To this end the transformation properties of S_i , P_k , and Q (Q to be Order Parameter within a pseudo-proper model which will be discussed later) have been compiled:

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

ID	Irreducible Part	After action of 4^1_3
A	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(S_1+S_2)$ S_3	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(S_1+S_2)$ S_3
B	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(S_1-S_2)$ S_6	$-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(S_1-S_2)$ $-S_6$
E	S_4 S_5	$-S_5$ S_4

ID	Irreducible Part	After action of 4^1_3
A	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$
B	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, Q$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, -Q$
E	$\begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -P_2 \\ P_1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$

(1)

ID A induces the identical representation of PG 4 whereby ID B (one component, two parts) induces PG 2 (incl. OP Q), and ID E induces PG 1 (two components).

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

The Free Energy Expansion (FEE) – reflecting the dynamics of the crystal - for a proper ferroelastic transition can now be written:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_S + \mathbf{F}_P + \mathbf{F}_{S-P}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_S &= A(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)^2 + B(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)^4 + C(\mathbf{S}_1 + \mathbf{S}_2)^2 + D\mathbf{S}_3^2 + E(\mathbf{S}_4^2 + \mathbf{S}_5^2) + \\ &\quad + G\mathbf{S}_6^2 + H\mathbf{S}_6^4 + I(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)\mathbf{S}_6 + J(\mathbf{S}_1 + \mathbf{S}_2)\mathbf{S}_3 + K(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)^2(\mathbf{S}_1 + \mathbf{S}_2) + \\ &\quad + L(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)^2\mathbf{S}_3 + M\mathbf{S}_6^2(\mathbf{S}_1 + \mathbf{S}_2) + N\mathbf{S}_6^2\mathbf{S}_3 + n(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)^2\mathbf{S}_3^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_P = O(\mathbf{P}_1^2 + \mathbf{P}_2^2) + \mathbf{P}\mathbf{P}_3^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{S-P} &= R\mathbf{S}_3\mathbf{P}_3 + T(\mathbf{S}_1 + \mathbf{S}_2)\mathbf{P}_3 + U(\mathbf{P}_1\mathbf{S}_4 + \mathbf{P}_2\mathbf{S}_5) + V(\mathbf{P}_1\mathbf{S}_5 - \mathbf{P}_2\mathbf{S}_4) + \\ &\quad + W(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)^2(\mathbf{P}_1^2 + \mathbf{P}_2^2) + X\mathbf{S}_6^2(\mathbf{P}_1^2 + \mathbf{P}_2^2) + Y(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)^2\mathbf{P}_3 + Z\mathbf{S}_6^2\mathbf{P}_3 \end{aligned}$$

We can distinguish between **2 cases** where an acoustic mode is softening:

1. The driving/primary OP is the strain difference $(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)$ and therefore the only temperature-dependent parameter of eq. (1) is $A = A_o(T - T_o)$. (3)

2. The driving/primary OP is the shear strain \mathbf{S}_6 and therefore the only temperature-dependent parameter of eq. (1) is $G = G_o(T - T_o)$. (4)

Note: $(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)$ and \mathbf{S}_6 cannot appear as primary OPs simultaneously, since they do not exhibit a common coefficient in FEE eq. (2) ($A \neq G$, see overleaf).

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

The following material coefficients are used in FEE:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) & B &= \frac{1}{192}(c_{1111}^o - 4c_{1112}^o + 3c_{1122}^o) & C &= \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) \\
 D &= \frac{1}{2}c_{33}^o & E &= \frac{1}{2}c_{44}^o & G &= \frac{1}{2}c_{66}^o & H &= \frac{1}{24}c_{6666}^o \\
 I &= c_{16}^o & J &= c_{13}^o & K &= \frac{1}{24}(c_{111}^o - c_{112}^o) & L &= \frac{1}{12}(c_{113}^o - c_{123}^o) & (5) \\
 M &= \frac{1}{6}c_{166}^o & N &= \frac{1}{6}c_{366}^o & O &= \frac{1}{2}\beta_{11}^o = \frac{1}{2\varepsilon_{11}^o} & n &= \frac{1}{24}(c_{1133}^o - c_{1233}^o) \\
 P &= \frac{1}{2}\beta_{33}^o = \frac{1}{2\varepsilon_{33}^o} & R &= h_{33}^o & T &= h_{31}^o & U &= h_{14}^o & V &= h_{15}^o
 \end{aligned}$$

A straightforward method to elaborate the respective irreducible parts of the material coefficients can be referred to in /15/. Third order elastic constants are listed at Brugger /16/ and 4th order constants at Chung /17/.

It has to be noted that the coefficients in FEE have to satisfy following conditions:

1. c_{ij}^o - bare elastic stiffnesses measured at constant polarization (and at constant OP Q as discussed later in the pseudo-proper model)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

1. β_{ij}^0 - bare dielectric impermeabilities measured at constant strain (and at constant OP Q as discussed later in the pseudo-proper model)
2. h_{kl}^0 - bare piezoelectric modules are those measured at constant OP Q (as discussed later in the pseudo-proper model)

Considering now that no external electrical (E_k) or mechanical (T_i) fields are applied, the solution of the equation system:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F}{\partial S_i} &= T_i = 0 \\ \frac{\partial F}{\partial P_k} &= E_k = 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

yields the State Parameters in dependence of the OP for the “free crystal”:

$$\begin{aligned} & P_1 = P_2 = 0 & P_3 &= K_1(S_1 - S_2)^2 \\ \text{1st case: OP} &= (S_1 - S_2) & (S_1 + S_2) &= K_2(S_1 - S_2)^2 & P_4 &= K_3(S_1 - S_2)^2 \\ & S_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(S_1 - S_2) + \frac{K_2}{2}(S_1 - S_2)^2 & S_2 &= -\frac{1}{2}(S_1 - S_2) + \frac{K_2}{2}(S_1 - S_2)^2 \\ & S_6 &= -\frac{I}{2G}(S_1 - S_2) & S_4 &= S_5 = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Note: K_i are constants, not explicitly shown here.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Inserting the state parameters into FEE (eq. (2)) the following expression is obtained, which is suited to find the equilibrium states of the crystal:

$$F = A'(S_1 - S_2)^2 + B'(S_1 - S_2)^4 \quad (8)$$

with renormalized coefficients $A' = A - \frac{I^2}{4G}$ and B' . (9)

As result the actual PT-temperature is changed from T_0 to $T_c = T_0 + \frac{I^2}{4A_0G}$ (10)

It is assumed that the coupling coefficient $I = c_{16}^o$ is small and therefore yields: $T_0 \approx T_c$.

The equilibrium values of the OP are easily derived from eq. (8):

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial (S_1 - S_2)} = 0 = 2A'(S_1 - S_2) + 4B'(S_1 - S_2)^3 \quad (11)$$

Solution 1: $(S_1 - S_2) = 0$ Paraphase (12)

Solution 2: $(S_1 - S_2)^2 = -\frac{A'}{2B'}$ Ferrophase (13)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

The material coefficients are now calculated acc. to /18,19/:

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{mn}^E &= \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial S_n} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial P_k} R_{kv} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial P_v} \\
 &\quad \text{with } \delta_{vj} = \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_k \partial P_j} \cdot R_{kv} \\
 \beta_{mn}^T &= \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial P_n} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_k} R_{kv} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_n \partial S_v} \\
 &\quad \text{with } \delta_{vj} = \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_k \partial S_j} \cdot R_{kv} \\
 h_{mn} &= \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_n}
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Note: - Stiffnesses are those at constant electric field (E), Impermeabilities at constant mech. stress (T).
 - circled expressions exhibit throughout this paper “piezoelectric coupling terms” that describe the differences between c_{mn}^E and c_{mn}^P respectively between β_{mn}^T and β_{mn}^S .

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Throughout the complete paper following abbreviations are used to describe the piezoelectric coupling terms (acc. to eq. (14)):

$$R_{11} = R_{22} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} c_{33}^o [(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) + (c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)] - c_{13}^{o2}}{(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) [c_{33}^o (c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) - c_{13}^{o2}]} \quad (15)$$

$$R_{12} = R_{21} = -R_{11} = -R_{22} \quad R_{61} = R_{16} = R_{62} = R_{26} = R_{63} = R_{36} = 0$$

$$R_{33} = \frac{c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o}{c_{33}^o (c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) - 2c_{13}^{o2}} \quad R_{13} = R_{31} = R_{23} = R_{32} = \frac{-c_{13}^o}{c_{33}^o (c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) - 2c_{13}^{o2}}$$

$$R_{44} = R_{55} = \frac{1}{c_{44}^o} \quad R_{66} = \frac{1}{c_{66}^o}$$

It needs to be remembered that the expressions:

$$c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o = 4A = 4A_o (T - T_o) \quad (\text{case 1}), \text{ and}$$

$$c_{66}^o = 2G = 2G_o (T - T_o) \quad (\text{case 2}) \text{ are temperature dependent!}$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

$$\chi_{OP}^{-1} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial(S_1 - S_2)^2} = \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) + \left[K_4 + \frac{1}{16}(c_{1111}^o - 4c_{1112}^o + 3c_{1122}^o) \right] (S_1 - S_2)^2 \quad \text{Inverse OP-Susceptibility}$$

$$\Rightarrow \chi_{OP}^{-1} = \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^E - c_{12}^E) = \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) = 2A_o(T - T_o) \quad \text{Paraphase (note: } T_c \approx T_o)$$

$$\Rightarrow \chi_{OP}^{-1} = \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^E + c_{22}^E - 2c_{12}^E) = 4A_o(T_c - T) + 2A_o(T_c - T_o) \quad \text{Ferrophase (note: } T_c \approx T_o)$$

$$\begin{aligned} c_{11}^E &= \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) + \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) + \frac{1}{6}(c_{1111}^o - c_{1112}^o)(S_1 - S_2) + \left[K_4 + \frac{1}{16}(c_{1111}^o - 4c_{1112}^o + 3c_{1122}^o) \right] (S_1 - S_2)^2 \\ c_{22}^E &= \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) + \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) - \frac{1}{6}(c_{1111}^o - c_{1112}^o)(S_1 - S_2) + \left[K_4 + \frac{1}{16}(c_{1111}^o - 4c_{1112}^o + 3c_{1122}^o) \right] (S_1 - S_2)^2 \\ c_{12}^E &= -\frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) + \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) - \left[K_4 + \frac{1}{16}(c_{1111}^o - 4c_{1112}^o + 3c_{1122}^o) \right] (S_1 - S_2)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{with } \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) = 2A = 2A_o(T - T_o)$$

$$c_{16}^E = c_{16}^o \left(1 - \frac{c_{166}^o}{3c_{66}^o} (S_1 - S_2) \right)$$

$$c_{26}^E = c_{16}^o \left(-1 - \frac{c_{166}^o}{3c_{66}^o} (S_1 - S_2) \right)$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{33}^E &= c_{33}^o + \frac{1}{12}(c_{1133}^o - c_{1233}^o)(S_1 - S_2)^2 - \frac{h_{33}^{o2}}{\beta_{33}^o} \\
 c_{31}^E &= c_{13}^o + \frac{1}{6}(c_{113}^o - c_{123}^o)(S_1 - S_2) - Y \frac{2h_{33}^o}{\beta_{33}^o}(S_1 - S_2) \\
 c_{32}^E &= c_{13}^o - \frac{1}{6}(c_{113}^o - c_{123}^o)(S_1 - S_2) + Y \frac{2h_{33}^o}{\beta_{33}^o}(S_1 - S_2) \\
 c_{36}^E &= -\frac{c_{366}^o c_{16}^o}{3c_{66}^o}(S_1 - S_2) + Z \frac{2h_{33}^o c_{16}^o}{\beta_{33}^o c_{66}^o}(S_1 - S_2) \\
 c_{44}^E &= c_{44}^o - \frac{(h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2})}{\beta_{11}^o} \\
 c_{55}^E &= c_{44}^o - \frac{(h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2})}{\beta_{11}^o} \\
 c_{66}^E &= c_{66}^o + K_5(S_1 - S_2)^2 - Z^2 \frac{4c_{16}^{o2}}{\beta_{33}^o c_{66}^{o2}}(S_1 - S_2)^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

morphic coefficient!

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

$$\beta_{11}^T = \beta_{11}^o + 2 \left(W + X \frac{c_{16}^{o2}}{c_{66}^{o2}} \right) (S_1 - S_2)^2 \left(-\frac{h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2}}{c_{44}^o} \right)$$

$$\beta_{22}^T = \beta_{11}^o + 2 \left(W + X \frac{c_{16}^{o2}}{c_{66}^{o2}} \right) (S_1 - S_2)^2 \left(-\frac{h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2}}{c_{44}^o} \right)$$

$$\beta_{33}^T = \beta_{33}^o \left[-R_{11} h_{31}^{o2} - 12R_{11} Y^2 (S_1 - S_2)^2 - \frac{4Z^2 c_{16}^{o2}}{c_{66}^{o3}} (S_1 - S_2)^2 - 2R_{13} h_{31}^o h_{33}^o - R_{33} h_{33}^{o2} \right]$$

$$h_{31} = h_{31}^o + 2Y(S_1 - S_2)$$

$$h_{32} = h_{31}^o - 2Y(S_1 - S_2)$$

$$h_{33} = h_{33}^o$$

$$h_{14} = h_{14}^o$$

$$h_{15} = h_{15}^o$$

$$h_{24} = -h_{15}^o$$

$$h_{25} = h_{14}^o$$

$$h_{36} = -Z \frac{2c_{16}^o}{c_{66}^o} (S_1 - S_2)$$

morphic coefficient!

(18)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

2nd case: OP = S_6

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 = P_2 &= 0 & P_3 &= K_6 S_6^2 \\
 (S_1 + S_2) &= K_7 S_6^2 & S_3 &= K_8 S_6^2 \\
 S_1 &= \frac{K_7}{2} S_6^2 - \frac{I}{4A} S_6 & S_2 &= \frac{K_7}{2} S_6^2 + \frac{I}{4A} S_6 \\
 (S_1 - S_2) &= -\frac{I}{2A} S_6 & S_4 = S_5 &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Note: K_i are constants, not explicitly shown here.

Inserting the state parameters into FEE (eq. (2)) the following expression is obtained, which is suited to find the equilibrium state of the crystal:

$$F = G'S_6^2 + H'S_6^4 \tag{20}$$

with renormalized coefficients $G' = G - \frac{I^2}{4A}$ and H' . (21)

As result the actual PT-temperature is changed from T_0 to $T_c = T_0 + \frac{I^2}{4G_0 A}$ (22)

It is assumed that the coupling coefficient $I = c_{16}^0$ is small and therefore results: $T_0 \approx T_c$.

The equilibrium values of the OP is easily derived from eq. (20):

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial S_6} = 0 = 2G'S_6 + 4H'S_6^3 \tag{23}$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Solution 1: $S_6 = 0$ Paraphase (24)

Solution 2: $S_6^2 = -\frac{G'}{2H'}$ Ferrophase (25)

$$\chi_{OP}^{-1} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_6^2} = c_{66}^o + K_{10} S_6^2 \left[\frac{4Z^2}{\beta_{33}^o} S_6^2 \right] \quad \text{Inverse OP-Susceptibility}$$

$$\Rightarrow \chi_{OP}^{-1} = c_{66}^E = c_{66}^o = 2G_o(T - T_o) \quad \text{Paraphase (note: } T_c \approx T_o)$$

$$\Rightarrow \chi_{OP}^{-1} = c_{66}^E = 4G_o(T_c - T) \left[1 - \frac{Z^2}{2\beta_{33}^o H'} \right] + 2G_o(T_c - T_o) \quad \text{Ferrophase (note: } T_c \approx T_o)$$

$$c_{11}^E = \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) + \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) - \frac{1}{3} \frac{(c_{111}^o - c_{112}^o)c_{16}^o}{c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o} S_6 + \left[K_4 + \frac{1}{16}(c_{1111}^o - 4c_{1112}^o + 3c_{1122}^o) \right] K_9 S_6^2 \quad (26)$$

$$c_{22}^E = \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) + \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) + \frac{1}{3} \frac{(c_{111}^o - c_{112}^o)c_{16}^o}{c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o} S_6 + \left[K_4 + \frac{1}{16}(c_{1111}^o - 4c_{1112}^o + 3c_{1122}^o) \right] K_9 S_6^2$$

$$c_{12}^E = -\frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) + \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) - \left[K_4 + \frac{1}{16}(c_{1111}^o - 4c_{1112}^o + 3c_{1122}^o) \right] K_9 S_6^2$$

$$\frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^E + c_{22}^E - 2c_{12}^E) = \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) + \left[K_4 + \frac{1}{16}(c_{1111}^o - 4c_{1112}^o + 3c_{1122}^o) \right] K_9 S_6^2$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

$$c_{16}^E = c_{16}^o + \frac{c_{166}^o}{3} S_6$$

$$c_{26}^E = -c_{16}^o + \frac{c_{166}^o}{3} S_6$$

$$c_{31}^E = c_{13}^o - \frac{1}{3} \frac{(c_{113}^o - c_{123}^o) c_{16}^o}{c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o} S_6 + Y \frac{4h_{33}^o c_{16}^o}{\beta_{33}^o (c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)} S_6$$

$$c_{32}^E = c_{13}^o + \frac{1}{3} \frac{(c_{113}^o - c_{123}^o) c_{16}^o}{c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o} S_6 - Y \frac{4h_{33}^o c_{16}^o}{\beta_{33}^o (c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)} S_6$$

$$c_{33}^E = c_{33}^o + \frac{1}{12} \frac{(c_{1133}^o - c_{1233}^o) c_{16}^{o2}}{(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)^2} S_6^2 - \frac{h_{33}^{o2}}{\beta_{33}^o}$$

$$c_{36}^E = \frac{1}{3} c_{366}^o S_6 - Z \frac{2h_{33}^o}{\beta_{33}^o} S_6$$

$$c_{44}^E = c_{44}^o - \frac{(h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2})}{\beta_{11}^o}$$

$$c_{55}^E = c_{44}^o - \frac{(h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2})}{\beta_{11}^o}$$

(27)

morphic coefficient!

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \beta_{11}^T &= \beta_{11}^o + 2 \left(X + 4W \frac{c_{16}^{o2}}{(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)^2} \right) S_6^2 \left(\frac{h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2}}{c_{44}^o} \right) \\
 \beta_{22}^T &= \beta_{11}^o + 2 \left(X + 4W \frac{c_{16}^{o2}}{(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)^2} \right) S_6^2 \left(\frac{h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2}}{c_{44}^o} \right) \\
 \beta_{33}^T &= \beta_{33}^o \left(-R_{11} h_{31}^{o2} - 48R_{11} Y^2 \frac{c_{16}^{o2}}{(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)^2} S_6^2 - \frac{4Z^2}{c_{66}^o} S_6^2 - 2R_{13} h_{31}^o h_{33}^o - R_{33} h_{33}^{o2} \right) \quad (28)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$h_{31} = h_{31}^o - 4Y \frac{c_{16}^o}{c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o} S_6 \qquad h_{15} = h_{15}^o \qquad h_{14} = h_{14}^o$$

$$h_{32} = h_{31}^o + 4Y \frac{c_{16}^o}{c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o} S_6 \qquad h_{24} = -h_{15}^o \qquad h_{25} = h_{14}^o$$

$$h_{33} = h_{33}^o \qquad h_{36} = 2ZS_6 \qquad \text{morphie coefficient!}$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Now the Free Energy Expansion (FEE) for a pseudo-proper ferroelastic transition (**case 3**) can be compiled (similar to Quirion /22/ and David /23/):

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_{\text{OP}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{S}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{P}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{S-P}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{S-Q}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{P-Q}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{F}_{\text{OP}} &= A_1 Q^2 + B_1 Q^4 \\
 \mathbf{F}_{\text{S}} &= A(S_1 - S_2)^2 + B(S_1 - S_2)^4 + C(S_1 + S_2)^2 + DS_3^2 + E(S_4^2 + S_5^2) + \\
 &\quad + GS_6^2 + HS_6^4 + I(S_1 - S_2)S_6 + J(S_1 + S_2)S_3 + K(S_1 - S_2)^2(S_1 + S_2) + \\
 &\quad + L(S_1 - S_2)^2 S_3 + MS_6^2(S_1 + S_2) + NS_6^2 S_3 + n(S_1 - S_2)^2 S_3^2 \\
 \mathbf{F}_{\text{P}} &= O(P_1^2 + P_2^2) + PP_3^2 \\
 \mathbf{F}_{\text{S-P}} &= RS_3 P_3 + T(S_1 + S_2)P_3 + U(P_1 S_4 + P_2 S_5) + V(P_1 S_5 - P_2 S_4) + \\
 &\quad + W(S_1 - S_2)^2(P_1^2 + P_2^2) + XS_6^2(P_1^2 + P_2^2) + Y(S_1 - S_2)^2 P_3 + ZS_6^2 P_3 \\
 \mathbf{F}_{\text{S-Q}} &= r(S_1 - S_2)Q + sS_6 Q + tS_3 Q^2 + u(S_1 + S_2)Q^2 + vS_4 S_5 Q + w(S_4^2 + S_5^2)Q^2 \\
 \mathbf{F}_{\text{P-Q}} &= x(P_1^2 + P_2^2)Q^2 + yP_3^2 Q^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

The driving OP is now Q (e.g. related to a soft optical mode) and couples linearly with both $(S_1 - S_2)$ and S_6 (acoustic modes). The only temperature-dependent parameter in eq. (29) is $A_1 = A_{10}(T - T_0)$. (30)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

- The equilibrium values of the OP is easily derived from eq. (32):

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial Q} = 0 = 2A_1'Q + 4B_1'Q^3 \quad (35)$$

Solution 1: $Q = 0$ Paraphase (36)

Solution 2: $Q^2 = -\frac{A_1'}{2B_1'}$ Ferrophase (37)

- To calculate the temperature dependences of the material coefficients (ref. to eq. (40, overleaf) also the 2nd derivatives F_{QQ} (= inverse order parameter susceptibilities) have to be used. They can be derived from FEE (eq. (29)), whereby the equilibrium OP and state parameters (ref. to eqs. (31, 36, 37)) have to be used:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{QQ} &= 2A_1 + 12B_1Q^2 + 2tS_3 + 2u(S_1+S_2) + 2yP_3^2 \\ F_{QQ} &= 2A_1 + (12B_1 + 2tK_{17} + 2uK_{16} + 2yK_{15})Q^2 \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

- This yields finally:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{QQ} &= 2A_{10}(T-T_0) && \text{for the Paraphase, and} \\ F_{QQ} &= 4A_{10}(T_c-T) + 2A_{10}(T_c-T_0) && \text{for the Ferrophase} \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

(see also /20,21/)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

$$c_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial S_n} - \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial Q} \cdot \left[\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q \partial Q} \right]^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial P_k} R_{kv} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial P_v}$$

$$\text{with } \delta_{vj} = \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_k \partial P_j} \cdot R_{kv}$$

$$\beta_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial P_n} - \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q} \cdot \left[\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q \partial Q} \right]^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_n \partial Q} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_k} R_{kv} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_n \partial S_v}$$

$$\text{with } \delta_{vj} = \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_k \partial S_j} \cdot R_{kv} \quad (40)$$

$$h_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_n} - \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q} \cdot \left[\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q \partial Q} \right]^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q}$$

- The material coefficients which will be derived are those valid for isothermal conditions.
- The stiffnesses are those at no applied electric field (E_i) and freely moving OP.
- The dielectric impermeabilities are at no applied mechanical stress (T_{ij}) and freely moving OP.
- The piezoelectric coefficients are those at freely moving OP.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

- Since (S_1-S_2) and S_6 couples linearly with OP Q, as well as inter alia, it doesn't become easily obvious which combination of elastic stiffnesses has to go to zero when approaching T_c .
- According to Boccara /24/ and others /20/ the eigenvalues of the stiffness matrix of the PG 4, related to the eigenvector, which describes the transition to the ferrophase with PG-symmetry 2, must become zero at T_c .
- First step is to look at the transformation matrix D_{kl} ($k,l = 1 \dots 6$) which generates the symmetry adapted strain vector (decomposition into irreducible parts) from the ordinary strain, expressed as a 6 component vector. As shown on page 9 this is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{S_1 + S_2}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{S_1 - S_2}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix}$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

- Application of transformation matrix D_{kl} onto the matrix of stiffnesses of PG 4 leads to the stiffness matrix in form of symmetry adapted (irreducible) parts, like:

$$\tilde{c}_{kl}^o = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o & \sqrt{2}c_{13}^o & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \sqrt{2}c_{13}^o & c_{33}^o & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{2}c_{16}^o \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{44}^o & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{44}^o & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sqrt{2}c_{16}^o & 0 & 0 & c_{66}^o \end{pmatrix}$$

- As shown previously the specific eigenvector being in charge of the PT 4F2 reads like:

$$\tilde{s}_k = \left(0 \quad 0 \quad \frac{s_1 - s_2}{\sqrt{2}} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad s_6 \right)^T$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

- The eigenvalue equation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o - \lambda & \sqrt{2}c_{13}^o & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \sqrt{2}c_{13}^o & c_{33}^o - \lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o - \lambda & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{2}c_{16}^o \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{44}^o - \lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{44}^o - \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sqrt{2}c_{16}^o & 0 & 0 & c_{66}^o - \lambda \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{S_1 - S_2}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

leads to the specific eigenvalue (see also /24/):

$$\lambda_{\pm} = \frac{1}{2} \left[c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o + c_{66}^o \pm \sqrt{(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o - c_{66}^o)^2 + 8c_{16}^{o^2}} \right]^*$$

whereby the solution with '+' has to be discarded because the eigenvalue needs to become zero at T_c .

It has to be noted that the stiffnesses $c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o$ and c_{66}^o (as discussed in cases 1 and 2 above) will individually not become zero at the phase transition point.

* [Note:](#) The expression derived by Quirion et al. /22/ appears to be incorrect.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{11}^E &= c_{11}^o + \frac{1}{6}(c_{111}^o - c_{112}^o)K_{18}Q + K_{20}Q^2 - \frac{(r + 2uQ)^2}{F_{QQ}} \\
 c_{22}^E &= c_{11}^o - \frac{1}{6}(c_{111}^o - c_{112}^o)K_{18}Q + K_{20}Q^2 - \frac{(-r + 2uQ)^2}{F_{QQ}} \\
 c_{12}^E &= c_{12}^o - K_{20}Q^2 - \frac{(r + 2uQ)(-r + 2uQ)}{F_{QQ}} \\
 \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^E + c_{22}^E - 2c_{12}^E) &= \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) - \frac{r^2}{F_{QQ}} && \text{Paraphase} \\
 \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^E + c_{22}^E - 2c_{12}^E) &= \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) + K_{20}Q^2 - \frac{r^2}{F_{QQ}} && \text{Ferrophase} \\
 c_{16}^E &= c_{16}^o \left(1 - \frac{c_{166}^o}{3c_{66}^o} K_{18}Q \right) - \frac{(r + 2uQ)s}{F_{QQ}} \\
 c_{26}^E &= c_{16}^o \left(-1 - \frac{c_{166}^o}{3c_{66}^o} K_{18}Q \right) - \frac{(-r + 2uQ)s}{F_{QQ}} \\
 c_{33}^E &= c_{33}^o + \frac{1}{12}(c_{1133}^o - c_{1233}^o)K_{18}^2Q^2 - \frac{4t^2Q^2}{F_{QQ}} \left[-\frac{h_{33}^{o2}}{\beta_{33}^o} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

$$c_{31}^E = c_{13}^o + \left[\frac{1}{6} (c_{113}^o - c_{123}^o) - \gamma \frac{2h_{33}^o}{\beta_{33}^o} \right] K_{18} Q - \frac{(r + 2uQ)2tQ}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$c_{32}^E = c_{13}^o - \left[\frac{1}{6} (c_{113}^o - c_{123}^o) - \gamma \frac{2h_{33}^o}{\beta_{33}^o} \right] K_{18} Q - \frac{(-r + 2uQ)2tQ}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$c_{36}^E = \left(-\frac{c_{366}^o c_{16}^o}{3c_{66}^o} + Z \frac{2h_{33}^o c_{16}^o}{\beta_{33}^o c_{66}^o} \right) K_{18} Q - \frac{2tsQ}{F_{QQ}} \quad \text{morphic coefficient!}$$

$$c_{44}^E = c_{44}^o + 2wQ^2 \frac{(h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2})}{\beta_{11}^o}$$

$$c_{55}^E = c_{44}^o + 2wQ^2 \frac{(h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2})}{\beta_{11}^o}$$

$$c_{45}^E = vQ \quad \text{morphic coefficient!}$$

$$c_{66}^E = c_{66}^o + \left(K_{21} - Z^2 \frac{4K_{19}^2}{\beta_{33}^o} \right) Q^2 - \frac{s^2}{F_{QQ}}$$

(42)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \beta_{11}^T &= \beta_{11}^o + 2xQ^2 + 2\left(W + X \frac{c_{16}^{o2}}{c_{66}^{o2}}\right)K_{18}^2Q^2 - \frac{h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2}}{c_{44}^o} \\
 \beta_{22}^T &= \beta_{11}^o + 2xQ^2 + 2\left(W + X \frac{c_{16}^{o2}}{c_{66}^{o2}}\right)K_{18}^2Q^2 - \frac{h_{14}^{o2} + h_{15}^{o2}}{c_{44}^o} \\
 \beta_{33}^T &= \beta_{33}^o + 2yQ^2 \left[-12R_{11}Y^2K_{18}^2Q^2 - \frac{4Z^2}{c_{66}^o}K_{19}^2Q^2 - R_{11}h_{31}^{o2} - 2R_{13}h_{31}^oh_{33}^o - R_{33}h_{33}^{o2} \right] \\
 h_{31} &= h_{31}^o + 2YK_{18}Q - \frac{4yK_{15}(rQ^3 + 2uQ^4)}{F_{QQ}} \\
 h_{32} &= h_{31}^o - 2YK_{18}Q - \frac{4yK_{15}(-rQ^3 + 2uQ^4)}{F_{QQ}} \\
 h_{33} &= h_{33}^o - \frac{8ytK_{15}Q^4}{F_{QQ}} \\
 h_{14} &= h_{14}^o & h_{15} &= h_{15}^o & h_{24} &= -h_{15}^o & h_{25} &= h_{14}^o \\
 h_{36} &= 2ZK_{19}Q - \frac{4ysK_{15}Q^3}{F_{QQ}} & & & & & & \text{morphic coefficient!}
 \end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

Qualitative summary of results:

Case 1: $\text{OP} = \text{S}_1\text{-S}_2$

Case 2: $\text{OP} = \text{S}_6$

Case 3: $\text{OP} = \text{Q}$ (pseudo-ferroelastic)

(Coefficients r, s, t, u, y of eq. (29) are assumed to be positive. Arrows mean jumps.)

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4. Comparison with experimental results and summary

To compare the predictions with experimental results it has to be kept in mind that:

- In absence of external forces RLHS exhibits always a multidomain state in the Ferrophase /01,02,03/, whereby the current predictions base on the fact that the crystal is in a monodomain state of a well defined orientation (ref. to slide 4). This means that the experimental results for the Ferrophase need to be individually considered case by case, whether applicable.
- In the Paraphase such particularities don't appear, and therefore data measured there, are assumed to be more useful to check theoretical predictions.
- The predictions have been derived taking not into account the ordinary pyroelectric- as well as the ordinary thermal expansion- effects.
- The measuring conditions can play an important role. E.g. the elastic coefficients are usually measured at adiabatic conditions, whereby the predictions are done for isothermal coefficients.

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The measured state parameters (S_1, S_2, S_3, P_3) (ref. to /03,05,07/) fit nicely with the predictions, but do not differ for the 3 cases discussed.

The elastic coefficient c_{66} ($c_{ii} \approx \rho v_{ii}^2$) is in fair agreement with case 3, as well as $c_{44} = c_{55}$. c_{33} shows a small jump downward at T_c which can also only be explained within case 3 (see also overleaf).

ref. to Hempel /05/

ref. to Quirion /22/

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The elastic coefficient $c_{11} = \rho v_{11}^2$ is nicely in line with the predictions of case 3 (see also overleaf the data from Wolejko /02/ measured with pendulum device).

ref. to Hempel /05/

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The coefficient-combination $(c_{11}-c_{12})$ follows qualitatively only the predictions derived for case 3.

The dielectric permittivity β_{33} is in good agreement with all 3 cases.

ref. to Wolejko /02/

ref. to Hempel /05/

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Summarizing it can be stated that – as proposed by Quirion et al. /22/ - the *pseudo-proper ferroelastic Landau model* indeed describes best the so far obtained experimental results.

Major arguments are:

- The (small) jump of c_{33} at T_c which can only be explained with this model.
- No linear but hyperbolic temperature-dependences have been experimentally observed so far for the elastic coefficients c_{11} , c_{12} , c_{66} in the Paraphase which contradicts the proper ferroelastic models
- The measured temperature dependence of c_{11} matches well with the prediction of the pseudo-proper model.

To prove the model and to get more clarity on the correct Free Energy Expansion, especially the temperature dependences of λ incl. c_{11} , c_{12} , $(c_{11}-c_{12})$, c_{31} , c_{66} , c_{16} , c_{36} as well as of selected piezoelectric coefficients should be investigated in more detail.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

- /01/ Wolejko, T., et al., *Ferroelectrics*, 81, 175(1988)
- /02/ Wolejko, T., et al., *Ferroelectrics*, 81, 179(1988)
- /03/ Mroz, B., et al., *J. Phys. Cond. Matter*, 1, 4425(1989)
- /04/ Aizu, K., *J. Phys. Soc. of Japan*, 28, 706(1970)
- /05/ Hempel, H., et al., *phys. stat. sol. a*(110), 459(1988)
- /06/ Zúñiga, F. J., et al., *Acta Cryst.*, C46, 1199(1990)
- /07/ Mroz, B., et al., *Phys. Rev. B*55, 11174(1997)
- /08/ Janovec, V., et al., *Czech J. Phys.*, B25, 1362(1975)
- /09/ Boyle, L. L., et al., *Acta Cryst.*, A28, 485(1972)
- /10/ Sapriel, J., *Phys. Rev. B*12, 5128 (1975)
- /11/ Kovalev, O. V., “Representation of Crystallographic Space Groups”, Taylor & Francis Ltd., 1993
- /12/ Kocinsky, J., “Theory of Symmetry Changes at Continuous Phase Transitions”, Elsevier, Amsterdam-Oxford-New York, 1983

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

- /13/ Sirotn, Yu. I., Shaskolskaya, M. P., “Fundamentals of Crystal Physics”, Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1982
- /14/ Toledano, P., et al., Phys. Rev. B27, 5717(1983)
- /15/ Hempel, H., PhD Dissertation, 1886
- /16/ Brugger, K., J. of Appl. Phys., 36, 759(1965)
- /17/ Chung, David, Y., Acta Cryst. A30, 1(1974)
- /18/ Slonczewski, J. C., Thomas, H., Phys. Rev. B1, 3599(1970)
- /19/ Hempel, H., internal paper
- /20/ Bulou, A., et al., Key Engineering Materials 68, 133(1992)
- /21/ Carpenter, M., A., American Mineralogist 83, 2(1998)
- /22/ Quirion, G., J. Phys. Cond. Matter, 21, 455901(2009)
- /23/ David, W. I. F., J. Phys. C: Solid State Phys. 16, 5093(1983)
- /24/ Boccara, N., Annals of Physics, 47, 40(1968)

Annex

Investigation of an Improper Ferroelastic Transition Model (Aizu Species: 4mmFmm2)

Preface:

- Initially a symmetry change according to Aizu Species 4mmFmm2 (/01/, /02/, /03/) was assumed
- This was later discarded (/05/, /06/, /07/), but in current paper a symmetry change $4\text{mm} \rightarrow \text{mm}2$ is exemplarily investigated, based on an improper model to demonstrate the differences between the proper / pseudo-proper and an improper transition behaviour.

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Primitive 4mm Symmetry of the Paraelastic Phase

- 8 corresponding space groups do exist: C_{4v}^i with $i=1\dots 8$ (e.g. ref. to /08, /09/)
- Reciprocal lattice is calculated according to :

$$b_i = 2\pi \frac{a_j \times a_k}{a_i (a_j \times a_k)} \quad i, j, k = 1, 2, 3$$

- At tetragonal lattices there is $b_i \parallel a_i$ ($i=1\dots 3$) \Rightarrow reciprocal lattice is primitive, too
- Now the BRILLOUIN Zone can be constructed
- Change of translational symmetry is described by certain lattice vectors (k -vectors), that need to be in 'symmetric position', i.e.:

$$k_j = -k_j + K \quad \text{with } K \text{ being an entire reciprocal lattice vector (Kocinsky /09/)}$$

- The complete set of those vectors can be identified either by trying out or, more conveniently, by inspecting of Kovalev's tables /08/:

$$\frac{1}{2} b_1, \frac{1}{2} b_2, \frac{1}{2} b_3, \frac{1}{2} (b_1+b_2), \frac{1}{2} (b_2+b_3), \frac{1}{2} (b_1+b_3), \frac{1}{2} (b_1+b_2+b_3), 0$$

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- In order to describe the transition from 4mm to mm2, the k -vector with inherent mm2-symmetry has to be selected via following procedure:

All 8 symmetry elements g_k of 4mm (each represented as matrix $R(g_k)$) will be applied to all k -vectors in symmetric position. The set of those symmetry elements that transform the selected vector into itself or into an equivalent vector (acc. to the relation $k_j = k_j + K$) constitute a point symmetry group. We are searching for mm2!

Example: $\frac{1}{2} b_1 = (\pi/a, 0, 0)$

$$\text{Symmetry element: } 4^2 \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \curvearrowright \begin{pmatrix} \pi/a \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\pi/a \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

- Finally four k -vectors exhibit mm2-symmetry, namely:

$$\frac{1}{2} b_1, \frac{1}{2} b_2, \frac{1}{2} (b_2 + b_3), \frac{1}{2} (b_1 + b_3)$$

- The first two vectors belong to Brillouin-Zone point "X", and the others to "R" (/08/)

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- In order to identify the interrelation between these vectors, the corresponding ‘stars’ have to be determined (e.g. ref. to Kocinski /09/)
- the star of an arbitrarily selected k -vector is obtained when all symmetry elements (of the point group $4mm$) act on it like $k' = Rk + K$, e.g.:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \xrightarrow{\quad} & \begin{pmatrix} \pi/a \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \pi/a \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} & \text{a.s.o.} \\
 = 4^1 & & = \frac{1}{2} b_1 & = \frac{1}{2} b_2
 \end{array}$$

- The corresponding *star consists now of all nonequivalent k' -vectors resulting from this operation*; particularly we get:

Star (**K1**): $\frac{1}{2} b_1, \frac{1}{2} b_2$ (has got two *arms*)

Star (**K4**): $\frac{1}{2} (b_2+b_3), \frac{1}{2} (b_1+b_3)$ (has got *two arms*, too)

Note: All other k -vectors in symmetrical position as mentioned above possess symmetry $4mm$, and therefore cannot describe a transition to $mm2$. Consequently we have to exclude them from further considerations.

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- Star **K1** describes a doubling of the elementary cell in *either* x- or y-direction, or in x- *and* y- direction *simultaneously* (causing a quadruplication of the elementary cell in the ferroelastic phase)
- Star **K4** behaves like **K1** but with an additional doubling along z-direction
- Since nothing specific is known regarding the definitive symmetries of the para- and ferrophase, we will confine our subsequent considerations to star **K1**
- Next step is the provision of the **Full Irreducible Representations (FIRs)** of the space groups C_{4v}^i with regard to star **K1** (all FIRs of the Space Groups are listed at Kovalev /08/). Their dimensions is two because the projective (small) representations are all one-dimensional, but star **K1** has two arms
- The *structure* of the related matrixes are identical for C_{4v}^i with $i=1,3,5,7$ and $i=2,4,6,8$ respectively
- Again for the reasons, that we don't know the exact space groups, we confine the investigations to C_{4v}^i with $i=1,3,5,7$
- In the following we will look at the FIRs (here provided for the generators, which is sufficient)

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FIRs	Generators	4^1	$m[100]$	
D_1		$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	(1)
D_2		$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	
D_3		$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	
D_4		$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	

Notes:

- The matrix *structure* is identical for all 4 FIRs for the space groups C_{4v}^i with $i=1,3,5,7$ and therefore the related Free Energy Expressions (FEE) are identical.
- D_1 - D_4 are active representations, because they are real and the star $K1$ consists of two arms and consequently the Landau condition is fulfilled. The Lifshitz is also obeyed since the projective (small) representations are all one-dimensional (see e.g. /09/).

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Expression of the Free Energy Expression (FEE) with regard to Order Parameter:

All Terms of the FEE) have to be invariant under the action of all symmetry operations (incl. integral translations) of the high temperature phase (para-phase)! We will consider here FIR D_1 only.

- Since the above mentioned 4 FIRs are all 2-dimensional, we have to consider an Order Parameter (OP) made up of 2 OP-Components
- Therefore we interpret the OP as a *vector* with 2 components p, q

$$\text{OP} = \begin{pmatrix} p \\ q \end{pmatrix}$$

1st Step - invariance under the symmetry generators (sufficient):

$$(i) \quad \text{e.g. } D_1(4') \quad \curvearrowright \quad \begin{pmatrix} p \\ q \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} p' \\ q' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} q \\ p \end{pmatrix}$$

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$$(ii) \quad D_1(m[100]) \curvearrowright \begin{pmatrix} p \\ q \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} p' \\ q' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} p \\ q \end{pmatrix}$$

2nd step - invariance under complete translations (translation operator $T(t_N)$):

Vectors describing complete translations: $t_n = n_1 a_1 + n_2 a_2 + n_3 a_3$ with n_1, n_2, n_3 – integer and $a_1 = a \cdot e_x, a_2 = a \cdot e_y, a_3 = c \cdot e_z$ basis vectors of the high temperature unit cell (4mm)

$$(iii) \quad T(t_N) \curvearrowright p = p' = e^{-ik_1 t_n} p = \pm p \quad (+ \text{ if } n_1=2, 4, \dots \mid - \text{ if } n_1=1, 3, \dots)$$

$$(iv) \quad T(t_N) \curvearrowright q = q' = e^{-ik_2 t_n} q = \pm q \quad (+ \text{ if } n_2=2, 4, \dots \mid - \text{ if } n_2=1, 3, \dots)$$

k_1, k_2 are the arms of $\mathbf{K1}$, whereby k_1 relates to OP-component p and k_2 to q . Since the OP-terms have to be invariant **under all possible complete translations t_n** – this means for all values (and combinations) of n_1 and n_2 .

This demand can only be satisfied with quadratic terms: p^2, q^2, p^2q^2, \dots

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3rd step – construction power terms of p and q (n-exponent, δ_i –constants):

!

(i) $\delta_1 p^n + \delta_2 q^n = \delta_1 p'^n + \delta_2 q'^n \rightarrow$ invariant if n even (see (iii), (iv) above) and $\delta_1 = \delta_2$ (see (i), (ii))

!

(ii) $\delta p^n q^m = \delta p'^n q'^m \rightarrow$ invariant if n,m even (see (iii) and (iv))

The Order Parameter Part (F_{OP}) of the Free Energy Expression reads:

$$F_{OP} = A(p^2+q^2) + B(p^4+q^4) + Cp^2q^2 + \dots \quad (2)$$

Remarks:

1. Expansion up to 4th power of p, q shall be sufficient because of 2nd order phase transition (experimentally evidenced)
2. According to Landau's theory is $A=A_0(T-T_0)$ while B, C ... are usually temperature independent coefficients
3. „Conditions of Landau and Lifshitz“ are obeyed (D_1 - D_4 are “active representations”) which allows a 2nd order and commensurate phase transition

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4th Step – Couplings of order parameter (OP) and macroscopic parameters:

- The order OP itself represents a microscopic parameter which is related to a certain point of the BRILLOUIN Zone (at $k \neq 0$ in the present case – “X”-point)
- All macroscopic parameters are directly related to the Γ -point's symmetry (which reflects the symmetry of the high temperature point group under consideration – here $4mm$)
- The Γ -Point of the BRILLOUIN Zone relates to $k=0$
- All Parameters related to $k=0$ are 'per se' and always invariant under complete lattice translations of the high temperature symmetry
- All coupling terms of OP and macroscopic parameters must be simultaneously invariant regarding the action of the symmetry generators as well as of complete translations

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Macroscopic Strain and Polarization (tensor of 2nd rank and polar vector)

Application of projection operator ρ_{ij}^T (see /09/) on a function $f(x)$:

$$\rho_{ij}^T f(x) = \frac{d_T}{|G|} \sum_{g_k \in G} T^*(g_k)_{ij} \cdot R(g_k) f(x) \quad \text{with:}$$

d_T - Dimension of irreducible representation at Γ -point

$|G|$ - Order of group 4mm (here =8)

g_k - Symmetry elements of 4mm

$T^*(g_k)_{ij}$ - complex conjugated matrix elements of irreducible representation

$R(g_k)$ - Symmetry operator connected with element g_k

with $f(x) = P$ (polarization vector) and S_{ij} (strain tensor):

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad S = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{23} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

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Result: 1. Irreducible parts of the polarization: P_1, P_2, P_3

2. Irreducible parts of the strain tensor (in Voigt notation (/10/) and normalized (see also /11/):

$$\frac{(S_1 + S_2)}{\sqrt{2}}, S_3, \frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}}, S_4, S_5, S_6$$

To finally construct the FEE in which **all** terms have to be invariant under the action of the symmetry generators of the point Group 4mm (in particular the elements: **4**¹ and **m**[100]) and under complete translations related to star **K1**.

Therefore a transformation table for all parameters (OP, polarization, strain) has been compiled.

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Parameter	After action of 4^1	After action of $m[100]$	After complete translation
p	q	p	$\pm p$
q	p	q	$\pm q$
$\begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} P_2 \\ -P_1 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1+S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{(S_1-S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1+S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{(S_1-S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ -S_5 \\ S_4 \\ -S_6 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1+S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{(S_1-S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_4 \\ -S_5 \\ -S_6 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1+S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{(S_1-S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix}$

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Now the FEE can be finally compiled:

$$\mathbf{FEE} = \mathbf{F}_{\text{OP}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{P}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{S}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{OP-P}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{OP-S}} \quad \text{with}$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{OP}} = A(p^2+q^2) + B(p^4+q^4) + Cp^2q^2 + \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{P}} = D(P_1^2+P_2^2) + EP_3^2 +$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{S}} = F(S_1+S_2)^2 + GS_3^2 + H(S_4^2+S_5^2) + IS_6^2 + J(S_1-S_2)^2 +$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{OP-P}} = K(P_1^2+P_2^2)(p^2+q^2) + L(P_1^2+P_2^2)p^2q^2 + MP_3^2(p^2+q^2) + NP_3^2p^2q^2 +$$

$$O(P_1^2-P_2^2)(p^2-q^2) +$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{OP-S}} = P(S_1+S_2)(p^2+q^2) + Q(S_1+S_2)p^2q^2 + RS_3(p^2+q^2) + TS_3p^2q^2 +$$

$$US_6^2(p^2+q^2) + VS_6^2p^2q^2 + W(S_4^2+S_5^2)(p^2+q^2) + X(S_4^2+S_5^2)p^2q^2 +$$

$$Y(S_4^2-S_5^2)(p^2-q^2) + \mathbf{Z(S_1-S_2)(p^2-q^2)} + a(S_1-S_2)^2(p^2+q^2) +$$

$$b(S_1-S_2)^2p^2q^2 +$$

$F_{\text{S-P}}$ (piezoelectric coupling terms), $F_{\text{P-S-OP}}$ and other higher order energy terms have been omitted.

The term characteristic for an improper ferroelastic transition is the bold-marked expression in eq. (3). The elastic coefficient related to the spontaneous strain that appears at the transition point is $J = \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)$

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As shown in another article regarding improper transitions within this compilation, essential features are provided here without calculation:

- Spontaneous strain $(S_1 - S_2) \sim (p^2 - q^2)$ (4)

- The transition temperature is unchanged $T_0 = T_C$
- All macroscopic state parameters and coefficients are independent of temperature in the paraelastic phase (if ordinary thermal expansion and pyroelectric effect is excluded from the model)
- The elastic coefficient related to the spontaneous strain looks like:

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As discussed in another article on the Landau Theory, the Order Parameter part of FEE FOP has got different solutions, namely:

<u>Phase 0:</u>	($p=0, q=0$)	Paraelastic Phase
<u>Phase 1:</u>	($p \neq 0, q=0$) or ($p=0, q \neq 0$)	Phase 1, Ferroelastic Phase
<u>Phase 2:</u>	($p=q, q$)	Phase 2
<u>Phase 3:</u>	($p=-q, q$)	Phase 3

Inspecting in eq. (3) the coupling term $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{S}_1 - \mathbf{S}_2)(\mathbf{p}^2 - \mathbf{q}^2)$, it turns immediately out, that no spontaneous strain (ref. to eq. (4)) can appear in the Ferro Phases 2 and 3. Only Ferro Phase 1 can induce such strain, whereby the two options reflect two possible domains.

The solution ($p \neq 0, q=0$) characterizes the ferroelastic domain doubled along y-direction, and ($p=0, q \neq 0$) the other one doubled along x-direction. Along z-direction no doubling is taken into consideration within this model (star **K1**).

Be reminded, that the number of macroscopically distinguishable domains calculates as the ratio of the orders of the point group of the paraelastic phase (4mm, order 8) and of the ferroelastic phase (mm2, order 4) which yields 2.

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From geometrical considerations it becomes obvious (and can be easily proven by application of the formalism to calculate the orientation of domain walls in ferroelastics (see e.g. /12/)), that the walls are fixed ones, crossing x- and y-directions under 45° and run parallel to the z-direction. Pairs of walls stand perpendicular to each other.

As discussed by several authors (see e.g. /14/), in case of improper transitions (which are always accompanied by an increase of the primitive unit cell in the ferroic phase compared to the para phase), the number of different ferroic “terrains” calculates as product of the number of macroscopic domains (here 2) and the factor which represents the enlargement of the ferroic unit cell (here 2). Consequently there are $2 \cdot 2 = 4$ terrains in general which differ in the (microscopic) order parameter. Those are:

$$(-p, q=0), (+p, q=0), (p=0, -q), (p=0, +q)$$

Each ferroleastic domain is composed of 2 terrains which are separated from each other by so called anti-phase boundaries.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

On the other hand, the solutions $(p=q, q)$ and $(p=-q, q)$, i.e. the simultaneous appearance of p and q at the transition point, does not induce any orthorhombic distortion (see eq. (4)), thus the tetragonality is preserved and no ferroelasticity can be observed (i.e. just 1 macroscopic domain exists). Nevertheless, the volume of the primitive unit cell is doubled along x- and y-directions, meaning an increase of the unit cell by a factor of 4.

The number of terrains is therefore 4, which differ in the order parameter as follows:

$$(p=q, q=+|q|), \quad (p=q, q=-|q|), \quad (p=-q, q=+|q|), \quad (p=-q, q=-|q|)$$

In case the star **K4** is considered, the above made considerations are fully applicable with the only difference that there is an additional doubling along the z-direction of the unit cells in the ferro phase. The behavior with regard to the phase transition in general, the order parameter(s), the state parameters and the physical coefficients does not show differences.

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Lattice parameters:

$$a = a_{\text{tetra}}$$

$$b = a_{\text{tetra}}$$

$$c = c_{\text{tetra}}$$

Lattice parameters:

$$a = 2 a_{\text{tetra}} (1 + S_1)$$

$$b = a = 2 a_{\text{tetra}} (1 + S_1)$$

$$c = c_{\text{tetra}} (1 + S_3)$$

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- /01/ Wolejko, T., et al., *Ferroelectrics*, 81, 175(1988)
- /02/ Wolejko, T., et al., *Ferroelectrics*, 81, 179(1988)
- /03/ Mroz, B., et al., *J. Phys. Cond. Matter*, 1, 4425(1989)
- /04/ Aizu, K., *J. Phys. Soc. of Japan*, 28, 706(1970)
- /05/ Hempel, H., et al., *phys. stat. sol. a*(110), 459(1988)
- /06/ Zúñiga, F. J., et al., *Acta Cryst.*, C46, 1199(1990)
- /07/ Mroz, B., et al., *Phys. Rev. B*55, 11174(1997)
- /08/ Kovalev, O. V., “Representation of Crystallographic Space Groups”, Taylor & Francis Ltd., 1993
- /09/ Kocinsky, J., “Theory of Symmetry Changes at Continuous Phase Transitions”, Elsevier, Amsterdam-Oxford-New York, 1983
- /10/ Sirotnin, Yu. I., Shaskolskaya, M. P., “Fundamentals of Crystal Physics”, Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1982

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $\text{Rb}_4\text{LiH}_3(\text{SO}_4)_4$

/11/ Janovec, V., et al., Czech J. Phys., B25, 1362(1975)

/12/ Sapriel, J., Phys. Rev. B12, 5128 (1975)

/13/ Bulou, A., et al., Key Engineering Materials 68, 133(1992)

/14/ Wadhawan, V. K., Phase Transitions, 3, 3-103(1982)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Table of Contents

0. Abstract
1. About Non-Primary Ferroics
2. About Higher Order Ferroic Phase Transitions
3. Observability of Effects
4. Case $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – Ferroelastoelectrics
 - 4.1. Symmetry Change at 200 K
 - 4.2. Landau Modelling
 - 4.3. Calculation of Temperature Dependence of State Parameters and Material Coefficients
5. Comparison with Experimental Findings
6. Summary
7. Literature

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

0. Abstract

$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (shortly ACC) seems to be a candidate for a ferroelastoelectric phase transition according to Aizu's Species 4 / $mmm\bar{F}42m$.

Basing on symmetry considerations and the comprehensive usage of the Landau Theory, the temperature dependences of State Parameters as well as of essential Material Coefficients have been derived. All experimental data measured so far by others are in good agreement with these results.

Moreover, it was theoretically investigated, how the crystal should behave under the action of "external forces" (like electrical fields, mechanical stresses) imposed to the crystal.

It is shown that the character of the phase transition should change from ferroelastoelectric to ferroelastic, respectively to ferroelectric, or even to another type of ferroelastoelectric behaviour – accompanied by all typical properties and temperature dependences. Four respective scenarios have been discussed in detail.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

1. About Non-Primary Ferroics

- Non-Primary (or higher order) Ferroics are crystals that exhibit a certain domain structure – usually as result of a ferroic Phase Transition from a Prototype- or Paraphase (which are identical denominations)
- Order Parameters (OP) have the symmetry of macroscopic tensors (rank greater than 2), e.g.
 - Elastic coefficients (rank 4) – *Ferrobielasticity*
 - Piezoelectric coefficients (rank 3) – *Ferroelastoelectricity*
 - a.s.o /1/, /2/
- At a non-primary Phase Transition the crystal usually lowers its symmetry, the Point Group (PG) changes, but the Crystal System remains (if the hexagonal and rhombohedral system are treated as one system)
- The number of non-primary ferroic domains equals the quotient of the order of the Point Group of the Paraphase divided by the order of the Ferroic Phase

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- Switching from one to another domain state should be possible in principle if suitable external Forces are applied, e.g. at
 - Ferroelastoelectrics - simultaneously mechanical stress and an electric field
 - Ferrobielastics - simultaneously mechanical stresses

2. About Higher Order Ferroic Phase Transitions /1/, /2/

- *Proper* Phase Transitions are those where the translational symmetry is not changed (also called: equitranslational or ferrodistortive) transitions
- In general, proper transitions are related to the Γ - Point ($\vec{k} = 0$) of the Brillouin Zone of the Prototype Phase and the Order Parameter has the symmetry of macroscopic tensor components
- *Landau-Modelling* is in principle feasible, provided there is a Group-Subgroup relation between the two phases, the transition is of 2nd kind, and the Landau- as well as the Lifshitz- Condition is satisfied. (But also transitions of 1st kind and cases where the Landau-/Lifshitz – Conditions are violated can be described by Landau's theory satisfactorily.)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- To describe proper ferroic transitions, consideration of the respective Point Group Symmetries is sufficient
- In contrast, *improper* transitions change the translational symmetry. They are also called antiferrodistortive
- Improper transitions are related to other points of the Brillouin Zone than the Γ -Point, and the Order Parameter is necessarily of microscopic nature and
- *Landau-Modelling* requires to consider the symmetry changes of the respective Space Groups (SG)

3. Observability of Effects

- In case a Primary- and a Non-Primary Ferroic behaviour occurs simultaneously in a crystal, the Primary Ferroicity dominates
- Higher Order Ferroic Effects are in principle difficult to detect
- The energy input needed for higher order ferroics to switch among the domain states is generally much higher than for primary ferroics

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- Therefore the investigation of switching effects of Non-Primary Ferroics should be preferably undertaken in the vicinity of the Phase Transition Temperature

4. Case $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – Ferroelastoelectrics

4.1. Symmetry Change at 200 K

- $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (abbreviated ACC) single crystals have been subject of several experimental investigations /3/, /4/, /8/ as well as of theoretical considerations /5/
- Firstly, Suga et al. /3/ discovered a phase transition at about 200 K, the heat capacity shows a “ λ -type” behaviour, thus indicating a transition of 2nd kind, which was also confirmed by Slaboszewska et al. /8/
- Bansal et al. /4/ carried out structural investigations and found a structural change from $P4_2/mnm$ (D_{4h}^{14}) to $P42_1m$ (D_{2d}^3) at 200 K (at cooling). In notation named after Aizu /9/, the species is called

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

$4/mmm\overline{F}42m$ (within the framework of Point Groups, “F” stands here for “Ferroelastoelectric”)

- According to Toledano /2/ and Kovalev /7/, $4/mmm\overline{F}42m$ can only occur at the Γ -Point of $4/mmm$, which represents the prototypic phase
- Γ -Point means that the transition is equitranslational ($\vec{k}=0$), and of proper respectively of pseudoproper nature
- If a transition is equitranslational than it is sufficient to describe it within the framework of Point Groups /2/
- The Prototypic Phase $4/mmm$ (Symmetry G_0) consists of the following symmetry elements (g_k) :
 $1, 4_z^1, 4_z^2, 4_z^3, 2_x^1, 2_y^1, 2_{[-110]}^1, 2_{[110]}^1, \overline{1}, m_{[100]}, m_{[010]}, m_{[001]}, m_{[-110]}, m_{[110]}, 4_z^1, 4_z^3$
- The **Generators of $4/mmm$** are: $4_z^1, 2_x^1, \overline{1}$
- The Order of $4/mmm$ is $|G_0| = 16$ (total number of symmetry elements g_k)
- If looking just at the Point Groups, generally there are two options (refer to cases A, B below) how the transition can occur:

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- As stated before, in case of ACC it will be sufficient to undertake the theoretical investigations within the framework of the Point Groups
- Moreover it was found (Bansal et al. /4/) that the symmetry G_1 of the ferroelastoelectric phase shall be D_{2d}^3 , which corresponds to “case A”
- Note: Within the framework of Point Groups, cases A and B are equivalent – all following results can be transferred from one to the other case by a 45° -Rotation around the z-axis. We are going to deal with case A only
- The number of possible ferroelastoelectric domains equals

$$\frac{\text{Order of } 4/mmm}{\text{Order of } \overline{4}2m} = \frac{16}{8} = 2$$

- These two domains differ (at the lowest rank) in the matrix of the Piezoelectric Constants h_{ijk} as well as in the Gyration Tensor's Components g_{kl} , which appear at the transition temperature (so called “morphic” coefficients). Above the transition temperature all h_{ijk} and g_{kl} are zero (centrosymmetric prototypical phase)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- Piezoelectric Coefficients' Tensor (Voigt's Notation), e.g. Sirotin et al. /10/

Domain 1

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & h_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & h_{14} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & h_{36} \end{pmatrix}$$

Domain 2

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -h_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -h_{14} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -h_{36} \end{pmatrix}$$

Note: both domains differ by sign in their piezoelectric modules. Switching between the domain states should be possible via simultaneous action of stresses and electr. fields like: S_4/E_1 or S_5/E_2 or S_6/E_3

- Gyration Coefficients' Tensor (Voigt's Notation), e.g. /10/

Domain 1

$$\begin{pmatrix} g_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -g_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Domain 2

$$\begin{pmatrix} -g_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & g_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Note: both domains differ by sign in their optical activity along x- resp. y-axis. This property is also called „Ferrogropy“

- The Symmetry elements that map domain 1 into domain 2 are all which were lost at the transition, i.e.:

$$4_z^1, 4_z^3, 2_{[-110]}^1, 2_{[110]}^1, \bar{1}, m_{[100]}, m_{[010]}, m_{[001]}$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

4.2. Landau Modelling

As listed at Kovalev /7/ there are 10 Irreducible Representations (IDs) of Point Group 4/mmm (at the Γ -Point) - Table of Characters ($\chi_{\tau_i}(g)$)

g_k \ ID	4_z^2	$2_x^1, 2_y^1$	$4_z^1, 4_z^3$	$2_{[-110]}^1,$ $2_{[110]}^1$	$\bar{1}$	$m_{[001]}$	$m_{[100]},$ $m_{[010]}$	$\bar{4}_z^1, 4_z^3$	$m_{[-110]},$ $m_{[110]}$
$\tau_1=A_{1g}$	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
$\tau_2=A_{1u}$	1	1	1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
$\tau_3=A_{2g}$	1	-1	1	-1	1	1	-1	1	-1
$\tau_4=A_{2u}$	1	-1	1	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	1
$\tau_5=B_{1g}$	1	1	-1	-1	1	1	1	-1	-1
$\tau_6=B_{1u}$	1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	1	1
$\tau_7=B_{2g}$	1	-1	-1	1	1	1	-1	-1	1
$\tau_8=B_{2u}$	1	-1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	1	-1
$\tau_9=E_g$	-2	0	0	0	2	-2	0	0	0
$\tau_{10}=E_u$	-2	0	0	0	-2	2	0	0	0

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- As it can be easily shown (e.g. Kocinski /11/) that in case of equitranslational phase transitions ($\vec{k}=0$) only those IDs will lead to a certain low symmetry phase (subgroup of $\bar{4}/\text{mmm}$) where the characters of the symmetry elements of the subgroup (here $42m$) are either:

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_{\tau_i}(g) &= 1 && \text{for one-dimensional IDs} \\ & && \text{or} \\ \chi_{\tau_i}(g) &= 0, 2 && \text{for two-dimensional IDs} \end{aligned}$$

- **Only IDs τ_6 and τ_8 are able to induce the $\bar{4}2m$ - PG Symmetry**
Note: τ_6 corresponds to case A as mentioned above and τ_8 to case B
- Now it will be checked that τ_6 really can induce a ferroelastoelectric phase. To this end it is necessary to calculate the respective reduction coefficients (e.g. /11/):

$$m_E = \frac{1}{|G_o|} \sum_{g \in G_o} \chi_P^{(v)}(g) \cdot \chi_{\tau_i}(g)$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

ID	Ferroelastolectricity	Ferroelasticity	Ferroelectricity
$\tau_1 = \mathbf{A}_{1g}$	No ($m_E=0$)	Not checked for	
$\tau_2 = \mathbf{A}_{1u}$	Yes ($m_E=1$)	No ($m_E=0$)	No ($m_E=0$)
$\tau_3 = \mathbf{A}_{2g}$	No ($m_E=0$)	Not checked for	
$\tau_4 = \mathbf{A}_{2u}$	Yes ($m_E=3$)	No ($m_E=0$)	Yes ($m_E=1$)
$\tau_5 = \mathbf{B}_{1g}$	No ($m_E=0$)	Not checked for	
$\tau_6 = \mathbf{B}_{1u}$	Yes ($m_E=2$)	No ($m_E=0$)	No ($m_E=0$)
$\tau_7 = \mathbf{B}_{2g}$	No ($m_E=0$)	Not checked for	
$\tau_8 = \mathbf{B}_{2u}$	Yes ($m_E=2$)	No ($m_E=0$)	No ($m_E=0$)
$\tau_9 = \mathbf{E}_g$	No ($m_E=0$)	Not checked for	
$\tau_{10} = \mathbf{E}_u$	Yes ($m_E=5$)	No ($m_E=0$)	Yes ($m_E=1$)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- Next task is to check for the Landau- and Lifshitz Conditions:
- The Lifshitz Condition is automatically fulfilled because the transition is related to $\vec{k}=0$
- Fulfilment of Landau's Condition is checked by calculating the expression /11/:

$$\frac{1}{|G_0|} \sum_{g \in G_0} [\chi_{\tau_6}]^{\beta}(g) \stackrel{?}{=} 0$$

with

$$[\chi_{\tau_6}]^{\beta}(g) = \frac{1}{3} \chi_{\tau_6}(g^3) + \frac{1}{2} \chi_{\tau_6}(g^2) \cdot \chi_{\tau_6}(g) + \frac{1}{6} (\chi_{\tau_6}(g))^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\chi_{\tau_6}]^{\beta}(g) &= \frac{1}{3} (1+1+1+1-1-1-1-1-1-1-1-1+1+1+1+1) + \\
 &\quad \frac{1}{2} (1+1+1+1-1-1-1-1-1-1-1-1+1+1+1+1) + \\
 &\quad \frac{1}{6} (1+1+1+1-1-1-1-1-1-1-1-1+1+1+1+1) = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

- The Landau Condition is also fulfilled \rightarrow **ID τ_6 is an "active" representation**

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- Next step is to decompose the Strain Tensor S and Polarization Vector P into irreducible parts with regard to PG 4/mmm

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad S = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{23} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

- To this end the ordinary representation of the symmetry elements $T(g)$ (with regard to the Cartesian coordinate system $(x=1, y=2, z=3)$ and the Projection Operator ρ_{ij}^τ will be utilized:

$$\rho_{ij}^\tau f(x) = \frac{d_\tau}{|G_o|} \sum_{g \in G_o} \tau^*(g)_{ij} \cdot T(g)f(x) \quad \text{with } f(x) = S \text{ resp. } P$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- This exercise yields the following irreducible parts which form the “basis functions” for the Free Energy Expansion (FEE):

Strain S:

$\frac{1}{2}(\text{S}_{11}+\text{S}_{22})$, S_{33} , $\frac{1}{2}(\text{S}_{11}-\text{S}_{22})$, S_{23} , S_{13} , S_{12} respectively

$\frac{(\text{S}_1 + \text{S}_2)}{\sqrt{2}}$, S_3 , $\frac{(\text{S}_1 - \text{S}_2)}{\sqrt{2}}$, S_4 , S_5 , S_6 (in Voigt's Notation /10/ and normalized)

Polarization P:

P_1 , P_2 , P_3

- Next step is to figure out the terms that will constitute the FEE. Each term entering FEE has to be invariant under all symmetry operations of 4/mmm. But it is sufficient to ensure the invariance just for the generating symmetry elements (Generators)
- Following table shows how the Order Parameter Q and the State Parameters S and P behave if the Generators act on them. For S and P this has to be done in the Cartesian Space (x, y, z) and for Q the corresponding ID τ_6 has to be applied

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Initial Irreducible Parts, written as normalized Vectors	after action of 4_z^1	after action of 2_x^1	after action of $\bar{1}$
$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1 + S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1 + S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ -\frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ -S_5 \\ S_4 \\ -S_6 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1 + S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_4 \\ -S_5 \\ -S_6 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1 + S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} P_2 \\ -P_1 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ -P_2 \\ -P_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -P_1 \\ -P_2 \\ -P_3 \end{pmatrix}$
Q	$-Q$	Q	$-Q$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- The FEE describes the dynamics and can now be written (ref. also to /5/):

$$F=F(Q,S,P)=F_{OP}+F_S+F_P+F_{P_S}+F_{OP_P}+F_{OP_S}+F_{OP_S_P}$$

with

$$F_{OP} = AQ^2+BQ^4$$

$$F_S = C(S_1-S_2)^2+D(S_1+S_2)^2+ES_3^2+F(S_4^2+S_5^2)+GS_6^2+H(S_1+S_2)S_3+r(S_1+S_2)S_6^2+xS_3S_6^2$$

$$F_P = J(P_1^2+P_2^2)+KP_3^2$$

$$F_{P_S} = L(P_1^2+P_2^2)(S_1+S_2)+M(P_1^2+P_2^2)S_3+NP_3^2(S_1+S_2)+OP_3^2S_3+RP_1P_2S_6+g(P_1^2-P_2^2)(S_1-S_2)+h(P_2P_3S_4+P_1P_3S_5) \quad (1)$$

$$F_{OP_P} = tQP_1P_2P_3+UQ^2(P_1^2+P_2^2)+VQ^2P_3^2$$

$$F_{OP_S} = WQ^2(S_1+S_2)+XQ^2S_3+YQ^2(S_4^2+S_5^2)+ZQ^2(S_1-S_2)^2+bQ^2S_6^2$$

$$F_{OP_S_P} = dQP_3S_6+eQ(P_1S_4+P_2S_5)+fQP_3S_4S_5$$

whereby all term-factors are assumed to be constant, except $A=A_0(T-T_0)$.
Factor B has to be positive $B>0$.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- The transformation matrix within the “Voigt’s Space” that maps

$$\begin{pmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{into} \quad \begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1 + S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{has got the form:} \quad \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

and can be equally used to calculate the irreducible parts of the elastic coefficients, entering the FEE

- This yields: $C = \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o); D = \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o); E = \frac{1}{2}c_{33}^o; F = \frac{1}{2}c_{44}^o = \frac{1}{2}c_{55}^o$
 $G = \frac{1}{2}c_{66}^o; H = c_{13}^o = c_{23}^o; J = \frac{1}{2}\beta_{11}^o = \frac{1}{2}\beta_{22}^o; K = \frac{1}{2}\beta_{33}^o$ (2)

- The upper index “o” means that the elastic stiffnesses are those at constant Q and P and the impermeabilities are those at constant Q and S .

4.3. Calculation of Temperature Dependences of State Parameters and Material Coefficients

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F}{\partial S_i} &= T_i \\ \frac{\partial F}{\partial P_k} &= E_k \end{aligned} \right| \quad (3)$$

- Solving this system of equations if non or certain values of „external forces“ T_i (mechanical stress) resp. E_k (electric field) are applied yield following 4 selected scenarios. Inserting the calculated expressions for S_i and P_k into FEE gives the Free Energy just as a function of the OP Q .
- The actual transition temperature T_c and the temperature dependence of Q can be derived. Moreover, according to the *Curie Principle* (ref. e.g. /11/) the symmetry of the Para- as well as of the Ferroic Phase reduces if certain “external forces” are applied. Resulting Aizu’s Species are denominated.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Applied External Forces	Symmetry Change (Species) (based on Case A)	Kind of Ferroicity
$E_k=0, T_i=0$	$4/mmm\bar{F}42m$	Ferroelastoelectric (Scenario 1)
$E_3 \neq 0, T_i=0$	$4mmFm_{xy}m_{xy}^-2_z$	Ferroelastic (Scenario 2)
$E_1 \neq 0, T_i=0$	$m_y m_z 2_x F 2_x$	Ferroelastic
$E_2 \neq 0, T_i=0$	$m_x m_z 2_y F 2_y$	Ferroelastic
Field along 45° between x,y ($\rightarrow E_1=E_2 \neq 0, E_3=0, T_i=0$)	$m_{xy}^- m_z 2_{xy} F m_{xy}^-$	Ferroelastic
$E_1 \neq E_2 \neq 0, E_3=0, T_i=0$	$m_z F 1$	Ferroelastic
$T_1 \neq 0, T_2=0$ (or $T_1 \neq T_2 \neq 0$)	$m_x m_z m_y F 2_x 2_y 2_z$	Ferroelastoelectric (Scenario 4)
Stress $ 2T $ along 45° between x,y ($\rightarrow T_1=T_2=T_6=T$)	$m_{xy} m_{xy}^- m_z F m_{xy} m_{xy}^- 2_z$	Ferroelectric (Scenario 3)
Stress along arbitrary angle between x,y, but $\neq 45^\circ$ ($\rightarrow T_1 \neq T_2 \neq T_6 \neq 0$)	$2_z / m F 2_z$	Ferroelectric
$T_3 \neq 0, E_k=0 \rightarrow$ no symmetry breaking	$4/mmm\bar{F}42m$	Ferroelastoelectric

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 1: $E_k=0, T_i=0, 4/mmm\bar{F}42m$, ferroelastoelectric

$$P_1 = P_2 = P_3 = S_4 = S_5 = S_6 = 0$$

$$S_3 = \left(\frac{2DX - HW}{H^2 - 4DE} \right) \cdot Q^2$$

$$S_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2EW - HX}{H^2 - 4DE} \right) \cdot Q^2 = S_2$$

- The behaviour in the Paraphase is included when putting $Q=0$ (4)
- Since the term-factor A in FEE is not renormalized, the transition temperature where Q appears, is unchanged $T_c=T_0$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 2: $E_3 \neq 0, T_i = 0, 4mm\bar{F}m_{xy}m_{xy}^- 2_z$, **ferroelastic**

$$P_1 = P_2 = S_4 = S_5 = 0$$

$$S_6 = -\frac{d}{4GK} \cdot Q \cdot E_3$$

$$P_3 = \left(\frac{1}{2K} + \frac{bQ^2}{2GK} \right) \cdot E_3$$

$$S_3 = \left(\frac{2DX - HW}{H^2 - 4DE} \right) \cdot Q^2 + \left(\frac{2DN - HN}{4K^2H^2 - 16DEK^2} \right) \cdot E_3^2$$

$$S_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2EW - HX}{H^2 - 4DE} \right) \cdot Q^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2EN - HN}{4K^2H^2 - 16DEK^2} \right) \cdot E_3^2 = S_2 \quad (5)$$

- Higher order terms regarding Q have been neglected
- The behaviour in the Paraphase is included when putting $Q \equiv 0$
- Since S_6 is proportional to Q, the transition can be classified to be of *pseudo-proper ferroelastic* nature

- Through the terms dependent on E_3 the term-factor A in FEE renormalizes and the actual transition temperature T_c does not coincide with T_0 .
 T_c depends on the absolute value of E_3 .

Note: $S_1 = S_2$ because of orientation of the mirror planes in Ferrophase (ref. to slide 8, case A).

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 3: $T_1=T_2=T_6=T_i \neq 0$, $E_k=0$, $m_{xy} m_{xy}^- m_z F m_{xy} m_{xy}^- 2_z$, **ferroelectric**

$$P_1 = P_2 = S_4 = S_5 = 0$$

$$S_6 = \left(\frac{1}{2G} + \frac{d^2 Q^2}{8G^2 K} \right) \cdot T_i$$

$$P_3 = -\frac{d}{4GK} \cdot Q \cdot T_i$$

$$S_3 = \left(\frac{2DX - HW}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot Q^2 + \left(\frac{H}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot T_i$$

$$S_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2EW - HX}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot Q^2 - \left(\frac{E}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot T_i = S_2$$

- Higher order terms regarding Q have been neglected
- The behaviour in the Paraphase is included when putting $Q=0$
- P_3 is proportional to Q, and the transition can be classified to be of *pseudo-proper ferroelectric* nature

(6)

- Through the terms dependent on T_i the term-factor A in FEE renormalizes and the actual transition temperature T_c does not coincide with T_0 . T_c depends on applied mechanical stress T_i .

Note: $S_1=S_2$ because of orientation of the mirror planes in Ferrophase (ref. to slide 8, case A).

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 4: $T_1=T_i \neq 0, E_k=0, m_x m_z m_y F 2_x 2_y 2_z$, **ferroelastoelectric**

$$P_1 = P_2 = P_3 = 0$$

$$S_4 = S_5 = S_6 = 0$$

$$S_3 = \left(\frac{2DX - HW}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot Q^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{H}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot T_i$$

$$S_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2EW - HX}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot Q^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{4C} - \frac{E}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot T_i$$

$$S_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2EW - HX}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot Q^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{4C} + \frac{E}{H^2 - 4ED} \right) \cdot T_i$$

(7)

- Higher order terms regarding Q have been neglected

- The behaviour in the Paraphase is included when putting $Q \equiv 0$

- Through the terms dependent on T_i the term-factor A in FEE renormalizes and the actual transition temperature T_c does not coincide with T_0 .
 T_c depends on applied mechanical stress T_i .

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- Slonczewski et al. /12/ derived a compact formalism to calculate the temperature dependence of the elastic stiffness coefficients c_{ij} resulting from the motion of the order parameter, and at constant external electric fields (E_k).
- A very similar formalism is valid for the description of dielectric impermeabilities β_{kl} at constant external mechanical stresses (T_i).
- The piezoelectric modules h_{mn} are those measured at freely moving OP.
- In the following the isothermal behaviour of material coefficients will be derived, taking into account that:
 - the OP Q can freely move
 - there might be additional contributions, originating from the piezoelectric effect if allowed by symmetry

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

$$c_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial S_n} - \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial Q} \cdot \left[\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q \partial Q} \right]^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial P_k} R_{kv} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial P_v}$$

with $\delta_{vj} = \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_k \partial P_j} \cdot R_{kv}$

$$\beta_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial P_n} - \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q} \cdot \left[\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q \partial Q} \right]^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_n \partial Q} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_k} R_{kv} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_n \partial S_v}$$

with $\delta_{vj} = \sum_k \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_k \partial S_j} \cdot R_{kv}$ (8)

$$h_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_n} - \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q} \cdot \left[\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q \partial Q} \right]^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q}$$

- As result for the 4 scenarios the temperature dependences of the material coefficients are explicitly provided on the slides 30-34. The appearing constants are the same as summarized on slide 19 (eq. (2)).
- The equilibrium state of ACC is obtained if the state parameters regarding the 4 scenarios (ref. to eqs. (4-7)) are introduced in FEE (eq. (1)).

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- As result the FEE (eq. (1)) of ACC under defined external forces reads like:
 - Scenario 1: $F=AQ^2 + B'Q^4$ with $A=A_0(T-T_0)$ (9)
 - Scenarios 2-4: $F=A'Q^2 + B'Q^4$ with $A'=A_0(T-T_c)$ (10)
- From this the equilibrium OP-expressions can be calculated:
 - Scenario 1: $Q^2=-A/(2B')$ (11)
 - Scenarios 2-4: $Q^2=-A'/(2B')$ (12)
- As depicted in eqs. (8), for the temperature dependences of the material coefficients also the 2nd derivatives are needed. From FEE (eq. (1)) we get:
 - Scenario 1: $F_{QQ}=2A+12BQ^2+2W(S_1+S_2)+2XS_3$ (13)
 - Scenario 2: $F_{QQ}=2A+12BQ^2+2VP_3^2+2W(S_1+S_2)+2XS_3+2bS_6^2$ (14)
 - Scenario 3: $F_{QQ}=2A+12BQ^2+2VP_3^2+2W(S_1+S_2)+2XS_3+2bS_6^2$ (15)
 - Scenario 4: $F_{QQ}=2A+12BQ^2+2W(S_1+S_2)+2XS_3+2Z(S_1-S_2)^2$ (16)
- For the individual scenarios the explicit expressions for the state parameters (ref. to eqs. (4-7)) have to be introduced into eqs. (13-16), as well as eqs. (11,12). The paraphase is described if put $Q=0$.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- Finally the OP-expressions (eqs. (11,12)), the state parameters (eqs. (4-7)) as well as the 2nd derivatives- expressions (eqs. (13-16)) are the ones which need to be introduced into the formulas in eq. (8) and in the resulting expressions on slides 30-34 in order to describe the temperature dependences of the coefficients.
- Furthermore following additional abbreviations are used throughout the paper to describe the piezoelectric contributions (acc. to eq. (8)):

$$R_{11} = R_{22} = \frac{c_{33}^o c_{11}^o - c_{13}^{o2}}{(c_{11}^{o2} - c_{12}^{o2})c_{33}^o - 2(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)c_{13}^{o2}}$$

$$R_{12} = R_{21} = \frac{c_{13}^{o2} - c_{33}^o c_{12}^o}{(c_{11}^{o2} - c_{12}^{o2})c_{33}^o - 2(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)c_{13}^{o2}}$$

$$R_{33} = \frac{c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o}{c_{33}^o (c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) - 2c_{13}^{o2}} \quad R_{13} = R_{31} = R_{23} = R_{32} = \frac{-c_{13}^o}{c_{33}^o (c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o) - 2c_{13}^{o2}}$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 1: $E_k=0$, $T_i=0$, $4/mmm\bar{F}42m$, **ferroelastoelectric**

$$c_{11} = 2C + 2D + 2ZQ^2 - \frac{(2WQ)^2}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$c_{22} = c_{11}$$

$$c_{33} = 2E - \frac{(2XQ)^2}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$c_{44} = 2F + 2YQ^2 - \frac{(eQ)^2}{2J}$$

$$c_{55} = c_{44}$$

$$c_{66} = 2G + 2bQ^2 + 2r(S_1 + S_2) + 2xS_3 - \frac{(dQ)^2}{2K}$$

$$c_{12} = -2C + 2D - 2ZQ^2 - \frac{(2WQ)^2}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$c_{13} = H - \frac{(2WQ)(2XQ)}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$\beta_{11} = 2J + 2L(S_1 + S_2) + 2MS_3 + 2UQ^2 - \frac{(eQ)^2}{2F}$$

$$\beta_{22} = \beta_{11}$$

$$\beta_{12} = 0$$

$$\beta_{33} = 2K + 2N(S_1 + S_2) + 2OS_3 + 2VQ^2 - \frac{(dQ)^2}{2G}$$

$$h_{14} = h_{25} = eQ$$

$$h_{36} = dQ$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 2: $E_3 \neq 0, T_i = 0, 4mmFm_{xy} m_{xy}^- 2_z$, ferroelastic

$$c_{11} = 2C + 2D + 2ZQ^2 - \frac{(2WQ)^2}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{(2NP_3)^2}{2K}$$

$$c_{22} = c_{11}$$

$$c_{33} = 2E - \frac{(2XQ)^2}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{(2OP_3)^2}{2K}$$

$$c_{44} = 2F + 2YQ^2 - \frac{(eQ)^2 + (hP_3)^2}{2J}$$

$$c_{55} = c_{44}$$

$$c_{66} = 2G + 2bQ^2 + 2r(S_1 + S_2) + 2xS_3 - \frac{(4bQS_6 + dP_3)^2}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{(dQ)^2}{2K}$$

$$c_{12} = -2C + 2D - 2ZQ^2 - \frac{(2WQ)^2}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{(2NP_3)^2}{2K}$$

$$c_{13} = H - \frac{(2WQ)(2XQ)}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{4NOP_3^2}{2K}$$

$$\beta_{11} = 2J + 2L(S_1 + S_2) + 2MS_3 + 2UQ^2 - \frac{(eQ)^2 + (hP_3)^2}{2F}$$

$$\beta_{22} = \beta_{11}$$

$$\beta_{12} = RS_6 + tQP_3 - \frac{2ehQP_3}{2F}$$

$$\beta_{33} = 2K + 2N(S_1 + S_2) + 2OS_3 + 2VQ^2 - \frac{(4VQP_3 + dS_6)^2}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$- \left(2(2NP_3)^2(R_{11} + R_{12}) + 16NOP_3^2R_{13} + (2OP_3)^2R_{33} + \frac{(dQ)^2}{2G} \right)$$

$$h_{14} = h_{25} = eQ$$

$$h_{15} = h_{24} = hP_3$$

$$h_{33} = 2OP_3 - \frac{2XQ(4VQP_3 + dS_6)}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$h_{31} = 2NP_3 - \frac{2WQ(4VQP_3 + dS_6)}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$h_{32} = h_{31}$$

$$h_{36} = dQ - \frac{(4bQS_6 + dP_3)(4VQP_3 + dS_6)}{F_{QQ}}$$

Circled term induces temperature dependence already in Paraphase

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 3: $T_1=T_2=T_6 \neq 0$, $E_k=0$, $m_{xy} m_{xy}^- m_z F m_{xy} m_{xy}^- 2_z$, **ferroelectric**

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{11} &= 2C + 2D + 2ZQ^2 - \frac{(2WQ)^2}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{(2NP_3)^2}{2K} & \beta_{11} &= 2J + 2L(S_1 + S_2) + 2MS_3 + 2UQ^2 - \frac{(eQ)^2 + (hP_3)^2}{2F} \\
 c_{22} &= c_{11} & \beta_{22} &= \beta_{11} \\
 c_{33} &= 2E - \frac{(2XQ)^2}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{(2OP_3)^2}{2K} & \beta_{12} &= RS_6 + tQP_3 - \frac{2ehQP_3}{2F} \\
 c_{44} &= 2F + 2YQ^2 - \frac{(eQ)^2 + (hP_3)^2}{2J} & \beta_{33} &= 2K + 2N(S_1 + S_2) + 2OS_3 + 2VQ^2 - \frac{(4VQP_3 + dS_6)^2}{F_{QQ}} \\
 c_{55} &= c_{44} & & - \left(2(2NP_3)^2(R_{11} + R_{12}) + 16NOP_3^2 R_{13} + (2OP_3)^2 R_{33} + \frac{(dQ)^2}{2G} \right) \\
 c_{66} &= 2G + 2bQ^2 + 2r(S_1 + S_2) + 2xS_3 & h_{14} &= h_{25} = eQ \\
 & \quad - \frac{(4bQS_6 + dP_3)^2}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{(dQ)^2}{2K} & h_{15} &= h_{24} = hP_3 \\
 c_{12} &= -2C + 2D - 2ZQ^2 - \frac{(2WQ)^2}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{(2NP_3)^2}{2K} & h_{33} &= 2OP_3 - \frac{2XQ(4VQP_3 + dS_6)}{F_{QQ}} \\
 c_{13} &= H - \frac{(2WQ)(2XQ)}{F_{QQ}} - \frac{4NOP_3^2}{2K} & h_{31} &= 2NP_3 - \frac{2WQ(4VQP_3 + dS_6)}{F_{QQ}} \\
 & & h_{32} &= h_{31} \\
 & & h_{36} &= dQ - \frac{(4bQS_6 + dP_3)(4VQP_3 + dS_6)}{F_{QQ}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Circled term induces temperature dependence already in Paraphase

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 4: $T_1 \neq 0$, $E_k = 0$, $m_x m_z m_y F^2 x^2 y^2 z$, **ferroelastoelectric**

- In order to properly describe this scenario – in particular to prove that $c_{11} \neq c_{22}$, $c_{44} \neq c_{55}$ and $h_{14} \neq h_{25}$ - the following additional (higher order) terms*) have to be introduced into the FEE (ref. to eq. (1)):

$$m(S_1 - S_2)^2(S_1 + S_2)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad n(S_4^2 - S_5^2)(S_1 - S_2) \quad \text{and} \quad p(P_1 S_4 - P_2 S_5)(S_1 - S_2)Q$$

$$c_{11} = 2C + 2D + m(12S_1^2 - 4S_2^2) + 2ZQ^2 - \frac{(2WQ + 4ZQ(S_1 - S_2))^2}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$c_{22} = 2C + 2D + m(12S_2^2 - 4S_1^2) + 2ZQ^2 - \frac{(2WQ - 4ZQ(S_1 - S_2))^2}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$c_{33} = 2E - \frac{(2XQ)^2}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$c_{13} = H - \frac{(2WQ + 4ZQ(S_1 - S_2))(2XQ)}{F_{QQ}}$$

$$c_{66} = 2G + 2bQ^2 + 2r(S_1 + S_2) + 2xS_3 - \frac{(dQ)^2}{2K}$$

$$c_{44} = 2F + 2n(S_1 - S_2) + 2YQ^2 - \frac{(eQ)^2}{2J}$$

$$c_{55} = 2F - 2n(S_1 - S_2) + 2YQ^2 - \frac{(eQ)^2}{2J}$$

$$c_{12} = -2C + 2D - 8mS_1S_2 - 2ZQ^2 - \frac{(2WQ + 4ZQ(S_1 - S_2))(2WQ - 4ZQ(S_1 - S_2))}{F_{QQ}}$$

*) these terms are not needed to describe scenarios 1-3

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 4: $T_1 \neq 0$, $E_k = 0$, $m_x m_z m_y F 2_x 2_y 2_z$, **ferroelastoelectric**, continued

$$\beta_{11} = 2J + 2L(S_1 + S_2) + 2MS_3 + 2g(S_1 - S_2) + 2UQ^2 - \frac{(e + p(S_1 - S_2))^2 Q^2}{2F}$$

$$\beta_{22} = 2J + 2L(S_1 + S_2) + 2MS_3 - 2g(S_1 - S_2) + 2UQ^2 - \frac{(e - p(S_1 - S_2))^2 Q^2}{2F}$$

$$\beta_{12} = 0$$

$$\beta_{33} = 2K + 2N(S_1 + S_2) + 2OS_3 + 2VQ^2 - \frac{(dQ)^2}{2G}$$

$$h_{14} = eQ + p(S_1 - S_2)Q$$

$$h_{25} = eQ - p(S_1 - S_2)Q$$

$$h_{36} = dQ$$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Qualitatively, the temperature dependences can now be depicted, taking not into account the ordinary pyroelectric and thermal expansion effect, as well as the multidomain state in the ferroic phases:

Scenario 1: $4/mmm\bar{F}42m$, **ferroelastoelectric**

Scenario 2: $4mmFm_{xy}m_{xy}^-2_z$, **ferroelastic**

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scenario 3: $m_{xy} m_{xy}^- m_z F m_{xy} m_{xy}^- 2_z$, **ferroelectric**

$$S_1 = S_2, S_3, S_6$$

$$C_{44} = C_{55}, \beta_{11} = \beta_{22}, \beta_{12}$$

$$P_3, h_{14} = h_{25}, h_{15} = h_{24}$$

(morphic)

$$C_{11} = C_{22}, C_{33}, C_{66}, C_{13}, C_{12}$$

$$\beta_{33}$$

$T_c \neq T_0$

$$h_{33}, h_{31} = h_{32}, h_{36}$$

(morphic)

Scenario 4: $m_x m_z m_y F 2_x 2_y 2_z$, **ferroelastoelectric**

$$S_1 \neq S_2, S_3$$

$$C_{44} \neq C_{55}, C_{66}, \beta_{11} \neq \beta_{22}, \beta_{33}$$

$$h_{14} \neq h_{25}, h_{36}$$

(morphic)

$$C_{11} \neq C_{22}, C_{12}$$

$$C_{33}, C_{13}$$

$T_c \neq T_0$

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

5. Comparison with Experimental Findings

Up to now no investigations of ACC are known where a constant electric field or mechanical stress was applied when passing through the Phase Transition Point.

The experimental data available so far /13,14/ are all measured according to the Scenario 1 (see page 35), under not defined domain conditions in the Ferrophase.

The temperature dependence of the dielectric impermeabilities (which are within Scenario 1 exactly the inverse of the permittivities) is predicted to show no jump at the phase transition point, but a different slope in the Ferroic Phase. This coincides well with the data measured.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Despite the constant (and comparable) slope in the Para- and -Ferroic Phase, c_{33} is well described by the predicted behavior (although the jump is somehow smeared).

$c_{11} = c_{22}$ is less in coincidence with the predictions but similar. The jump (if at all) is even more smeared and the slope in the phases are different - as it is predicted.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

$c_{44} = c_{55}$ and c_{66} show now jump but just a weak change of slope at the transition point. This is in line with the predictions, and can be explained with the smallness of respective coefficients in the FEE influencing the stiffnesses.

h_{36} is in agreement with the predicted behavior. It reflects the temperature dependence of the order parameter. As expected, above the transition point h_{36} is identical to zero ('morphic coefficient').

5. Summary

The transition of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 200 K is a candidate of a classical ferroelastoelectric phase transition.

Moreover, if certain constant external field (e.g. electric field, mechanical stress) is applied to the crystal throughout the entire temperature range, the type of Ferroicity should change. It has been shown that the transition can then be either ferroelastic or ferroelectric, accompanied by all typical dependences (incl. domain structures).

Especially interesting is the predicted temperature dependence of c_{66} in the Paraphase, if an electric field E_3 is applied (scenario 2). But without that field (e.g. “switched off” at a defined temperature) c_{66} should return to the temperature-independent value as described by scenario 1.

A similar behaviour is predicted for β_{33} within scenario 3, where a constant mechanical stress is applied, which could also be “switched off”.

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

6. Literature

- /1/ Wadhawan, V.K., Phase Transitions, 3, 3 (1982)
- /2/ Toledano, P., et al., Phys. Rev. B16, 386 (1977)
- /3/ Suga, H., et al., Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan, 38, 1007 (1965)
- /4/ Bansal, M.L., et al., J. Phys. Chem. Solids (GB), 40, 109 (1979)
- /5/ Hempel, H., et al., Ferroelectrics, 104, 361 (1990)
- /6/ Janovec, V., et al., Czech. J. Phys., B25, 1362 (1975)
- /7/ Kovalev, O.V., “Irreducible and Induced Representations and Corepresentations of Space Groups”, Moscow, Nauka, 1986
- /8/ Slaboszewska, M., et al., Ferroelectrics, 302, 55 (2004)
- /9/ Aizu, K., J. Phys. Soc. of Japan, 27, 387 (1969)
- /10/ Sirotnin, Yu.I., Shaskolskaya, M.P., “Fundamentals of Crystal Physics”, Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1982
- /11/ Kocinsky, J., “Theory of Symmetry Changes at Continuous Phase Transitions”, Elsevier, Amsterdam-Oxford-New York, 1983
- /12/ Slonczewski, J.C., et al., Phys. Rev. B1, 3599 (1970)

Phase Transition & Landau Theory of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

/13/Slaboszewska M., Tylczynski Z., Pietraszko A., Z., Karaev A., Ferroelectrics 302, 55-58(2004)

/14/Tylczynski Z., Wiesner M., Materials Chemistry and Physics 149-150, 566-573(2015)

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

Table of Contents

1. Introduction
2. Basics
3. Symmetry Considerations (Phase II omitted)
4. Landau Modelling
5. Phase Diagram and Stability
6. Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients
7. Discussion of Results and Comparison with Experimental Findings
8. Conclusion
9. Literature

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

1. Introduction

LiKSO_4 (abbreviated LPS) exhibits a series of Phase Transitions (PTs), if temperature (or/and pressure) is changed.

Numerous investigations have been made so far, but there is still no consistent view how this crystal behaves.

The most recent summary regarding the phase sequence is as follows:

Fig. 1 Phase Transition Sequence acc. to /1/, /2/, /3/ (and references therein)

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

The essential findings can be summarized:

- Phase I shall exhibit Point Group (PG) symmetry $6/mmm$ or $6mm$ (see /2/, /3/)
- Symmetry of phase II seems to be $Pm\bar{c}n$ (centro-symmetric PG: mmm) or $Pc2_1n$ (polar PG: $mm2$) (see /2/, /3/)
- No ferroelectricity nor ferroelastoelectricity was experimentally found in the entire temperature interval (see e.g. /4/)
- Ferroelasticity was observed in phases II and V (see e.g. /4/)
- All PTs observed are of 1st Order, PT III→IV shall be reconstructive /1/
- Phases IV and V are not „pure“ but „mixed“ phases, depending on the crystal's „individuality“, i.e. depending on growth- and thermal treatment conditions (see /5/)
- LPS exhibits certain twinning in phases III and IV (see /5/, /6/)
- Depending on the a.m. „individuality“, and actual twinning composition, measurements' results are often less reproducible (or comparable), and the PT between phases IV and V is sluggish (see e.g. /5/)
- The few theoretical models which have been established to describe the ferro-elastic IV–V PT are not comprehensive enough to describe LPS' behaviour in this temperature region satisfactorily (see /7-13/). The most advanced model was proposed by Quirion et al. /14/
- Also, no attempt has been undertaken yet to model the (unusual) series of PTs III–IV-V

The aim of the present paper is to undertake an extended approach to model the phase sequence I-III-IV-V, and to compare it with existing data and temperature dependences.

2. Basics

The following basic assumptions have been made:

1. The Landau Theory will be consequently applied
2. Phase I is assumed to exhibit 6mm symmetry (because of the 1st and 2nd finding above, and because of the fact that PG 6mm is the common supergroup of the phases III, IV, and V (see e.g. /15/). Therefore 6mm (to be precise - Space Group $P6_3mc$) will be considered to represent the Prototypic Phase, as it was also assumed by Quirion et al. /14/ and Willis et al. /11/.
In this context, there is no need to argue about reconstructive transition(s) as suggested in /1/, despite the fact that the atomic displacements accompanied with the III \rightarrow IV PT shall be significant (see e.g. /5/).
3. Phase II will not be considered (but „skipped“) – in order to reduce by far the complexity of the calculations.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

4. All phases of the targeted sequence I–III–IV–V do have the same translational symmetry, thus the PTs are all of the „ferrodistortive“ type where the translational symmetry is preserved, and the modelling can be done within the framework of PGs.
5. No „mixture“ of phases will be taken into account, only „pure“ phases.
6. No kind of twinning will be taken into account for the Landau Modelling – with other words – the results of the following theoretical considerations are valid for the case that each PT leads to a defined single orientation state of the crystal (ref. to following slide).

Note:

Modelling of the mentioned phase sequence under the assumption that the Prototypic Phase exhibits $6/mmm$ instead of $6mm$ symmetry should be possible as well, but then the concept of PTs, induced by „reducible representations“, needs to be applied (see e.g. /13/, /17/). The author believes that in this case the complexity of the calculations is not reasonably manageable, and the expected additional information is assumed to be marginal and will primarily be related to the (theoretical) possibility of polarization reversal along the 6-fold axis (i.e. ferroelectricity) within certain phases (which was not observed experimentally!).

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

3. Symmetry Considerations (Phase II omitted)

Throughout all the phases one fixed rectangular system of coordinates $x(1)$, $y(2)$, $z(3)$ is used (mind the orientation of the symmetry elements in the stereographs below)

Symmetry elements g_i :
(see e.g. /16/)

(PG-Generators in red)

Order G of group:

Number of orientation states $n=12/G_{6,3m,m}$

Kind of expected ferroicity with regard to the prototypic phase see e.g. /17/, /18/):

I ($6mm$)

1, C_6^1 , C_6^2 , C_6^3 , C_6^4 , C_6^5 ,
 $m_{[010]}$, $m_{[-110]}$, $m_{[100]}$,
 $m_{[210]}$, $m_{[110]}$, $m_{[120]}$

12

1

none
(prototypic phase)

III (6)

1, C_6^1 , C_6^2 , C_6^3 , C_6^4 , C_6^5

6

2

ferroelastoelectricity (and ferrogyrotropy*)

IV ($3m$)

1, C_6^2 , C_6^4 , $m_{[210]}$, $m_{[-110]}$,
 $m_{[120]} (=m_y)$

6

2

ferroelastoelectricity and ferroelasticity

V (m)

1, $m_{[120]} (=m_y)$

2

6

ferroelasticity, ferroelectricity

*) Ferrogyrotropy represents an implicit form of ferroicity (see /19/)

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

	III (6)	IV (3m)	V (m)
Number of orientation states $n=12/G_{6,3m,m}$	2	2	6
Lost symmetry elements of PG 6mm - being the twin operations between the orientation states	$m_{[010]}, m_{[-110]}, m_{[100]},$ $m_{[210]}, m_{[110]}, m_{[120]}$	$C_6^1, C_6^3, C_6^5,$ $m_{[010]}, m_{[100]}, m_{[110]}$	$C_6^1, C_6^2, C_6^3, C_6^4, C_6^5,$ $m_{[010]}, m_{[-110]}, m_{[100]}, m_{[210]}, m_{[110]}$
Tensor components in which the orientation states differ (upper index defines the orientation state)	<u>Piezoelectric coefficients</u> $h_{14}^{(2)} = -h_{14}^{(1)}$ <u>Gyration</u> $G_{ij}^{(2)} = -G_{ij}^{(1)}$	<u>Piezoelectric coefficients</u> $h_{11}^{(2)} = -h_{11}^{(1)}$ <u>Elastic coefficients</u> $c_{15}^{(2)} = -c_{15}^{(1)}$	<u>Strain Tensor Components</u> (see next slide) <u>Polarization Vector Components</u> (see next slide)
kind of expected ferroicity:	ferroelastoelectricity (and ferrogzyrotropy)	ferroelastoelectricity and ferrobielasticity	ferroelasticity and ferroelectricity

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

Application of the lost symmetry elements yield following 6 orientation states for phase V. Depicted are the spontaneous values only, calculated e.g. after Aizu /20/:

(1)

(2)

(3)

(4)

(5)

(6)

a) Polarisation

$$\begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}P_1 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}P_1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2}P_1 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}P_1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} -P_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2}P_1 \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}P_1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}P_1 \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}P_1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

b) Deformation

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 & c \\ 0 & -a & 0 \\ c & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{a}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}a & \frac{c}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}a & \frac{a}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}c \\ \frac{c}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}c & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{a}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}a & -\frac{c}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}a & \frac{a}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}c \\ -\frac{c}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}c & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 & -c \\ 0 & -a & 0 \\ -c & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{a}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}a & -\frac{c}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}a & \frac{a}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}c \\ -\frac{c}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}c & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{a}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}a & \frac{c}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}a & \frac{a}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}c \\ \frac{c}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}c & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Notes:

1. In the prototypic phase I (6mm) all spontaneous components (a, c, P₁) are zero.
2. The abbreviations a=½(S₁₁-S₂₂), c=S₁₃ are used.
3. Orientational states (1), (3) and (5), and the related spontaneous strains and polarizations represent the a „stand alone“ PT 3m → m.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

Sapriel /21/ calculated the permissible domain wall orientations for all ferroelastic species. For phase V (PG m) it turns out that there are 19 different walls allowed if we refer to the prototypic phase I (PG 6mm).

(a and c represent the spontaneous tensor components as outlined on the previous slide, x, y, z the coordinates)

$$z=0$$

$$x=\sqrt{3} y$$

$$y=cz/a\sqrt{3}$$

$$x=cz/a$$

$$(3x+\sqrt{3} y)-2cz/a=0$$

$$(x+\sqrt{3} y)+2cz/a=0$$

$$(x-\sqrt{3} y)-2cz/a=0$$

$$x=0$$

$$x=-\sqrt{3} y$$

$$y=-cz/a\sqrt{3}$$

$$x=-cz/a$$

$$(3x-\sqrt{3} y)+2cz/a=0$$

$$(x+\sqrt{3} y)-2cz/a=0$$

$$y=0$$

$$x=y/\sqrt{3}$$

$$x=-y/\sqrt{3}$$

$$(3x+\sqrt{3} y)+2cz/a=0$$

$$(3x-\sqrt{3} y)-2cz/a=0$$

$$(x-\sqrt{3} y)+2cz/a=0$$

Note:

The expressions marked in purple describe the permissible domain walls regarding a “stand alone ferroelastic PT” from a phase with symmetry 3m to m only. This particular PT constitutes a subset of the complete series of transitions I-III-IV-V. In the limit $a \gg c$ they coincide with the green equations which were found experimentally (see e.g. /4/).

4. Landau Modelling

The Landau Theory can describe the PTs that shall be permitted from a high symmetry group. The maximal subgroups in which the respective Irreducible Representations (IRs) exhibit identity representations, represent the allowed low symmetry groups. The low symmetry phases are characterized by the presence of certain Order Parameters (OPs) /17/.

The Landau Theory imposes to look up the „active“ or „acceptable“ IRs only, which can lead to a PT of second order between strictly periodic crystalline structures /22/. This means:

- (a) The anti-symmetrized square, noted $\{\Gamma\}^2$, of $\Gamma_n(k^*)$ must not have any IR in common with the vector representation of G_0 (k^* specifies the relevant star of k-vectors) – *Lifshitz Condition* (absence of asymmetric gradient terms of OP).
- (b) The symmetrized third power of $\Gamma_n(k^*)$, noted $[\Gamma]^3$, must not contain the totally symmetric IR of G_0 – *Landau Condition* (absence of cubical OP terms).

Nevertheless it has been proven that many 1st order PTs can be successfully described within the Landau Theory (see /22/). If the *Landau Condition* is violated, cubical OP-term(s) are allowed and lead necessarily to a PT of 1st order. If the *Landau Condition* is obeyed and a 1st order PT shall be described, as it is the case of LPS (will be shown later), the Free Energy Expression (FEE) has to be expanded up to the 6th power of the order parameter(s).

To get started the Irreducible Representations of PG 6mm need to be inspected.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

Irreducible Representations of PG 6mm acc. to /23/, /24/:

IR acc. to /21/	IR acc. to /15/	1	C ₆ ¹	C ₆ ²	C ₆ ³	C ₆ ⁴	C ₆ ⁵	m _[010]	m _[-110]	m _[100]	m _[210]	m _[110]	m _[120]
T1	A1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
T2	A2	1	1	1	1	1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
T3	B1	1	-1	1	-1	1	-1	1	-1	1	-1	1	-1
T4	B2	1	-1	1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	-1	1	-1	1
T5	E1	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$
T6	E2	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$

Note: The IRs T5 and T6 are originally complex ones. They have been transformed into real, physical IRs by a suitable unitary transformation (e.g. ref. to /25/ and /26/):

$$\text{IR}_{\text{real}} = \underline{U}^+ \text{IR} \underline{U} \quad \text{with} \quad \underline{U} = 1/\sqrt{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -i \\ 0 & i \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \underline{U}^+ = 1/\sqrt{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ i & -i \end{pmatrix}$$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- Since T1-T4 are one-dimensional they give rise to one-dimensional Basis Functions (BF) (one-dimensional OPs), whereas T5 and T6 are interrelated to two-dimensional BFs (two-dimensional OPs).
- The identification of the PG-symmetries induced by the individual IRs can be easily derived by checking under which symmetry elements of PG 6mm the BFs are invariant. This can be conveniently done in the space where the OPs move. Those elements constitute the PGs of the respective low symmetry phases.
- Corresponding investigations lead inter alia to:

IR	Basis Function (BF), written as OP-vector	BF are invariant under action of symmetry elements g_i of PG 6mm	Induced low temperature symmetry (PG)
T2	Q_6	$1, C_6^1, C_6^2, C_6^3, C_6^4, C_6^5$	6
T4	Q_{3m}	$1, C_6^2, C_6^4,$ $m_{[210]}, m_{[-110]}, m_{[120]} (=m_y)$	$3m_y$
T5	$\begin{pmatrix} Q_{m1} = 0 \\ Q_{m2} \neq 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$1, m_{[120]} (=m_y)$	m_y

- By checking the respective reduction coefficients (see e.g. /26/) it can be shown that the IRs T2, T4 and T5 fulfil both, the Landau- and the Lifshitz- conditions. Therefore, neither gradient- nor cubical OP terms are allowed to enter the FEE.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- Next step towards the FEE is to decompose the (ordinary) strain tensor and (ordinary) polarisation vector into their irreducible parts regarding PG 6mm.

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad S = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{23} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

- Utilisation of the projection operator (see e.g. /26/)

$$\rho_{ij}^T f(x) = \frac{d_T}{|G|} \sum_{g_k \in G} T^*(g_k)_{ij} \cdot T(g_k) f(x) \quad \text{with } f(x) = P \text{ resp. } S \text{ and}$$

$T(g_k)$ – operator related to symmetry element g_k

yield the following results:

Strain S: $\frac{1}{2}(S_{11}+S_{22}), S_{33}, \frac{1}{2}(S_{11}-S_{22}), S_{12}, S_{13}, S_{23}$ respectively

$\frac{(S_1 + S_2)}{\sqrt{2}}, S_3, \frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}}, S_4, S_5, S_6$ (in Voigt's Notation /16/ and normalized)

Polarisation P: P_1, P_2, P_3

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- Each term of the FEE has to be invariant under the action of all the symmetry elements of PG 6mm
- It is sufficient to prove this invariance under the action of the “generators” of PG 6mm, namely C_6^1 and $m_{[100]}$
- To this end the transformation properties of S_i , P_k , Q_6 , Q_{3m} , $Q_{m1,2}$ have been compiled:

irreducible part	after action of C_6^1	after action of $m_{[100]}$
Q_6	Q_6	$-Q_6$
Q_{3m}	$-Q_{3m}$	$-Q_{3m}$
$\begin{pmatrix} Q_{m1} \\ Q_{m2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}Q_{m1} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}Q_{m2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}Q_{m1} + \frac{1}{2}Q_{m2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} Q_{m1} \\ -Q_{m2} \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(S_1 + S_2) \\ S_3 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(S_1 - S_2) \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(S_1 + S_2) \\ S_3 \\ -\frac{1}{2}\left[\frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{\sqrt{2}}S_6\right] \\ \frac{1}{2}(S_4 - \sqrt{3}S_5) \\ \frac{1}{2}(S_5 + \sqrt{3}S_4) \\ -\frac{1}{2}[\sqrt{3}(S_1 - S_2) + S_6] \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(S_1 + S_2) \\ S_3 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(S_1 - S_2) \\ S_4 \\ -S_5 \\ -S_6 \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}P_2 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -P_1 \\ P_2 \\ P_3 \end{pmatrix}$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- The FEE, reflecting the full dynamics of the system, can now be written as:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_{OP} + \mathbf{F}_{OP-OP-OP} + \mathbf{F}_S + \mathbf{F}_P + \mathbf{F}_{S-P} + \mathbf{F}_{S-P-OP} + \mathbf{F}_{OP-P} + \mathbf{F}_{OP-S} \quad \text{with}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_{OP} &= A_1 Q_6^2 + A_2 Q_6^4 + A_3 Q_6^6 + B_1 Q_{3m}^2 + B_2 Q_{3m}^4 + B_3 Q_{3m}^6 + C_1 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) + \\ &\quad C_2 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)^2 + C_3 (Q_{m1}^3 - 3Q_{m2}^2 Q_{m1})^2 + C_4 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)^3 \\ F_{OP-OP-OP} &= \gamma_1 Q_6^2 Q_{3m}^2 + \gamma_2 Q_6^2 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) + \gamma_3 Q_{3m}^2 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) \\ F_S &= D[(S_1 - S_2)^2 + S_6^2] + E(S_1 + S_2)^2 + F S_3^2 + G(S_1 + S_2) S_3 + H(S_4^2 + S_5^2) \\ F_P &= I(P_1^2 + P_2^2) + J P_3^2 \\ F_{S-P} &= K(S_1 + S_2) P_3 + L S_3 P_3 + M(P_1 S_5 + P_2 S_4) \\ F_{S-P-OP} &= N(S_1 + S_2) P_3 Q_6^2 + O S_3 P_3 Q_6^2 + P(P_1 S_5 + P_2 S_4) Q_6^2 + Q(S_1 + S_2) P_3 Q_{3m}^2 + R S_3 P_3 Q_{3m}^2 + \\ &\quad S(P_1 S_5 + P_2 S_4) Q_{3m}^2 + U(S_1 + S_2) P_3 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) + V S_3 P_3 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) + \\ &\quad W(P_1 S_5 + P_2 S_4) (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) + x Q_6 (P_1 S_4 - P_2 S_5) + y Q_{3m} [(S_1 - S_2) P_1 - S_6 P_2] \\ F_{OP-P} &= X Q_6^2 P_3 + Y Q_{3m}^2 P_3 + Z (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) P_3 + b (P_1^2 + P_2^2) Q_6^2 + d (P_1^2 + P_2^2) Q_{3m}^2 + \\ &\quad e (P_1^2 + P_2^2) (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) + f (P_1 Q_{m2} - P_2 Q_{m1}) \\ F_{OP-S} &= h Q_6^2 [(S_1 - S_2)^2 + S_6^2] + i Q_6^2 S_3 + j Q_6^2 (S_1 + S_2) + k Q_6^2 (S_4^2 + S_5^2) + l Q_{3m}^2 [(S_1 - S_2)^2 + S_6^2] + \\ &\quad m Q_{3m}^2 S_3 + n Q_{3m}^2 (S_1 + S_2) + o Q_{3m}^2 (S_4^2 + S_5^2) + p (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) [(S_1 - S_2)^2 + S_6^2] + \\ &\quad q (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) S_3 + r (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) (S_1 + S_2) + s (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) (S_4^2 + S_5^2) + t (Q_{m2} S_5 - Q_{m1} S_4) + \\ &\quad u [(S_1 - S_2) (Q_{m2}^2 - Q_{m1}^2) - 2 S_6 Q_{m1} Q_{m2}] + v [(S_1 - S_2) S_5 - S_4 S_6] Q_{3m} + w [(S_1 - S_2) S_5 - S_4 S_6] Q_{m1} Q_{m2} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Note:

The OP-terms have been provided up to the power of six to reflect that all PTs are of 1st order

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

whereby all term-factors, as usual in Landau's Theory, are assumed to be constant, except $A_1=A_0(T-T_6)$, $B_1=B_0(T-T_{3m})$, $C_1=C_0(T-T_{m1m2})$.

- The transformation matrix within the "Voigt's Space" that mapped

$$\begin{pmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix} \text{ into } \begin{pmatrix} \frac{(S_1 + S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_3 \\ \frac{(S_1 - S_2)}{\sqrt{2}} \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \end{pmatrix} \text{ looks like } \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

and can be equally used to calculate e.g. the irreducible (strain) parts of the elastic coefficients, resp. of the piezoelectric coefficients. The results are summarized below.

- The following equalities regarding eq. (1) hold:

$$D = \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) \quad \text{note: } c_{66}^o = \frac{1}{2}(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o) \quad \text{holds in hexagonal Crystals}$$

$$E = \frac{1}{4}(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o), \quad F = \frac{1}{2}c_{33}^o, \quad G = c_{13}^o, \quad H = \frac{1}{2}c_{44}^o$$

$$I = \beta_{11}^o = \frac{1}{\epsilon_{11}^o}, \quad J = \beta_{33}^o = \frac{1}{\epsilon_{33}^o}, \quad K = h_{31}^o, \quad L = h_{33}^o, \quad M = h_{15}^o$$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- The elastic stiffnesses c_{ij}^0 in the FEE (eq. (1)) are those defined at constant polarisation and at constant OPs.
- The dielectric impermeabilities β_{ij}^0 in eq. (1) are those at constant strains and at constant OPs.
- The piezoelectric coefficients h_{km}^0 in eq. (1) are those at constant OPs.
- Moreover, it must be kept in mind that the ordinary thermal expansion / contraction (i.e. the linear temperature dependence of the symmetry allowed strains as well as the ordinary pyroelectric effect (linear temperature dependence of the polarisation)) is not covered by the present model. This must be taken into consideration when comparing the theoretical results with experimental data.
- Next step is the solving of the following system of 9 state equations for the „free“ crystal:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F}{\partial S_i} = T_i = 0 & \quad i=1\dots6 \\ \frac{\partial F}{\partial P_k} = E_k = 0 & \quad k=1\dots3 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- At no „external forces“ T_i (mechanical stresses) nor E_k (electric fields) the OP-dependences of S_i and P_k are obtained.
- Neglecting higher orders of the OPs we get:

$$S_1 \approx \frac{1}{2} \left[-\frac{u(Q_{m2}^2 - Q_{m1}^2)}{2D} + \frac{K_1 Q_6^2 + K_2 Q_{3m}^2 + K_3(Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)}{K_4} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$S_2 \approx \frac{1}{2} \left[+\frac{u(Q_{m2}^2 - Q_{m1}^2)}{2D} + \frac{K_1 Q_6^2 + K_2 Q_{3m}^2 + K_3(Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)}{K_4} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$S_3 \approx \frac{1}{K_4 K_5} [(-K_1 K_6 + K_4(LX - 2Ji))Q_6^2 + (-K_2 K_6 + K_4(LY - 2Jm))Q_{3m}^2 + (-K_3 K_6 + K_4(LZ - 2Jq))(Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)] \quad (5)$$

$$S_4 \approx \frac{2tI - fM}{4HI - M^2} Q_{m1} \quad (6)$$

$$S_5 \approx \frac{fM - 2tI}{4HI - M^2} Q_{m2} \quad (7)$$

$$S_6 \approx \frac{uQ_{m1}Q_{m2}}{D + p(Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)} \quad (8)$$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

$$P_1 \approx \frac{Mt - 2fH}{4HI - M^2} Q_{m2} \quad (9)$$

$$P_2 \approx \frac{2fH - Mt}{4HI - M^2} Q_{m1} \quad (10)$$

$$P_3 \approx -\frac{1}{2JK_4K_5} [(K_5(KK_1 + XK_4) - K_1K_6 + K_4(LX - 2Ji))Q_6^2 + (K_5(KK_2 + YK_4) - K_2K_6 + K_4(LY - 2Jm))Q_{3m}^2 + (K_5(KK_3 + ZK_4) - K_3K_6 + K_4(LZ - 2Jq))(Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)] \quad (11)$$

- The following abbreviations have been used:

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 &= K_6(2Ji - LX) + K_5(KX - 2Jj) & K_2 &= K_6(2Jm - LY) + K_5(KY - 2Jn) \\ K_3 &= K_6(2Jq - LZ) + K_5(KZ - 2Jr) & K_4 &= (4EJ - K^2)(4JF - L^2) - K_6^2 \\ K_5 &= 4JF - L^2 & K_6 &= 2GJ - KL \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Note:

Inserting the equilibrium values of the OPs for the individual phases (ref. to eqs. (16-19)) into eqs. (3-11) give the respective dependences – ultimately on the temperature.

It should be noted that S₅, (S₄), P₁ and (P₂) show „pseudoproper-ferroelastic“- resp. „pseudoproper-ferroelectric“ behaviour, because they depend linearly on the OPs.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- Inserting the expressions for $S_i(Q_6, Q_{3m}, Q_{m1}, Q_{m2})$ and $P_k(Q_6, Q_{3m}, Q_{m1}, Q_{m2})$ into the FEE (eq. (1)) gives the Free Energy Expression F' of the mechanically and electrically "free" crystal just as a function of the OPs:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F' = & A_1 Q_6^2 + A'_2 Q_6^4 + A'_3 Q_6^6 + B_1 Q_{3m}^2 + B'_2 Q_{3m}^4 + B'_3 Q_{3m}^6 + C'_1 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) + \\
 & C'_2 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)^2 + C'_3 (Q_{m1}^3 - 3Q_{m2}^2 Q_{m1})^2 + C'_4 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)^3 + \\
 & \gamma'_1 Q_6^2 Q_{3m}^2 + \gamma'_2 Q_6^2 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2) + \gamma'_3 Q_{3m}^2 (Q_{m1}^2 + Q_{m2}^2)
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

- The renormalized term-factors are now: $A'_2, A'_3, B'_2, B'_3, C'_1, C'_2, C'_3, C'_4, \gamma'_1, \gamma'_2, \gamma'_3$, but A_1 and B_1 are unchanged.
- This yields inter alia the following expressions for the transition temperatures of the „free“ crystal:

OP: Q_6	T_6	- unchanged with regard to eq. (1)	(14)
OP: Q_{3m}	T_{3m}	- unchanged with regard to eq. (1)	
OP: Q_{m1}, Q_{m2}	T'_{m1m2}	- renormalized as	

$$T'_{m1m2} = T_{m1m2} + \frac{t^2 I + f^2 H}{C_o (4HI - M^2)} - 2M^2 \frac{t^2 I + f^2 H - tfM}{C_o (4HI - M^2)^2}$$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- Minimizing of F' with regard to the OPs according to the system of equations

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F'}{\partial Q_6} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial F'}{\partial Q_{3m}} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial F'}{\partial Q_{m1}} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial F'}{\partial Q_{m2}} = 0 \end{aligned} \right| \quad (15)$$

yield the specific equilibrium values of the OPs:

$$\text{Phase I (PG 6mm): } Q_6 = 0 \quad Q_{3m} = 0 \quad Q_{m1} = Q_{m2} = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Phase III (PG 6): } Q_6^2 = -\frac{A_2'}{3A_3'} - \frac{A_2'}{3A_3'} \sqrt{1 - \frac{3A_1A_3'}{A_2'^2}} \quad Q_{3m} = 0 \quad Q_{m1} = Q_{m2} = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Phase IV (PG 3m): } Q_6 = 0 \quad Q_{3m}^2 = -\frac{B_2'}{3B_3'} - \frac{B_2'}{3B_3'} \sqrt{1 - \frac{3B_1B_3'}{B_2'^2}} \quad Q_{m1} = Q_{m2} = 0 \quad (18)$$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

$$\text{Phase V (PG m): } Q_6 = 0 \quad Q_{3m} = 0 \quad Q_{m1} = 0 \quad Q_{m2}^2 = -\frac{C_2'}{3C_4'} - \frac{C_2'}{3C_4'} \sqrt{1 - \frac{3C_1' C_4'}{C_2'^2}} \quad (19)$$

Notes:

The coefficients A'_3 , B'_3 , C'_4 have to be positive and A'_2 , B'_2 , C'_2 are assumed to be negative.

Other Solutions where the different OPs do exist simultaneously would imply to have PTs related to so-called “reducible representations” which are not considered here because their induced low symmetry phases are beyond the scope of this work.

- Next task is to calculate the 2nd derivatives of FEE (ref. to eq. (1)) which are needed later (ref. to chapter 6., eqs. (29-31)) to derive the temperature dependences of the material coefficients
- After creation of the derivatives, the OP-dependence of the strain- and polarization components have to be used (eqs. (3)-(11)) and then the respective expressions for the equilibrium OPs (ref. to eqs. (16-19) above) have to be applied as well

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- The 2nd derivatives of FFE (eq. (1)) for the individual phases calculate like:

$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_i \partial Q_k}$ for	Para-phase	Phase PG 6	Phase PG 3m	Phase PG m
$Q_6 Q_6$	$2A_1$	$2A_1 + (12A_2 + K_{10})Q_6^2$	$2A_1 + (2\gamma_1 + K_{14})Q_{3m}^2$	$2A_1 + (2\gamma_2 + K_{18})Q_{m2}^2$
$Q_{3m} Q_{3m}$	$2B_1$	$2B_1 + (2\gamma_1 + K_{11})Q_6^2$	$2B_1 + (12B_2 + K_{15})Q_{3m}^2$	$2B_1 + (2\gamma_3 + K_{19})Q_{m2}^2$
$Q_{m1} Q_{m1}$	$2C_1$	$2C_1 + (2\gamma_2 + K_{12})Q_6^2$	$2C_1 + (2\gamma_3 + K_{16})Q_{3m}^2$	$2C_1 + (4C_2 + K_{20})Q_{m2}^2$
$Q_{m2} Q_{m2}$	$2C_1$	$2C_1 + (2\gamma_2 + K_{13})Q_6^2$	$2C_1 + (2\gamma_3 + K_{17})Q_{3m}^2$	$2C_1 + (12C_2 + K_{21})Q_{m2}^2$
$Q_{m1} Q_{m2}$	0	0	0	$K_{22} Q_{m2}^3$

(20)

Note:

Phase V (PG m) is characterized by equilibrium values of $Q_{m2} \neq 0$ and $Q_{m1} \equiv 0$ (see e.g. eq. (19)). The expressions for the 2nd derivatives are provided up to the OP power of three. Higher order terms have been omitted. K_{10} - K_{22} are constants.

5. Phase Diagram and Stability

- The FEE - F' (eq. (13)) is principally suited to investigate the possible equilibrium states of the LPS-phase sequence, but the calculations are too complex to handle
- Particularly we are here only interested in the appearance of the phases III, IV and V
- Since ID T5 (refer to slide 12) gives rise to a two-component OP (Q_{m1} , Q_{m2}), but phase V is induced by the special combination $Q_{m1}=0$ and $Q_{m2}\neq 0$, we are going to investigate a simplified “effective” FEE, as proposed by Gufan [27]. Also the terms with B'_3 , C'_3 and C'_4 in eq. (13) have been omitted:

$$F' = A_1 Q_6^2 + A'_2 Q_6^4 + A'_3 Q_6^6 + B_1 Q_{3m}^2 + B'_2 Q_{3m}^4 + C'_1 Q_{m2}^2 + C'_2 Q_{m2}^4 + \gamma'_1 Q_6^2 Q_{3m}^2 + \gamma'_2 Q_6^2 Q_{m2}^2 + \gamma'_3 Q_{3m}^2 Q_{m2}^2 \quad (21)$$

- Minimizing of F' with regard to the OPs according to the system of equations

$$\left. \begin{array}{ccc} \frac{\partial F'}{\partial Q_6} = 0 & \frac{\partial F'}{\partial Q_{3m}} = 0 & \frac{\partial F'}{\partial Q_{m2}} = 0 \end{array} \right\} \quad (22)$$

yield:

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

Phase I (6mm): $Q_6 = 0 \quad Q_{3m} = 0 \quad Q_{m1} = Q_{m2} = 0$ (23)

Phase III (6): $Q_6^2 = -\frac{A_2'}{3A_3'} - \frac{A_2'}{3A_3'} \sqrt{1 - \frac{3A_1A_3'}{A_2'^2}} \quad Q_{3m} = 0 \quad Q_{m1} = Q_{m2} = 0$ (24)

Phase IV (3m): $Q_6 = 0 \quad Q_{3m}^2 = -\frac{B_1}{2B_2'} \quad Q_{m1} = Q_{m2} = 0$ (25)

Phase V (m): $Q_6 = 0 \quad Q_{3m} = 0 \quad Q_{m1} = 0 \quad Q_{m2}^2 = -\frac{C_1'}{2C_2'}$ (26)

The coefficients B_2' , C_2' and A_3' have to be positive and A_2' is assumed to be negative.

Note:

Other Solutions where the different OPs do exist simultaneously would imply to have PTs related to “reducible representations” which are not considered here because their induced low symmetry phases are beyond the scope of this work.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

The schematic temperature dependences of the OPs are depicted in Fig. 2

- To check whether a phase sequence I-III-IV-V is possible at all and the solutions, as given above, are stable, we shall look at the phase diagram
- To this end the formalism developed by Gufan /28/ for two coupled OPs was expanded to three coupled OPs
- First finding is that in fact the phases I-III, III-IV, III-V, IV-V are adjacent (ref. to Fig. 3).
- Determination of the “loss of stability limits” for the considered phases turns out that they do not coincide, but do overlap. This means that all related PTs are necessarily of 1st order (see e.g. /25/) – which is well proven by all experimental findings so far
- As usual for 1st order PTs, the actual phase boundaries are determined by the equality of the FEEs of the concerned neighboring phases. In case of three coupled OPs as in LPS, the PTs are depicted by planes in the 3-dimensional phase diagram spanned by A_1 , B_1 , C'_1 (ref. to Fig. 3)
- Since we stick to the basics of the Landau Theory, we have in eqs. (21), (23-26) consequently assumed a linear temperature dependence of the coefficients A_1 , B_1 , C'_1 and weak or no temperature dependence of the remaining coefficients

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

Fig. 2 Qualitative temperature dependences of the Order Parameters Q_6 , Q_{3m} , Q_{m1} , Q_{m2}

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- Moreover, A'_3 , B'_2 and C'_2 in eq. (21) must be positive definite (because FEE must be positive for large OP-values), and A'_2 shall be negative definite (1st order transition)
- The OP-coupling coefficients γ'_1 , γ'_2 and γ'_3 must be all positive, because otherwise the phase diagram looks different and the phases of interest are not adjacent - which contradicts the above mentioned phase sequence
- Within the phase diagram we have now to search for a thermodynamic path along a straight line passing through the phases of the sequence I-III-IV-V, like a vector:

$$\boxed{A_1 \vec{e}_{A_1} + B_1 \vec{e}_{B_1} + C'_1 \vec{e}_{C'_1}} \quad \text{with } A_1, B_1, C'_1 \text{ being the coefficients from eq. (21) and } \vec{e}_{axes} \text{ unit vectors along the axes}$$

Note: Indeed, this path reflects the practical procedure i.e. the observation of the mentioned phase sequence at changing temperature.

- It also turns out that such a sequence is feasible provided the path-vector proceeds not too far from the origin of the coordinate system – namely above a Three-Phase Point. In particular the following inequalities have to be satisfied (see also /28/):

$$A_1 \geq \frac{(4A'_2 B'_2 - \gamma_1'^2) \gamma_1'}{8A'_3 B'_2} \quad \text{and} \quad B_1 \geq \frac{4(4A'_2 B'_2 - \gamma_1'^2) \gamma_1'^2 + (4A'_2 B'_2 - \gamma_1'^2)^2}{64A'_3 B_2'^2} \quad (27)$$

$$A_1 \geq \frac{(4A'_2 C'_2 - \gamma_2'^2) \gamma_2'}{8A'_3 C'_2} \quad \text{and} \quad C'_1 \geq \frac{4(4A'_2 C'_2 - \gamma_2'^2) \gamma_2'^2 + (4A'_2 C'_2 - \gamma_2'^2)^2}{64A'_3 C_2'^2}$$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

Fig. 3 Section of Phase Diagram

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- If in eq. (27) the equality sign is fulfilled, the equations describe lines in the phase diagram which are parallel to axis C'₁ respectively B₁ where 3 adjacent phases start to coexist. One of the three is always accompanied by mixed different OPs (which is not of interest here)
- Looking again at the path vector and Fig 3. It turns out that the sequence I-III-IV-V materializes if $T_6 > T_{3m} > T'_{m1m2}$. Interestingly, the sequence I-IV-III-V is theoretically also possible if $T_6 > T'_{m1m2} > T_{3m}$. However, series like I-V-III-IV or I-V-IV-III are not possible.
- When coming from high temperatures and moving along the path-vector we shall calculate those temperatures where the vector crosses the planes which represent the phase boundaries of the relevant adjacent phases in the phase diagram. These actual transition temperatures shall be equivalent to those which are observed experimentally. In fair approximation one obtains:

$$\text{I(PG 6mm)} \rightarrow \text{III(PG 6)} \quad T_6'' = T_6 + \frac{A_2'^2}{4A_3'A_o}$$

$$\text{III(PG 6)} \rightarrow \text{IV(PG 3m)} \quad T_{3m}'' \cong \frac{\sqrt{-\frac{3A_o^2 B_2'}{A_2'} T_6 - B_o T_{3m}}}{\sqrt{-\frac{3A_o^2 B_2'}{A_2'} - B_o}} \quad \text{with } A_2' < 0 \quad (28)$$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

$$\text{IV(PG } 3m) \rightarrow \text{V(PG } m) \quad T''_{m1m2} = \frac{T'_{m1m2} - \sqrt{\frac{C'_2 B_o^2}{B'_2 C_o^2}} T_{3m}}{1 - \sqrt{\frac{C'_2 B_o^2}{B'_2 C_o^2}}} \quad \text{with } T'_{m1m2} \text{ from eq.(14)}$$

- Finally the predicted temperature behaviour of the OPs, basing on the above made stability considerations, can be summarized as follows (see once more Fig. 2):
 - Coming from high temperatures, at T''_6 Q_6 suddenly appears with a jump (just like for an ordinary PT of 1st order)
 - On further cooling at T''_{3m} Q_6 suddenly disappears and at the same temperature Q_{3m} appears with a jump, although Q_{3m} could (theoretically) exist already above T''_{3m} (see dashed line in Fig. 2, which shows the typical 2nd order behavior reflected by eq. (25)), if this were not forbidden by stability reasons
 - Q_{m2} behaves similar like Q_{3m} . The equilibrium value of Q_{m1} is always equal to zero

6. Temperature Dependences of Material Coefficients

- The FEE as provided in eq. (1) does have dynamical significance and is suited to derive the temperature dependences of the material coefficients).
- Basing on the work of Slonczewski /29/ and Rehwald /30/, the material coefficients calculate from FFE (eq. (1)) as follows:

$$c_{mn}^E = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial S_n} - \sum_{i,k} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial Q_i} R_{ik}^Q \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_k} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_m \partial P_k} R_{kv}^P \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial P_v} \quad (29)$$

$$\text{with } \delta_{kj} = \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_i \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{ik}^Q \quad \delta_{vj} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_k \partial P_j} \cdot R_{kv}^P$$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

$$\beta_{mn}^T = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial P_n} - \sum_{i,k} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q_i} R_{ik}^Q \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_n \partial Q_k} - \sum_{k,v} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_k} R_{kv}^S \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_n \partial S_v} \quad (30)$$

$$\text{with } \delta_{kj} = \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_i \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{ik}^Q \quad \delta_{vj} = \sum_{k=1}^6 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_k \partial S_j} \cdot R_{kv}^S$$

$$h_{mn} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial S_n} - \sum_{i,k} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial P_m \partial Q_i} R_{ik}^Q \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_n \partial Q_k} \quad (31)$$

$$\text{with } \delta_{kj} = \sum_i \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial Q_i \partial Q_j} \cdot R_{ik}^Q$$

Notes:

1. The coefficients c_{mn}^E , β_{mn}^T to be determined according to the equation above are those at constant electric field, and at constant mechanical stress, respectively. These boundary conditions are usually realized within practical measurements.
2. In equations (29-31) “Q_i”, “Q_k” stand symbolically for Q₆, Q_{3m}, Q_{m1}, Q_{m2} (to shorten the expressions).

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

For phase V (PG m) the following relations hold for R_{jk}^Q which govern the OPs' influence on the material coefficients via eqs. (29-31). Approximations for small OP-values are provided in form of truncated Taylor Series:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_{11}^Q &= \frac{F_{Q_{m2}Q_{m2}}}{F_{Q_{m1}Q_{m1}}F_{Q_{m2}Q_{m2}} - F_{Q_{m1}Q_{m2}}^2} \approx \frac{1}{2C_1} \left(1 - \frac{4C_2 + K_{20}}{2C_1} Q_{m2}^2 \right) \\
 R_{22}^Q &= \frac{F_{Q_{m1}Q_{m1}}}{F_{Q_{m1}Q_{m1}}F_{Q_{m2}Q_{m2}} - F_{Q_{m1}Q_{m2}}^2} \approx \frac{1}{2C_1} \left(1 - \frac{12C_2 + K_{21}}{2C_1} Q_{m2}^2 \right) \\
 R_{12}^Q = R_{21}^Q &= \frac{F_{Q_{m1}Q_{m2}}}{F_{Q_{m1}Q_{m1}}F_{Q_{m2}Q_{m2}} - F_{Q_{m1}Q_{m2}}^2} \approx \frac{K_{22}}{2C_1^2} Q_{m2}^3
 \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

For the phases III (PG 6) and IV (PG 3m) yield:

$$R_{PG\ 6}^Q = (F_{Q_6Q_6})^{-1}, \quad R_{PG\ 3m}^Q = (F_{Q_{3m}Q_{3m}})^{-1}$$

The expressions for $F_{Q_iQ_i}$ are collected in the table (eq. (20)) on page 23.

Now, first the stiffnesses at constant polarisation and the dielectric impermeabilities at constant strain as well as the piezoelectric coefficients are calculated and presented on the following 4 slides.

Note: In the following tables the “Q_i” are those from eqs. (16)-(19) and the expressions for the state parameters are those taken from eqs. (3)-(11)

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

	Phase I (6mm)	Phase III (6)	Phase IV (3m)	Phase V (m)
$C_{11} =$	C_{11}^0	$2hQ_6^2 - \frac{4(NP_3 + j)^2 Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6 Q_6}}$	$2lQ_{3m}^2 - \frac{4(QP_3 + n)^2 Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m} Q_{3m}}}$	$2pQ_{m2}^2 - \left[\begin{aligned} &wS_5 Q_{m2}^2 R_{11}^Q + 4(UP_3 + 2p(S_1 - S_2) + r + u)^2 Q_{m2}^2 R_{22}^Q \\ &+ 4wS_5 (UP_3 + 2p(S_1 - S_2) + r + u) Q_{m2}^2 R_{12}^Q \end{aligned} \right]$
$C_{22} =$	C_{11}^0	$2hQ_6^2 - \frac{4(NP_3 + j)^2 Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6 Q_6}}$	$2lQ_{3m}^2 - \frac{4(QP_3 + n)^2 Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m} Q_{3m}}}$	$2pQ_{m2}^2 - \left[\begin{aligned} &-wS_5 Q_{m2}^2 R_{11}^Q + 4(UP_3 - 2p(S_1 - S_2) + r - u)^2 Q_{m2}^2 R_{22}^Q \\ &- 4wS_5 (UP_3 - 2p(S_1 - S_2) + r - u) Q_{m2}^2 R_{12}^Q \end{aligned} \right]$
$C_{33} =$	C_{33}^0	$-\frac{4(OP_3 + i)^2 Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6 Q_6}}$	$-\frac{4(RP_3 + m)^2 Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m} Q_{3m}}}$	$-4(VP_3 + q)^2 Q_{m2}^2 R_{22}^Q$
$C_{44} =$	C_{44}^0	$2kQ_6^2$	$2oQ_{3m}^2$	$2sQ_{m2}^2 - t^2 R_{12}^Q$
$C_{55} =$	C_{44}^0	$2kQ_6^2$	$2oQ_{3m}^2$	$2sQ_{m2}^2 - \left[\begin{aligned} &(w(S_1 - S_2))^2 Q_{m2}^2 R_{11}^Q + (2WP_1 Q_{m2} + 4sS_5 Q_{m2} + t)^2 R_{22}^Q \\ &- 2w(S_1 - S_2) Q_{m2} (2WP_1 Q_{m2} + 4sS_5 Q_{m2} + t) R_{12}^Q \end{aligned} \right]$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

	Phase I (6mm)	Phase III (6)	Phase IV (3m)	Phase V (m)
$C_{66} =$	C^0_{66}	$2hQ_6^2$	$2lQ_{3m}^2$	$2pQ_{m2}^2 - 4u^2Q_{m2}^2R_{11}^Q$
$C_{12} =$	C^0_{12}	$-2hQ_6^2 - \frac{4(NP_3 + j)^2Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6Q_6}}$	$-2lQ_{3m}^2 - \frac{4(QP_3 + n)^2Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m}Q_{3m}}}$	$-2pQ_{m2}^2 - \left[\begin{array}{l} -w^2S_5^2Q_{m2}^2R_{11}^Q \\ -(4(UP_3 + r)^2 - 4(2p(S_1 - S_2) + u)^2)Q_{m2}^2R_{22}^Q \\ -4wS_5(2p(S_1 - S_2) + u)Q_{m2}^2R_{12}^Q \end{array} \right]$
$C_{13} =$	C^0_{13}	$-\frac{4(NP_3 + j)(OP_3 + i)Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6Q_6}}$	$-\frac{4(QP_3 + n)(RP_3 + m)Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m}Q_{3m}}}$	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} 4(UP_3 + 2p(S_1 - S_2) + r + u)(VP_3 + q)Q_{m2}^2R_{22}^Q \\ + 2wS_5(VP_3 + q)Q_{m2}^2R_{12}^Q \end{array} \right]$
$C_{23} =$	C^0_{13}	$-\frac{4(NP_3 + j)(OP_3 + i)Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6Q_6}}$	$-\frac{4(QP_3 + n)(RP_3 + m)Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m}Q_{3m}}}$	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} 4(UP_3 - 2p(S_1 - S_2) + r - u)(VP_3 + q)Q_{m2}^2R_{22}^Q \\ - 2wS_5(VP_3 + q)Q_{m2}^2R_{12}^Q \end{array} \right]$
$C_{15} =$	0	0	vQ_{3m} (ferrobielectric)	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} w^2S_5(S_1 - S_2)Q_{m2}^2R_{11}^Q + 2(UP_3 + 2p(S_1 - S_2) + r + u) \cdot \\ \cdot Q_{m2}(2WP_1Q_{m2} + 4sS_5Q_{m2} + t)R_{22}^Q \\ + \left(wS_5(2WP_1Q_{m2} + 4sS_5Q_{m2} + t)Q_{m2} \right. \\ \left. + 2w(S_1 - S_2)(UP_3 + 2p(S_1 - S_2) + r + u)Q_{m2}^2 \right) R_{12}^Q \end{array} \right]$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

	Phase I (6mm)	Phase III (6)	Phase IV (3m)	Phase V (m)
$\beta_{11} =$	β^0_{11}	$2bQ_6^2$	$2dQ_{3m}^2$	$2eQ_{m2}^2 - [(2WS_5Q_{m2} + 4eP_1Q_{m2} + f)^2 R_{22}^Q]$
$\beta_{22} =$	β^0_{11}	$2bQ_6^2$	$2dQ_{3m}^2$	$2eQ_{m2}^2 - f^2 R_{11}^Q$
$\beta_{33} =$	β^0_{33}	$-\frac{2(M S_1 + S_2) + OS_3 + X)^2 Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6 Q_6}}$	$-\frac{2(Q S_1 + S_2) + RS_3 + Y)^2 Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m} Q_{3m}}}$	$-2(U(S_1 + S_2) + VS_3 + Z)^2 Q_{m2}^2 R_{22}^Q$
$h_{31} =$	h^0_{31}	$\frac{NQ_6^2 - 4(M S_1 + S_2) + OS_3 + X)(NP_3 + j)Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6 Q_6}}$	$\frac{QQ_{3m}^2 - 4(Q S_1 + S_2) + RS_3 + Y)(QP_3 + n)Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m} Q_{3m}}}$	$UQ_{m2}^2 - [4(U(S_1 + S_2) + VS_3 + Z)(UP_3 + 2\alpha S_1 - S_2) + r + u)Q_{m2}^2 R_{22}^Q + 2WS_5(U(S_1 + S_2) + VS_3 + Z)Q_{m2}^2 R_{12}^Q]$
$h_{32} =$	h^0_{31}	$\frac{NQ_6^2 - 4(M S_1 + S_2) + OS_3 + X)(NP_3 + j)Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6 Q_6}}$	$\frac{QQ_{3m}^2 - 4(Q S_1 + S_2) + RS_3 + Y)(QP_3 + n)Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m} Q_{3m}}}$	$UQ_{m2}^2 - [4(U(S_1 + S_2) + VS_3 + Z)(UP_3 - 2\alpha S_1 - S_2) + r - u)Q_{m2}^2 R_{22}^Q - 2WS_5(U(S_1 + S_2) + VS_3 + Z)Q_{m2}^2 R_{12}^Q]$
$h_{33} =$	h^0_{33}	$\frac{OQ_6^2 - 4(M S_1 + S_2) + OS_3 + X)(OP_3 + i)Q_6^2}{F_{Q_6 Q_6}}$	$\frac{RQ_{3m}^2 - 4(Q S_1 + S_2) + RS_3 + 2Y)(RP_3 + m)Q_{3m}^2}{F_{Q_{3m} Q_{3m}}}$	$VQ_{m2}^2 - [4(U(S_1 + S_2) + VS_3 + Z)(VP_3 + q)Q_{m2}^2 R_{22}^Q]$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

	Phase I (6mm)	Phase III (6)	Phase IV (3m)	Phase V (m)
$h_{15} =$	h^0_{15}	PQ_6^2	SQ_{3m}^2	$WQ_{m2}^2 -$ $\left[2WS_5Q_{m2} + 4eP_1Q_{m2} + f \right] (2WP_1Q_{m2} + 4sS_5Q_{m2} + t)R_{22}^Q$ $+ (2WS_5Q_{m2} + 4eP_1Q_{m2} + f)w(S_1 - S_2)Q_{m2}R_{12}^Q$
$h_{24} =$	h^0_{15}	PQ_6^2	SQ_{3m}^2	$WQ_{m2}^2 - tf \cdot R_{11}^Q$
$h_{14} =$	0	xQ_6 (ferroelastoelectric)	0	$+ t \cdot (2WS_5Q_{m2} + 4eP_1Q_{m2} + f)R_{12}^Q$
$h_{11} =$	0	0	yQ_{3m} (ferroelastoelectric)	$\left[2(2WS_5Q_{m2} + 4eP_1Q_{m2} + f)(UP_3 + 2\mu(S_1 - S_2) + r + u)Q_{m2}R_{22}^Q \right]$ $+ wS_5(2WS_5Q_{m2} + 4eP_1Q_{m2} + f)R_{12}^Q$

- The terms surrounded by circles give rise to expressions that are ***present in the entire temperature region – from phase I through V***, i.e. even there where the OPs are identical to zero (in particular there holds acc. to eq. (32): $R_{11}^Q = R_{22}^Q = (2C_1)^{-1}$).
- Subsequently the *stiffnesses at constant electric fields and the dielectric impermeabilities at constant mechanical stresses* are calculated

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

To this end the terms standing most right in equations (29) and (30) are calculated and result in^{*)}:

$$R_{11}^P = R_{22}^P \approx (2\beta_{11}^o)^{-1}$$

$$R_{33}^P \approx (2\beta_{33}^o)^{-1}$$

and^{*)}

$$R_{11}^S = R_{22}^S \approx \frac{-(c_{11}^o c_{33}^o - c_{13}^{o2})}{(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)(2 \cdot c_{13}^{o2} - (c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o)c_{33}^o)} \quad R_{12}^S = R_{21}^S \approx \frac{c_{12}^o c_{33}^o - c_{13}^{o2}}{(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)(2 \cdot c_{13}^{o2} - (c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o)c_{33}^o)}$$

$$R_{13}^S = R_{31}^S = R_{23}^S = R_{32}^S \approx \frac{c_{13}^o}{2 \cdot c_{13}^{o2} - (c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o)c_{33}^o} \quad R_{33}^S \approx \frac{-(c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o)}{2 \cdot c_{13}^{o2} - (c_{11}^o + c_{12}^o)c_{33}^o} \quad (33)$$

$$R_{15}^S = R_{51}^S = R_{25}^S = R_{52}^S = R_{45}^S = R_{54}^S = R_{41}^S = R_{14}^S = R_{42}^S = R_{24}^S = 0$$

$$R_{44}^S = R_{55}^S \approx (c_{44}^o)^{-1} \quad R_{66}^S \approx (c_{66}^o)^{-1} = 2(c_{11}^o - c_{12}^o)^{-1}$$

Note: ^{*)} OP-related terms have been considered to be small and are therefore omitted.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

	stiffnesses at constant polarisation	„electromechanical“ contributions in the individual phases			
		Phase I (6mm)	Phase III (6)	Phase IV (3m)	Phase V (m)
$C_{11}^E =$	C_{11}	$-[K^2 R_{33}^P]$	$-[K + NQ_6^2]^2 R_{33}^P]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} yQ_{3m}^2 R_{11}^P \\ + (K + QQ_{3m}^2)^2 R_{33}^P \end{array} \right]$	$-[K + UQ_{m2}^2]^2 R_{33}^P]$
$C_{22}^E =$	C_{22}	$-[K^2 R_{33}^P]$	$-[K + NQ_6^2]^2 R_{33}^P]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} -yQ_{3m}^2 R_{22}^P \\ + (K + QQ_{3m}^2)^2 R_{33}^P \end{array} \right]$	$-[K + UQ_{m2}^2]^2 R_{33}^P]$
$C_{33}^E =$	C_{33}	$-[L^2 R_{33}^P]$	$-[L + OQ_6^2]^2 R_{33}^P]$	$-[L + RQ_{3m}^2]^2 R_{33}^P]$	$-[L + VQ_{m2}^2]^2 R_{33}^P]$
$C_{44}^E =$	C_{44}	$-[M^2 R_{22}^P]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} xQ_6^2 R_{11}^P \\ + (M + PQ_6^2)^2 R_{22}^P \end{array} \right]$	$-[M + SQ_{3m}^2]^2 R_{22}^P]$	$-[M + WQ_{m2}^2]^2 R_{22}^P]$
$C_{55}^E =$	C_{55}	$-[M^2 R_{11}^P]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} (M + PQ_6^2)^2 R_{11}^P \\ + (-xQ_6^2)^2 R_{22}^P \end{array} \right]$	$-[M + SQ_{3m}^2]^2 R_{11}^P]$	$-[M + WQ_{m2}^2]^2 R_{11}^P]$

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

	stiffnesses at constant polarisation	„electromechanical“ contributions in the individual phases			
		Phase I (6mm)	Phase III (6)	Phase IV (3m)	Phase V (m)
$c_{66}^E =$	c_{66}	0	0	$-(yQ_{3m})^2 R_{22}^P$	0
$c_{12}^E =$	c_{12}	$-[K^2 R_{33}^P]$	$-[K + NQ_6^2]^2 R_{33}^P$	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} -y^2 Q_{3m}^2 R_{11}^P \\ +(K + QQ_{3m}^2)^2 R_{33}^P \end{array} \right]$	$-[K + UQ_{m2}^2]^2 R_{33}^P$
$c_{13}^E =$	c_{13}	$-[KLR_{33}^P]$	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} (K + NQ_6^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (L + OQ_6^2) R_{33}^P \end{array} \right]$	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} (K + QQ_{3m}^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (L + RQ_{3m}^2) R_{33}^P \end{array} \right]$	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} (K + UQ_{m2}^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (L + VQ_{m2}^2) R_{33}^P \end{array} \right]$
$c_{23}^E =$	c_{23}	$-[KLR_{33}^P]$	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} (K + NQ_6^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (L + OQ_6^2) R_{33}^P \end{array} \right]$	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} (K + QQ_{3m}^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (L + RQ_{3m}^2) R_{33}^P \end{array} \right]$	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} (K + UQ_{m2}^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (L + VQ_{m2}^2) R_{33}^P \end{array} \right]$
$c_{15}^E =$	c_{15}	0	0	$-\left[\begin{array}{l} (yQ_{3m}) \cdot \\ \cdot (M + SQ_{3m}^2) R_{11}^P \end{array} \right]$	0

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

	Impermeabilities at constant strain	„electromechanical“ contributions in the individual phases			
		Phase I (6mm)	Phase III (6)	Phase IV (3m)	Phase V (m)
$\beta_{11}^T =$	β_{11}	$-[M^2 R_{55}^S]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} (xQ_6)^2 R_{44}^S \\ + (M + PQ_6^2)^2 R_{55}^S \end{array} \right]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} (yQ_{3m})^2 \cdot \\ \cdot (R_{11}^S + R_{22}^S - 2R_{12}^S) \\ + (M + SQ_{3m}^2)^2 R_{55}^S \end{array} \right]$	$- [(M + WQ_{m2}^2)^2 R_{55}^S]$
$\beta_{22}^T =$	β_{22}	$-[M^2 R_{44}^S]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} (M + PQ_6^2)^2 R_{44}^S \\ + (xQ_6)^2 R_{55}^S \end{array} \right]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} (M + SQ_{3m}^2)^2 R_{44}^S \\ + (yQ_{3m})^2 R_{66}^S \end{array} \right]$	$- [(M + WQ_{m2}^2)^2 R_{44}^S]$
$\beta_{33}^T =$	β_{33}	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} K^2 \cdot \\ \cdot (R_{11}^S + R_{22}^S + 2R_{12}^S) \\ + L^2 R_{33}^S \\ + 2KL(R_{13}^S + R_{23}^S) \end{array} \right]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} (K + NQ_6^2)^2 \cdot \\ \cdot (R_{11}^S + R_{22}^S + 2R_{12}^S) \\ + (L + OQ_6^2)^2 R_{33}^S \\ + 2(K + NQ_6^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (L + OQ_6^2)(R_{13}^S + R_{23}^S) \end{array} \right]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} (K + QQ_{3m}^2)^2 \cdot \\ \cdot (R_{11}^S + R_{22}^S + 2R_{12}^S) \\ + (L + RQ_{3m}^2)^2 R_{33}^S \\ + 2(K + QQ_{3m}^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (L + RQ_{3m}^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (R_{13}^S + R_{23}^S) \end{array} \right]$	$- \left[\begin{array}{l} (K + UQ_{m2}^2)^2 \cdot \\ \cdot (R_{11}^S + R_{22}^S + 2R_{12}^S) \\ + (L + VQ_{m2}^2)^2 R_{33}^S \\ + 2(K + UQ_{m2}^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (L + VQ_{m2}^2) \cdot \\ \cdot (R_{13}^S + R_{23}^S) \end{array} \right]$

7. Discussion of Results and Comparison with Experimental Findings

- In this chapter the *qualitative* temperature behaviour of the state parameters and material coefficients will be depicted and compared with experimental findings
- In order to do this into the expressions of the previous slides the precise dependences have to be introduced, i.e. for strains eqs. (3)-(8), for polarisations eqs. (9)-(11), for R_{ij}^Q eqs. (32), for R_{ij}^S and R_{ij}^P eq. (33). Everywhere where the OPs appear, their temperature dependences have to be inserted from eqs. (16)-(19).
- It must be noted here that the curves shall be correct for phases III and IV, because there are no ferroelectric nor ferroelastic domains, but care has to be taken because ferroelastolectricity respectively ferrobielasticity are present which do have an effect on certain material coefficients
- experimentally found behaviour for phase V is influenced by the always existing multidomain state and can therefore hardly be compared with theoretical predictions. Only exemptions are the “longitudinal properties” along the c-axis, because the domains behave all equally in this direction.
- Nevertheless the predicted behaviour in phase V is shown as well – but under the assumption, that the crystal undergoes the transition IV \rightarrow V to a (defined) single domain state as stipulated earlier (see slide 6)

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

- The temperature dependences around the I→III PT are not shown, because phase II has been omitted, and therefore no such PT (i.e. skipping of phase II) can materialize in practical experiments.
- Wherever possible, experimental data measured at increasing temperatures have been chosen, because those data are more reproducible than in cooling runs (see e.g. /5/)
- Some more remarks have to be made:
 - Since some coupling terms of the general form $X_*(\text{OP})^2$ appear in FEE (see eq. (1)), the affected material coefficients (c_{ij} , β_{kl} , h_{mn}) show jumps downwards at the transition temperatures (T''_6 , T''_{3m} , T''_{m1m2}) where the respective OPs appear suddenly (e.g. on cooling).
 - Also the opposite is true: If at a transition temperature an OP becomes unstable (i.e. disappears) the jump of the material coefficient is directed upwards.
 - It has been shown that exactly at T''_6 Q_6 disappears and Q_{3m} appears (the same applies at T''_{m1m2} for Q_{3m} and Q_{m2}). The accompanied jumps of the coefficients compete and yield a “resulting” jump which can be positive or negative or even zero (latter in case of exact compensation of contributing jumps)
 - Precise predictions would require to know the signs and values of the relevant term-factors of FEE (see eq. (1))

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO₄

- Another comment has to be made if stiffnesses c_{ij} are compared with compliances s_{ij} , The relation $s_{ii}=1/c_{ii}$ holds only if all c_{ij} with $i \neq j$ are equal zero (or very small). The relation between impermeabilities and permittivities is analogue.
- The relation between the piezocoefficients h_{mj} and the usually measured d_{ki} reads like /31/:

$$d_{nj} = h_{mi} s_{ij}^E \varepsilon_{mn}^S \quad \text{resp.} \quad h_{nj} = d_{mi} c_{ij}^E \beta_{nm}^S \quad (34)$$

- As mentioned earlier the present calculations do not cover the ordinary thermal dilatation/contraction nor the ordinary pyroelectric effect.
- Since in particular the signs of the majority of the term-factors of FEE (see eq. (1)) are not known, different temperature dependences - depending on the signs chosen – are possible. Wherever reliable experimental data are available, only those signs have been considered, where the curve fit is the best.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

Taken from /32/

- There is a good agreement between predicted and experimental data (see also /5/ and /33/)
- Since strain S_5 linearly depends on OP Q_{m2} (see eq. (13)), pseudoproper ferroelastic behaviour should be observed in phase V
- As found in /5/, LPS is monoclinic, but *pseudo-orthorhombic* in phase V. The angle between the polar c -axis and axes a (and b) amounts to $90^\circ \rightarrow$ therefore strain S_5 is in fact zero (but can theoretically be unequal zero as schematically depicted above).
- As an explanation from the phenomenological point of view it can be assumed that the responsible coupling coefficients t and f in eq. (1) and in eq. (7) are very small.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

Taken from /34/

- There is a good agreement between predicted and experimental data
- Since polarisation P_1 linearly depends on OP Q_{m2} (see eq. (9)), pseudoproper ferroelectric behaviour should be observed in phase V as well
- As found experimentally in /12/, /35/, LPS doesn't exhibit any spontaneous polarisation component P_1 nor a P_1 - (or P_3 -) polarisation switching in phase V
- Nevertheless, P_1 is allowed by group theory (similar like for S_5 on the previous slide)
- As an explanation from the phenomenological point of view it can be assumed that the coupling coefficients t and f in eq. (1) and in eq. (9) are very small.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

Taken from /8/

Taken from /12/

- Relation $\epsilon_{ij}=1/\beta_{ij}$ holds exactly for phases III, IV, but in phase V only if $\beta_{ij} \ll 1$ for $i \neq j$
- There is a good agreement regarding ϵ_{33} , but the experimentally found slope in phase IV is not predicted. Experiments by others (see /35/, /12/) revealed no slope in phase IV nor any singularity at the PT IV \leftrightarrow III.
- There is some principal agreement regarding ϵ_{11} and ϵ_{22} , but the predicted temperature dependence (with negative overall slope) above (!) T''_{m1m2} has never been observed experimentally.
- A possible explanation is that coefficient f in eq. (1) and in the respective expressions on slide no. 37 is very small, as already assumed to explain the observed behaviour of P_1

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

- Depicted curves for the h_{ij} coefficients are just possible examples. Depending on the magnitude and sign of the relevant term-factors (which are not known from theory) other curve-forms are possible as well (ref. to comments on slides nos. 44 and 45).
- Also it must be noted that usually the piezocoefficients d_{ij} are practically measured, which cannot be directly compared with the h_{ij} (see eq. (34)).
- Interesting is the fact, that h_{15} and h_{24} should be temperature dependent (with a positive overall slope) already in phases (I), III and IV, i.e. above T''_{m1m2} .
- No measurable slope would again imply that the coupling coefficients f and t in eq. (1) are very small.
- Experimentally measured piezocoefficients d_{ij} can be found e.g. in /12/, /36/.

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

Taken from /14/

- There is a good agreement for c_{11} , c_{22} – meaning that the observed dependences can be described by the formulas derived earlier.
- c_{33} shows at T''_{3m} a jump which can be explained if, on e.g. heating, at T''_{3m} Q_6 appears accompanied by a jump downwards and Q_{3m} disappears accompanied by a jump upwards. Obviously the first dominates and the resulting jump is directed downwards (see also explanation on slide no. 44)
- The same explanation holds in principle for c_{13} and c_{23} .

Taken from /37/

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

- There is less agreement for c_{44} , c_{55} which should show a positive overall slope in phases (I), III and IV, i.e. above T''_{m1m2} . Only possibility to explain the negative slope is that coefficient t is very small, and the terms with Q^2 dominate, i.e. they provide negative (slope) contributions – with coefficients k , o (see eq. (1) being positive).
- The direction of the experimentally found jump at T''_{3m} can be explained similarly as for c_{33} .
- The predicted jump at T''_{m1m2} was experimentally not observed, indicating small values of coefficients t , f and opposite signs of coefficients o and s .

- c_{66} is in fair agreement with measured data
- The negative slope above T''_{3m} (i.e. in phase III) is explainable within the model if coefficient h is positive definite

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

- The dependence of c_{12} is closely related to those of c_{11} , c_{22} , c_{66} (ref. to the expressions derived earlier)
- c_{15} is a „morphic“ coefficient, i.e. it is zero above T''_{3m} . It fits well with RUS measurements /11/ but it must be noted that another coordinate system (rotated by 30° around c-axis) was used. This means that our c_{15} coincides with c_{14} of /11/.

Note: There are numerous experimental data regarding the elastic stiffnesses of LPS available in the literature, e.g. /38/-/41/, but many of them are contradictory.

8. Conclusion

Basing on Symmetry Considerations, the Landau Theory of Phase Transitions and the related Phase Diagram an attempt has been made to theoretically describe the phase sequence of LPS.

It turned out that the majority of experimental data found up to now can be satisfactorily explained and even reasonably fitted qualitatively.

The predicted appearances of S_5 and P_1 in phase V are not evidenced by experiments.

Also the expected overall temperature dependences of the material the coefficients ϵ_{11} , ϵ_{22} , c_{44} , c_{55} in phases I, III and IV have not been experimentally observed.

These substantial deviations can be explained qualitatively well with the model if certain coefficients in the Free Energy Expansion are assumed to be very small.

9. Literature

- /1/ Perpetuo G. J. et al., Phys. Rev. B45, 5163 (1992)
- /2/ Scherf, Ch., Dissertation, RWTH Aachen, 2000
- /3/ Park, H. M., et al., Acta Cryst. A61, C373 (2005)
- /4/ Sorge, G. et al., phys. stat sol. (a)97, 431 (1986)
- /5/ Bhakay-Tamhane, S. et al., Phase Transitions 35, 75 (1991)
- /6/ Klapper, H. et al., Acta Cryst. B43, 147 (1987)
- /7/ Zeks B., et al., Phys. Stat. Sol. b122, 399 (1984)
- /8/ Fujimoto S., et al., J. Phys. D: Appl. Physics 18, 1878 (1985)
- /9/ An Tu et al., Solid State Commun., 61, 1 (1987)
- /10/ Mroz B., et al., J. Phys.: Condensed Matter 1, 5965 (1989)
- /11/ Willis F., et al., Phys. Rev. B54, 9077 (1996)
- /12/ Sorge, G., Hempel, H., Ferroelectrics 81, 167 (1988)
- /13/ Hempel, H., phys. stat. sol. (b)163, K77 (1991)
- /14/ Quirion G., J. Phys. C: Condensed Matter 15, 4979 (2003)

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

- /15/ Boyle L. L., et al. Acta Cryst. A28, 485 (1972)
- /16/ Sirotin, Yu. I., Shaskolskaya, M. P., "Fundamentals of Crystal Physics", Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1982
- /17/ Janovec V., et al., Czech J. Phys. B25, 1362 (1975)
- /18/ Toledano P., Toledano J.-C., Phys. Rev. B16, 386 (1977)
- /19/ Wadhawan, V. K., Phase Transitions 3, 3 (1982)
- /20/ Aizu, K., J. Phys. Soc. Japan 28, 706 (1970)
- /21/ Sapriel, J., Phys. Rev. B12, 5128 (1975)
- /22/ Toledano P., Toledano J.-C., "The Landau Theory of Phase Transitions", World Scientific Publishing, 1987
- /23/ Kovalev, O. V., "Representation of Crystallographic Space Groups", Taylor & Francis Ltd., 1993
- /24/ Cracknell, C. J., Bradley, A. P., "The Mathematical Theory of Symmetry in Solids", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1972
- /25/ Izyumov Yu. A., Syromyatnikov V. N., "Phase Transitions and Crystal Symmetry", Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht / Boston / London, 1990

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

- /26/ Kocinsky, J., "Theory of Symmetry Changes at Continuous Phase Transitions", Elsevier, Amsterdam-Oxford-New York, 1983
- /27/ Gufan et al., Sov. Solid State Phys. 22, 951 (1980)
- /28/ Gufan et al., Sov. Solid State Phys. 22, 270 (1980)
- /29/ Slonczewski, J. C. and Thomas, H., Phys. Rev. B1, 3599 (1970)
- /30/ Rehwald, W., Adv. In Physics, Vol. 22, 721 (1973)
- /31/ Xu, Y., „Ferroelectric Materials and Their Applications“, Elsevier Science Publishers, 1991
- /32/ Tomaszewski, P. E., et al., Phase Transitions 4, 37 (1983)
- /33/ Desert, A. et al., J. Phys. Cond. Matter 7, 8445 (1995)
- /34/ Brezewski, T., et al., Ferroelectrics 33, 9 (1981)
- /35/ Cach, R., et al., Ferroelectrics 53, 337 (1984)
- /36/ Mroz, B., et al., Ferroelectrics 42, 71 (1982)
- /37/ Kabelka, H., et al., Ferroelectrics 88, 93 (1988)
- /38/ Borisov, B. F., et al., phys. stat. sol. (b)199, 51 (1997)

Phase Sequence and Landau Theory of LiKSO_4

/39/ Drozdowski, M., et al. *Ferroelectrics* 77, 47 (1988)

/40/ Ganot, F., et al., *J. Phys. C: Solid State Phys.* 20, 491 (1987)

/41/ Kassem, E. M., et al., *Acta Physica Polonica* A63, 449 (1983)